
D4.27 4th periodic report on JIPs

WP4 Joint Integrative Projects

Responsible Partner: SVA

Contributing partners: INSA

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This programme has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Starting Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	D4.27 4th periodic report on JIPs
WP and Task	WP4; Task 4.2.2
Leader	Karin Artursson, SVA
Other contributors	Manuela Caniça, INSA, Elina Lahti, SVA
Due month of the report	M51
Actual submission month	M51
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: 31-Mar-22
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default)</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the: Commission Services).</i>	PU See updated Grant Agreement
Dissemination Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s):

Contents

1.	Introduction.....	5
2.	Summary of the performance of the Joint Integrative Projects	7
2.1.	Milestones and deliverables.....	7
2.2.	Publications	8
2.3.	Interactions with other JRPs/JIPs, European, international and national projects.....	11
2.4.	Data Management Plan (DMP)	13
2.5.	Critical risks.....	13
3.	JIP01 – ORION.....	14
3.1.	Summary of the work carried out	14
3.2.	Work carried out in the JIP, scientific results, and integrative outcomes.....	15
3.3.	Project self-assessment.....	27
3.4.	Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables	28
3.5.	Publications and additional outputs.....	32
3.6.	One Health impact.....	38
3.7.	Data Management Plan.....	40
4.	JIP2 - COHESIVE	41
4.1.	Summary of the work carried out	41
4.2.	Work carried out in the JIP, scientific results, and integrative outcomes.....	43
4.3.	Project self-assessment.....	53
4.4.	Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables	56
4.5.	Publications and additional outputs.....	64
4.6.	One Health Impact	69
4.7.	Data Management Plan.....	73
5.	JIP3 - CARE	73
5.1.	Summary of the work carried out	73
5.2.	Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes.....	74
5.3.	Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables	82
5.4.	Publications and additional outputs.....	86
5.5.	List of critical risks	88
6.	JIP4 – OH-HARMONY-CAP	89

6.1.	Summary of the work carried out	89
6.2.	Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes.....	90
6.3.	Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables	103
6.4.	Publications and additional outputs.....	106
6.5.	Contacts and co-operation with national or international projects, organisations (e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), networks, or national ministries.....	108
6.6	List of critical risks	109
7.	JIP5 - MATRIX.....	110
7.1.	Summary of the work carried out	110
7.2.	Work carried out in the JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes.....	111
7.3.	Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables	124
7.4.	Publications and additional outputs.....	128
7.5.	On-going and planned collaborations with national or European projects or networks	130
7.6.	Data Management Plan.....	133
7.7.	List of critical risks	133
8.	JIP6 - COVRIN.....	135
8.1.	Summary of the work carried out	135
8.2.	Work carried out in the JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes.....	135
8.3.	Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables	146
8.4.	Publications and additional outputs.....	150
8.5.	On-going and planned collaborations with national or European projects or networks	151
8.6.	Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors	152
8.7.	List of critical risks	155

1. Introduction

The joint core mission of partners in the One Health EJP is to provide expertise and services to prevent, detect and respond to societal challenges such as foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats shared by people and animals. The chain of actions from prevention via detection to response defines a series of capacities that need to be maintained and kept up to date by these expert institutes. These pertain to their capacity to design and implement surveillance activities, develop high quality laboratory methods, access relevant reference materials and data, as well as to their ability to interpret and communicate surveillance information in a timely and appropriate manner, as well as to provide guidance to risk managers about relevant actions, both for prevention and response. Similarly, the purpose of integrative activities and projects within the OHEJP is to strengthen the joint preparedness of partners to prevent, detect and respond to hazards within their joint remit, both nationally and in collaboration within other EU institutes and -agencies. Due to the legislated landscape in which OHEJP partners operate, and as a result of the close relationship and collaboration with the key EU stakeholders of OHEJP, ECDC and EFSA, there are already many strategies, initiatives, activities and systems in place to develop the capacity to respond to joint hazards within the field of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats.

The objective of Joint Integrative Projects (JIPs) is not to replicate, but to strengthen existing, well-functioning systems. The guidance and insight of EFSA and ECDC is of major importance to help such alignment. The objective of JIPs is also to bridge the gap between the sectors by successively focusing on the inter-sectorial mechanisms along the chain from preparedness to response, and to investigate and improve how the work processes of microbiologists, epidemiologists, and information specialists, function across the Public Health/Animal Health/Food Safety interface at the national level. Strengthening of inter-sectorial mechanisms at the national level will subsequently benefit the supra-national level.

Consequently, the ambition of the integrative activities of the One Health EJP is to develop structures, work processes and platforms that bridge inter-sectorial division within the domains defined by the OHEJP scope, resulting in one European surveillance community. This integrative development should be aligned with European priorities, accommodate, and be adapted to existing EU initiatives and support long-term sustainability in the improved joint capacity. Operational integration is promoted by means of several different instruments, the primary instrument being the implementation of JIPs. Prioritised needs regarding joint collaborative resources were identified in the strategic research agenda (SRA), developed in the context of the EJP proposal. An integrative strategy matrix was developed where the domains Foodborne zoonoses, Antimicrobial Resistance and Emerging Threats became the three pillars of the OHEJP. Further, the components that contribute to the improvement of the “Prevent, Detect and Respond chain” were identified. The prioritised components are reflected in the Joint Integrative Projects, which correspond to each of these components.

Integrative Strategy Matrix

The JIPs were selected in the two internal calls of the OHEJP. The first two JIPs, ORION and COHESIVE, started in 2018. ORION focused on the semantic and technical interoperability between the sectors, with focus on surveillance information. COHESIVE focused on the ability to pick up, share and communicate signals as well as the ability to conduct joint risk assessments. Both these projects finished in 2021 and are now under evaluation.

In 2020, three new JIPs started. MATRIX aims to extend the efforts of COHESIVE and ORION and to advance the implementation of One Health surveillance in practice, by building on existing resources, adding value to them, and creating synergies among the sectors. OH-Harmony-CAP aims to collect information on current capabilities, capacities, and interoperability at both the National Reference Laboratory and the primary diagnostic level. CARE will focus on developing new One Health concepts for proficiency testing of laboratories, reference materials and quality/availability of demographic data. These projects have all been extended to three-year projects ending in December Y5. In March Y4 a new JIP, the two-year project COVRIN started. This project is a response to the ongoing SARS-CoV2 pandemic and aims to integrate coronavirus research activities of all project partners. The project will identify drivers for the emergence and spread of SARS-CoV2 and generate data to build models for risk assessment of SARS-CoV2.

During Y4 most meetings have been digital, even if OH-HARMONY-CAP managed to have a consortium meeting as a hybrid event in Dublin. The WP4 support team got the opportunity to take part in the different consortium meetings. .

The topic “Sharing best intervention practice – twinning and simulation exercises” relating to the sixth component “Action” in the “Prevent, Detect and Respond chain” did not attract any applications in the second call. To partly cover up for this an OHEJP exercise, to be performed on a national level, is being planned for. During Y4 a Project Leader and an Exercise Leader were assigned and a Project Organisation set up. The exercise will be executed in Y5.

Since the joint EU capacity is a function of each member state’s capacity, the JIPs are expected to make their developments accessible to all partners and ensure there is transfer of skills and knowledge and promote harmonised approaches wherever it is relevant. In this way, the JIPs will serve to strengthen the scientific capacity within the EJP, as well as the future prevention, preparedness, detection and response of the EU to foodborne and other emerging threats across human-animal-environmental

sectors. To do this the projects have been encouraged to disseminate results and outcomes in various ways. Among the initiatives within the JIPs are for instance several national pilots to harmonize the work between public and animal health and food safety authorities. There has also been a supra national pilot, where new tools are implemented at EFSA and ECDC Other tools developed by the JIPs have been integrated into already existing tools like the FoodChain Lab.

WP4 is responsible for the supervision and evaluation of the JIPs. The body of this report is based on the 12-month reports for Y4 provided by the four not yet finished JIPs, with an initial introductory chapter summarising their operational performance in Y4. The two finished JIPs ORION and COHESIVE are reported on in a separate report D4.24 Final report of 1st call JIPs and evaluation reports, to be delivered M53.

2. Summary of the performance of the Joint Integrative Projects

The entire contents of the final reports have been copied below, except for the paragraphs related to the ethics, the data management and the list of dissemination and communication activities, which can be found elsewhere:

- The fourth Ethics report, encompassing Joint Research Projects, Joint Integrative Projects and PhD, has been delivered as D1.26 Ethical review report for Y4 (25 February 2022) on the EC Participant Portal.
- All information on the data management plan can be found in chapter 4 of the One Health EJP Periodic Technical Report Y4.
- The list of dissemination activities: this information has been analysed and reported in the One Health EJP Periodic Technical Report Y4, paragraph 3.1 “Overview of the dissemination activities”.

2.1. Milestones and deliverables

The six JIPs planned to submit 51 deliverables in Y4 (see table below). At the time of writing this report, 75% of the planned deliverables were finalized and uploaded on the private area of the OHEJP Website. Some deliverables still need to be uploaded on Zenodo. The impacts of COVID-19 were mentioned as the main reason for delay of deliverables.

JIP	No. of deliverables Y4	No. of finalised deliverables Y4	Percentage of finalised deliverables Y4	No. delayed deliverables
JIP01-ORION	8	8	100%	0
JIP02-COHESIVE	12	12	100%	0
JIP03-CARE	10*	4	40%	6
JIP04-OH HARMONY CAP	4	4	100%	0
JIP05-MATRIX	6	1	17%	5

JIP06-COVRIN	11	9	82%	2
TOTAL	51	38	75%	13

*One of these 10 deliverables included in the Annual Work Plan of Y4 was deleted during the year.

In total the JIPs had listed 20 milestones for Y4 (see table below), whereof 85% were achieved on time. The impacts of COVID-19 were mentioned as the main reason for delay of milestones. In one project, three milestones were deleted during Y4.

JIP	No. of milestones Y4	No. of finalised milestones Y4	Percentage of finalised milestones Y4
JIP01-ORION	1	1	100%
JRP05-COHESIVE	8	8	100%
JRP06-CARE	7	4	57%
JRP07-OH HARMONY CAP	2	2	100%
JRP10-MATRIX	2	2	100%
JRP12-COVRIN	0	0	100%
TOTAL	20	17	85%

Actions resulting from the follow up of milestones and deliverables:

- There are regular meetings between the WP4 support team and the JIP Project leaders (PLs) to inform about upcoming events, reports to be written etc., but also to share experiences.
- The PLs are reminded about upcoming deliverables about one month before each date for delivery.
- The WP4 team checks the delivery of each project deliverable and that it is uploaded correctly. WP4 have provided guidance on how to do this.
- WP4 takes care of the dissemination of deliverables to stakeholders indicated by the PLs.
- The PLs have been reminded about the importance to follow the Scientific Publication Policy

2.2. Publications

As the integrative projects are more development-oriented and a natural part of the alignment process, scientific publications are not an expected major outcome of the projects. Accessibility to newly developed or refined web tool applications are equally important.

Publications in scientific peer-reviewed journals 2021 as well as other published outcomes are listed below.

2.2.1. Peer-reviewed scientific papers

- Bai X, Scheutz F, Dahlgren HM, Hedenström I, Jernberg C. (2021). Characterization of Clinical Escherichia coli Strains Producing a Novel Shiga Toxin 2 Subtype in Sweden and Denmark. Microorganisms. 9: 2374. doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9112374
- Sundermann EM, Nauta M, Swart A (2021). A ready-to-use dose-response model of Campylobacter jejuni implemented in the FSKX-standard. Food Modelling Journal. 2: e63309. doi.org/10.3897/fmj.2.63309 (<https://zenodo.org/record/4923018>)
- Sundermann EM, Correia Carreira G, Käsbohrer A (2021). A FSKX compliant source attribution model for salmonellosis and a look at its major hidden pitfalls. Food Modelling Journal. 2: e70008. doi.org/10.3897/fmj.2.70008
- Decaro N, Grassi A, Lorusso E, Patterson EI, Lorusso A, Desario C, Anderson ER, Vasinioti V, Wastika CE, Hughes GL, Valleriani F, Colitti B, Ricci D, Buonavoglia D, Rosati S, Cavaliere N, Paltrinieri S, Lauzi S, Elia G, & Buonavoglia C. (2021). Long-term persistence of neutralizing SARS-CoV-2 antibodies in pets. Transboundary and emerging diseases. 10.1111/tbed.14308. doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14308
- Gonzales JL, De Jong MCM, Gerhards NM, Van der Poel WHM. (2021). The SARS-CoV-2 reproduction number R0 in cats. Viruses. 13: 2480. doi.org/10.3390/v13122480.
- Ibrahim T. Hagag, Saskia Weber, Balal Sadeghi, Martin H. Groschup, Markus Keller. (2021). Impact of animal saliva on the performance of rapid antigen tests for detection of SARS-CoV-2 (wildtype and variants B.1.1.7 and B.1.351). Vet Microbiol. 262: 109243. doi.org/10.1016/j.vetmic.2021.109243
- Lean FZX, Núñez A, Spiro S, Priestnall SL, Vreman S, Bailey D, James J, Wrigglesworth E, Suarez-Bonnet A, Conceicao C, Thakur N, Byrne AMP, Ackroyd S, Delahay RJ, van der Poel WHM, Brown IH, Fooks AR, Brookes SM. (2021). Differential susceptibility of SARS-CoV-2 in animals: Evidence of ACE2 host receptor distribution in companion animals, livestock and wildlife by immunohistochemical characterization. Transbound Emerg Dis. 10.1111/tbed.14232. doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14232
- Newman J, Thakur N, Peacock TP, Bialy D, Elreafey AM, Bogaardt C, Horton DL, Ho S, Kankeyan T, Carr C, Hoschler K, Barclay WS, Amirthalingam G, Brown K, Charleston B, Bailey D. (2021). Neutralising antibody activity against SARS-CoV-2 variants, including Omicron, in an elderly cohort vaccinated with BNT162b2. medRxiv. doi.org/10.1101/2021.12.23.21268293
- Gonzales JL, de Jong MCM, Gerhards NM, Van der Poel WHM. (2021). The SARS-CoV-2 Reproduction Number R0 in Cats. Viruses. 13: 2480. <https://doi.org/10.3390/v13122480>
- Decaro N, Grassi A, Lorusso E, Patterson EI, Lorusso A, Desario C, Anderson ER, Vasinioti V, Wastika CE, Hughes GL, Valleriani F, Colitti B, Ricci D, Buonavoglia D, Rosati S, Cavaliere N, Paltrinieri S, Lauzi S, Elia G, & Buonavoglia C. (2021). Long-term persistence of neutralizing SARS-CoV-2 antibodies in pets. Transboundary and emerging diseases, 10.1111/tbed.14308. Advance online publication. doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14308

2.2.2. Other published outcomes except meeting reports

- Presentation on the One Health EJP- Online welcome meeting March 3rd, 2021. Cross-sectoral framework for quality Assurance Resources for countries in the European Union (CARE) Proficiency testing and Reference Material. M. Torpdahl.

- Presentation on the One Health EJP CPD Module 2021 Feb. 2021 “rStrainSelect: an R-tool for sampling strains based on metadata in a One Health context Laurent Guillier, French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES)”
- FSKX format, RAKIP Model repository and FSK-Lab supporting training material in Moodle platform (<https://bfr-elearning.de/> Username: fsk-workshop21; Password: Matrix.2110)
- C Koren & R White (2021). Sykdomspulsen One Health – A real time surveillance system in an infrastructure coping with half a million analysis a day. OHEJP 2021 Annual Scientific Meeting. Satellite Workshop Software Fair.
- T Günther, M Filter (BfR), F Dórea (SVA). WP6 presentation – 2021-06-23 – Making linked data accessible for One Health Surveillance with the One Health Linked Data Toolbox – Live demonstration of linked data pipelines with HSO and RDF – available at: https://svasweden-my.sharepoint.com/:p/g/person/fernanda_dorea_sva_se/EQnWsnYRrZdMgBCO7he5_swB78zmQ8MoaAPgRFJLWPT8nA?e=7IUu7c
- G Benedetti (2021). One Health Session of the ECDC EPIET/EUPHEM Fellowship Project Review Module –participation in the related round table [Co-chairing] and brief presentation about the MATRIX project and integrated One Health surveillance.
- C Koren (NIPH) (2021). Designing a One Health website - Tips for user-friendliness and visual appeal – available at: https://svasweden-my.sharepoint.com/:b/g/person/fernanda_dorea_sva_se/EbuNWg5XuI9IuJuHtbzglckBnWzNpj6XVYf6nWV8jIFtmg?e=kS5XEc
- Co-analysing One Health data: considerations, pitfalls and biases – available at: <https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/docs/data/>

2.2.3. Meeting proceedings and abstracts

Fifteen conference proceedings and abstracts were published from the JIPs during year 4. See individual project Y4 reports for details.

- Boel J, Coldham N, Hallam S, Johnson P, Gyomose P, Torpdahl M, Lahti E, Jernberg C, Hendriksen R, Veldman K, Brouwer M. (2021). EJP-OH-CARE: Pilot studies to support guidance and suggestions for cross-sectoral One Health proficiency testing schemes. OHEJP ASM meeting in Copenhagen, Denmark.
- Wijnands L, Mooijman K. (2021). Cross sectoral quality assurance systems, an inventory. OHEJP ASM meeting in Copenhagen, Denmark.
- Mota JO, Aarts H, Guillier L, Desvignes V. (2021). Identification of data currently used in quantitative microbial risk assessment. OHEJP ASM meeting in Copenhagen, Denmark.
- Brisabois A, Chesneau O, Michelacci V, Shah F, Mistou M-Y, The OH-EJP CARE Consortium. (2021). EUROpanel OH: Construction of a CARE catalog of Bacteria Foodborne Pathogens Strains used as Reference Materials in the European Union. Société Française de Microbiologie, Nantes.
- Mistou M-Y, Chesneau O, Shah F, Michelacci V, Brisabois A, The OH-EJP CARE Consortium. (2021). EUROpanel OH: Construction of a catalogue of foodborne pathogenic bacterial strains that can be used as reference materials in the European Union. Société Française de Microbiologie, Nantes.

- De Olievera Mota et al. (2021). The Third French Individual and National Food Consumption (INCA3) Survey 2014–2015 and data for microbiological risk assessment: Models for domestic refrigerator temperatures. e-Agrostat 2021. 16th Agro-Industry and Statistical Methods Congress.
- Ziętek-Barszcz A. (2021). GIS as a tool for mapping Salmonella serovars in pigs in Poland between 2014-2018. OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting.
- Norden Z. (2021). Building political will for One Health risk analysis systems. OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting.
- Kausrud K. (2021). Evolving at the speed of risk. OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting.
- Cito F. (2021). Mapping the surveillance activities for food-hazards across Europe. OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting.
- Rodríguez A. (2021). Food surveillance data on Campylobacter and Salmonella in Spain (2016-2018): Spatial visualization and descriptive analysis. OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting.
- Günther T, Kramer-Schadt S, Fuhrmann M, Belik V. (2021). Analyses of environmental factors associated with the occurrence of antimicrobial resistance in wild boars (*Sus scrofa*): A generic data pipeline approach. OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting.
- de Abechucó EL, Filter M. (2021). One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist (OH-CRAC): a framework for harmonization of surveillance data reports. 39th Meeting of the Scientific Network for Zoonoses Monitoring Data.
- Günther T, Kramer-Schadt S, Fuhrmann M, Belik V. (2021). Environmental factors associated with the occurrence of antimicrobial resistance in wild boars (*Sus scrofa*) – Zoonoses 2021 – International Symposium on Zoonoses Research Online.
- Swanson D, Koren C, Hopp P, Jonsson M, Grøneng GM. (2012). Forecasting human gastrointestinal outbreaks in Norway with Campylobacter broiler farm surveillance data and results dissemination to health authorities. One Health in the 21st century 2021 Conference (<https://www.med.uio.no/helsam/english/research/centres/global-health/news-and-events/events/global-health-and-the-2030-agenda/2021/national-one-health-conference-2021-.html>)

2.3. Interactions with other JRP/JIPs, European, international and national projects

The aim of the JIPs themselves is to generate integrative activities. In addition, OHEJP WP4 arranges cogwheel workshops to facilitate interactions between the JRP/JIPs and other European projects and initiatives. Another initiative to facilitate interactions between the OHEJP projects is the Thematic Integrative Meetings (TIMs). Some examples of interactions initiated by JIPs are provided here. Additional and more detailed information can be found in the technical reports.

2.3.1. Interactions initiated by JIPs with international focus

In CARE there are several ongoing activities to identify available and existing External Quality Assurance (EQA) programs offered to the National Reference Laboratories. From this information a guidance will be set up for new EQA scheme expanding to whole genome sequencing (WGS). The partners have agreed on a list of nine pathogens, all known to be responsible for

foodborne human infections, to serve as a basis for gaps to be identified in available reference material to cover all known serotypes, genotypes and generally pathogenic variants of the selected pathogens.

- Yves Pascal D. VAN DER STEDE (EFSA), Marius Linkevicius (ECDC) and Daniel Palm (ECDC) are all kept in the loop in relation to communication that goes out from EJP CARE:
- A meeting was held in September with WP4 member and J. Takkinen from ECDC to present WP4 outputs.
- Another meeting with EFSA Microbial risk assessment network was also done in October 2021.
- OH-HARMONY-CAP co-hosted a Thematic Integrative Meeting (TIM) “EU surveillance frameworks and infrastructures in a harmonized One Health perspective” in collaboration with JIP CARE and OHEJP WP4. More than 80 people participated and the meeting concluded with a panel discussion with representatives from ECDC and EFSA.
- A joint venture application by MATRIX, CARE, and OH-HARMONY-CAP has been made for hosting the third One Health CPD–module with the theme, Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests in the fall of 2022.
- International collaborations were identified by MATRIX with ECDC regarding the EU-LabCap tool by JIP OH-HARMONY-CAP and with the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) regarding the SISOT (Surveillance and Information Sharing Operational Toolkit) tool.
- Links have been established by COVRIN with international research networks and projects like the UK Coronavirus network, the PREZODE network and the ERRAZE project.

2.3.2. Interactions initiated by JIPs with national focus

In OH-HARMONY CAP an OHLabCap instrument will be developed, which will support harmonised data collection and validation on selected food borne pathogens and encourage cross-sectorial communication and assist competent authorities in establishing and strengthening national networks.

The MATRIX project is advancing the implementation of One Health Surveillance (OHS) in practice by building onto existing resources, adding value and creating synergies among the sectors at a national level. The development of dashboards that enable data-driven surveillance to be carried out as an inter-sectorial activity, is one main activity, which is initiated in Sweden and Norway.

- National-level collaborations were developed by MATRIX in France with surveillance actors: French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety, national reference laboratories on Salmonella and Campylobacter; and Santé Publique France, the National Public Health Agency. These experiences contribute to work e.g. lessons learnt from JRP NOVA.
- National-level collaborations were developed by MATRIX in France with the Food chain surveillance platform (website, in French: <https://www.plateforme-sca.fr/> - description of platform objectives and organisation), especially the research group on Salmonella surveillance.
- The work done in MATRIX (WP5) shows high potential for synergies with the work of the WHO/OIE/FAO SISOT-team (Surveillance and Information Sharing Operational Toolkit). MATRIX is in contact with the team to align the work and potentially identify reciprocally beneficial tasks.

2.3.3. Cogwheel Workshops

The OHEJP WP4 is responsible for the arrangement of Cogwheel Workshops. The purpose of these workshops is to identify synergies, joint priorities and opportunities for collaboration within the OHEJP or with other EU initiatives. The JIPs have been presented and introduced to external European H2020 projects in these workshops. During Y4 two Cogwheel Workshops were arranged. Thus, the goal of 8 Cogwheel Workshops during the life span of the OHEJP has been reached.

In the 25th of February 2021 the 7th Cogwheel Workshop was arranged targeting the VEO project (Versatile Emerging infectious disease Observatory) (<https://www.veo-europe.eu/>) and the MOOD project (MOnitoring Outbreak events for Disease surveillance in a data science context) (<https://mood-h2020.eu/>). This Cogwheel Workshop was held as an online meeting with 54 participants, with 18 OHEJP projects represented in total, including one PhD project.

The 8th Cogwheel Workshop on the 29th of September 2021 was arranged to present ELIXIR (www.elixir-europe.org) which is a European inter-governmental organisation coordinating and providing life science resources for researchers to find, analyse and share data. This Cogwheel Workshop was held as an online meeting with 37 participants, with 22 OH EJP projects represented.

2.3.4. Thematic Integrative Meetings

Thematic Integrative Meetings (TIMs) are annual digital workshops aiming to facilitate integration across the OHEJP domains, but within themes. A total of four TIMs are planned during the life-span of the OHEJP. The third TIM was organised in co-operation with JIP-03 CARE and JIP04-OH HARMONY CAP on May 21st, 2021 with the theme of "EU surveillance frameworks and infrastructures in a harmonized One Health perspective". The TIM covered the ongoing work with reference material, harmonised protocols for detection and characterisation of methods, proficiency tests and Nagoya protocol. 4th TIM The fourth one will be in February of Y5 with the title "Data sharing across disciplines".

2.4. Data Management Plan (DMP)

All JIPs manage and update their DMPs on a regular basis, using the template provided in the CDP tool. This tool is used by all ongoing JIPs and JIPs. The Data Management Committee, with representatives from OHEJP WP 3, 4, 5 and 6, provide feedback once or twice a year. There was a shift of DMP Leader during Y4, but the DMP Leader position is still within Sciensano.

2.5. Critical risks

The potential risks identified in the 12-month reports of the JIP projects, not finished during Y4, are summarised in the table below.

Description of risk	CARE	OH-HARMONY-CAP	MATRIX	COVRIN
Loss of keypersons (staff and/or leaders)	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Delay in work plan execution	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No	Yes	Yes	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No	No	Yes	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Poor intra-project relationship	No	No	Yes	No

Potential entry/exit of partners	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Other risks (please describe)	COVID	COVID	COVID	COVID

Critical risks managed during Y4 are still mainly due to the pandemic, which has caused some delays. Since all JIPs got an extension, the delays are not expected to impact the final deliveries. In MATRIX one partner left the project and one new partner was added. The duties of the partner, which left, was taken over by other MATRIX partners.

Critical risks are discussed at the quarterly meetings with all the JIP leaders, as well as in individual follow-up meetings between WP4 support team and PLs.

3. JIP01 – ORION

3.1. Summary of the work carried out

The ORION project finalized the project work as planned in June 2021. As outlined in the original project plan the ORION project developed and optimized One Health resources that were evaluated in a number of national One Health (OH) pilots as well as in a supra-national pilot with EFSA and ECDC.

One of the main ORION project outcomes is the so-called “One Health Surveillance (OHS) Codex”, which is a framework supporting the implementation of the One Health paradigm in areas linked to the harmonization of OHS data and solutions. This framework was implemented as a continuously updateable online resource (<https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io>). It is founded on the ORION requirement analysis where ORION partners jointly concluded that surveillance data integration in a One Health context requires a number of specific actions on different problem types by various stakeholders along the full surveillance pathway. This finding led - 9/117 - to the design of an extendable OHS Codex structure that covers four main principles. Each principle represents an area, where resources to support cross-sector understanding and information exchange will help stakeholders to adopt the One Health paradigm. This structure enabled ORION partners to develop and integrate a broad spectrum of innovative solutions, resources and findings into a consistent overarching framework, including lessons learned from national pilots. Among others, the OHS Codex encompass the “One Health Report Annotation Checklist” (OH-CRAC), National OHS Report Templates, the One Health EJP Glossary, a OHS Inspiration catalogue, the OH Surveillance Pathway Visualization, the OH Knowledge Base – Surveillance systems, the Sequencing for Surveillance (SfS) Handbook and the Health Surveillance Ontology.

In several national OH pilots country specific solutions were established that created direct impact on cross-sector communication, surveillance data exchange and interpretation. For example, in the WP2-NGS pilot the first cross-sector IRIDA (<https://www.irida.ca/NGS>) data analysis platform was established at the Norwegian Research and Education Cloud (<https://www.nrec.no/>). As a result, there is an increased collaboration and information exchange between the veterinary and public health sectors in Norway. The Danish pilots contributed to improved OH reporting, e.g. the *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* chapter in DANMAP 2019, and the Danish national surveillance system for AMR and AMU (<https://www.danmap.org/>). They also established a sequencing based *Campylobacter* surveillance system that will be extended in the future into a platform for real-time surveillance data and result sharing. The Swedish pilot led to the implementation of new work procedures in the process of generating the annual surveillance reports on zoonotic diseases with an improved collaboration among the national OH sectors. The revised processes helped to identify and address bottlenecks in cross-sectoral interoperability and FAIRness of surveillance results. Innovative data interoperability solutions supporting data interoperability were developed and tested.

On international level, the ORION project performed a number of activities to share knowledge with international stakeholders like EFSA and ECDC, for example in a dedicated pilot project. In addition, a number of ORION solutions were integrated into the Surveillance and Information Sharing Operational Tool (SISOT) of WHO/FAO/OIE. Members of the ORION project presented research results at various international conferences, e.g. ASM2019, ASM2020, ASM2021, the 6th World One Health Congress etc., conducted several webinars and organized international workshops with other research projects and institutes, e.g. the NGS workshop 2020, the CPD2021 module, the ASM2021 Satellite Workshop Software Fair. ORION partners published eight scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and several other publications are still in preparation.

The project coordination organized trimonthly web meetings for the whole ORION consortium including stakeholders and interested EJP members, and monthly calls for the WP leaders & deputy leaders. The project contributed to the EJP DMP committee, initiated a number of collaborations and information exchange with other EJP projects (e.g. MATRIX, COHESIVE, RADAR, NOVA, BeONE), initiatives (e.g. RAKIP, SISOT, IRIDA, PAHO-WHO workshops) as well as with national and international research and development projects (SafeConsume, SEQ-TECH, SIGMA, Vinnova, FORMAS, COMBACTE-MAGNET EPI-Net network).

3.2. Work carried out in the JIP, scientific results, and integrative outcomes

3.2.1. WP1- OH Surveillance Codex

WP1-T1: Inventories and requirement analysis for “OH Surveillance Codex” (M1-M12).

The requirement analysis was performed in the first year of the ORION project and laid the foundation for the development of the OHS Codex. The OHS Codex was envisioned as a high level framework for harmonised, cross-sectional description and categorisation of surveillance data (SD) covering all surveillance phases and all knowledge types. To identify the needs of the community/stakeholders, - 10/117 - WP1 carried out literature reviews, online surveys and individual interviews with different domain experts.

The collected feedback outlined the lack of resources supporting mutual understanding and interpretation of data from the different OHS domains, which is a major bottleneck for meaningful OHS data analysis. In order to facilitate and contribute to mutual understanding between OH sectors, it was decided that the WP1 should work on two different solutions:

- a) a community driven glossary collecting OH related terms that helps to identify terms with different or shared interpretation across sectors helping to overcome communication hurdles in the future;
- b) a guidance document for harmonized categorization of metadata from different OHS domains providing recommendations on how to structure metadata in SD reports.

Further details about the methods and results of this requirement analysis can be found in the deliverable D-JIP1-1.1.

WP1-T2: Development of “OH Surveillance Codex” (M13-M24)

In the second year of the project, the outcomes from the requirement analysis phase collected by the different ORION WPs were brought together to identify current best practices and needs within the OHS community. The collected feedback confirmed that cross-sectoral and multi-disciplinary communication, collaboration and knowledge exchange are still significant challenges for the OHS community. To address these challenges, the conceptual design of the OHS Codex evolved into a high-level framework that comprises four high-level “action” principles (Collaboration, Knowledge, Data and Dissemination) that match well with priority areas identified in the “Tripartite Guide to Addressing

Zoonotic Diseases in Countries” published by WHO, FAO and OIE. Within each of the four principles, the OHS Codex provides a collection of useful resources developed by the different ORION WPs, as well as pointers to success stories for the application of these resources. The OHS Codex was envisioned as a “living” framework that is continuously reviewed and updated as the project and the developed resources evolved adapting to the needs of the OH community in the future. From a technical perspective, the OHS Codex was implemented as an open source community resource that is available via: <https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>.

In this phase, the conceptual design of the tools developed in WP1 to support communication and OHS harmonization were also updated. The OHEJP Glossary was further developed and maintained as a collaborative effort of three EJP projects, ORION, NOVA and COHESIVE, with support from OH experts of EJP stakeholders. An essential part of the work was the extensive curation and review of the terms and definitions by OH experts from each target sector (animal health, public health and food safety). The first draft of the OH Consensus Report Annotation Checklist (OH-CRAC) was also outlined in this phase. The OH-CRAC aims at providing best practice annotation of SD in reports from different OH sectors

JIP1-WP1-T3: One Health pilot (M7-M39)

WP1 pilots had the goal of demonstrating that the resources developed by WP1 (OHEJP Glossary and OH-CRAC) and the supporting standards and tools developed by WP3 are practically applicable and generate the expected added value. WP1 performed the following pilots:

WP1 One Health Pilot - For this pilot, the EJP project “Antibiotic Resistance Dynamics” (ARDIG) and “German One Health Initiative” (GOHI) were chosen as use cases to validate the WP1 solutions in the AMR and AMU domains. The WP1 OH pilot specifically tested and improved the OH-CRAC, OHEJP Glossary and Glossaryfication Web Service. This web service was developed to add value to the OHEJP Glossary by generating automatically glossaries for user provided documents (reports, protocols, manuscripts, etc.).

EJP ORION WP1 & WP3 supra-national pilot with EFSA & ECDC - In addition to the originally planned national WP1 OH pilot, the ORION WP1 and WP3 agreed to pursue together a pilot to test the uptake-potential of WP1 and WP3 solutions by EFSA and ECDC. Under this pilot, we evaluated the potential benefits and usability of the following tools: OH-CRAC, OHEJP Glossary and the Health Surveillance Ontology (WP3) facilitating its accessibility and providing use cases via the One Health Linked Data Toolbox (OHLDT, <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/one-healthlinked-data-toolbox/>).

During the execution of the WP1 pilots, the feedback collected from both pilots was used to make the necessary adjustments and improve the different resources. A detailed description of the performed activities, results and lessons learned during the implementation of the pilots for each of the tools can be found in the final pilot reports provided as appendices to the deliverable D-JIP1-1.3.

JIP1-WP1-T4: Evaluation and Recommendations (M31-M42)

During the course of the project, the OHS Codex was significantly improved, updated and a new version was implemented as an open source community resource that is available via <https://ohsurveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>. Furthermore, the OHS Codex was further extended to include the summaries and lessons learned from the pilot studies performed in the context of ORION. A collaboration plan was established with the EJP MATRIX project to further extend and maintain the OHS Codex once the ORION project ends.

The development of the OHEJP Glossary (available at <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/ohejpglossary/>) required a collaborative effort involving actors from all OH sectors, disciplines and countries. This collaborative work implies the continuous extension, curation and validation of the glossary content. This process was supported by the implementation of a new backend software infrastructure, which

provides efficient technical and operational resources to curate and manage the glossary content in a collaborative manner.

The Glossaryfication Web Service extended the use of the OHEJP Glossary as end users can automatically search within any user-provided text document for terms that are contained in the OHEJP Glossary. Based on the feedback collected in the pilots, other glossaries from national and international institutions were added to the service (available at : <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/ohejp-glossary/>). The inclusion of glossaries within OH reports using this service can improve communication and collaboration across OH sectors in a long-term perspective.

The OH-CRAC was also made available as a web-based interactive annotation tool (<https://aflex.vrac.iastate.edu/checklist/?t=OH-CRAC>) for functional meta-information extraction in reports/documents uploaded as pdf files. The application of OH-CRAC in the WP1 pilots proofed that the adoption of OH-CRAC could improve the completeness and transparency of the SD reports and facilitates the cross-sector mapping of meta-information on SD.

The OHLDT is a platform combining different tools developed based on the Health Surveillance Ontology (HSO). The joint work between ORION WP1 and WP3 demonstrated the potential of using HSO to join and enrich different datasets and link them to other sources (e.g. EFSA, ECDC or Wikipedia data).

3.2.2. WP2-Epi

Multiple surveillance systems are carried out annually by Member States (MS) of the European Union in the sectors of public health, animal health and food & feed. Some results of these surveillance systems are reported to EFSA, ECDC, and/or other reporting systems of the EU. However, several MS carry out additional national or regional surveillance related to zoonoses that are not reported to higher EU reporting bodies. The aim of this work package was to develop a knowledge base for surveillance systems including an accessible search platform with references to data sources.

To understand the surveillance systems in existence across EU MS, within this WP we first reviewed the literature and ran a questionnaire between WP2Epi partners (T1). The results showed a large difference in terminology and definitions between sectors. Hence, we supported the setup of a glossary in WP1. Altogether, these differences were too large to create a common inventory for all three sectors (public health, animal health, and feed & food), and therefore, we decided to develop three different inventory tables that were as similar as possible yet maintained the integrity of the different terminology between the sectors. We discussed our tables with EFSA and ECDC and based on their comments, analysed the reporting tool metadata of EFSA and ECDC to align our terminology with theirs wherever possible.

As a result, we developed a knowledge base to easily access and search for information on zoonotic and foodborne diseases under surveillance in EU MS within a single platform, tested it and improved it (T2). We used a scientific software within R to develop an application (shiny-app). The advantage being that R was free and the language widely used by scientists making it easy to proceed with the work and maintain the knowledge hub.

Close to 500 surveillance systems are currently in the inventory (https://shiny.fli.de/ifeapps/EJPOrion_WP2Epi/), and the collection of surveillance systems is expected to increase given the support by other EJP projects, such as EJP MATRIX.

To test the knowledge base on suitability for adding all kinds of surveillance systems and other scientific studies, we tested the knowledge hub within the pilot studies (T3).

Another objective of this WP was the analysis of methods for planning and assessment of surveillance systems with respect to the latent trait One Health-ness (OH-ness). By OH-ness, we mean the willingness of public and private bodies to follow the OH mindset during the planning and the implementation of surveillance and monitoring measures. The methodology of the Rasch model was adopted and implemented as an analysis script in Python to investigate OH-ness.

Additionally, a web UI to a database collection of statistical methods and software tools used in surveillance is set up at FLI (M30) using a public shiny interface. The web application was published in M33 at <https://shiny.fli.de/ife-apps/toolsdatabase/>. The databases will continue to be maintained in the upcoming years.

Even if the pilot studies are designed to test and support the general aim of WP2, in most cases the scope was much broader and gave additional impact in the analysis of surveillance systems in Europe. In the pilot study 1 (ST1), carried out by FLI and BfR we analysed in detail the role of *Toxoplasma gondii* as a zoonotic agent. Therefore, a literature research and a systematic review was carried out. Despite staff turnover and the Covid-19 pandemic, the vast majority of goals were achieved. The results of this pilot study were directly added to the knowledge hub.

Other pilot studies analysed the role of *Salmonella*, Hepatitis E, and AMR. These pilot studies were not only supporting WP2Epi but other WPs as well. For example, in the Dutch pilot a more in-depth collaboration between Dutch ORION partner institutes concerning hepatitis E surveillance was set up. Overview of involved institutes, collaborations and their projects were visualized in a country map. Both institutes (WBVR and RIVM) performed an evaluation of the current status of HEV surveillance within the institutes. A start has been made for joint analysis, by making a data template to organize HEV data in a FAIR manner, including a codebook with names and descriptions of relevant variables.

In the UK pilot study carried out by PHE and APHA on *Salmonella* surveillance data exchange it was explored how the data flow and data sharing between different sectors, including gene sequences, could be improved. This pilot established a framework for the sharing of *Salmonella* sequence data between human, food safety and animal health sectors (including associated isolate metadata at level of granularity/sensitivity determined according to one of six data sharing objectives). Data sharing protocol and a Memorandum of Understanding were developed. Hence, this pilot was relevant for WP1, WP2Epi, WP2NGS, and WP3. In the pilot study carried out by Sciensano, different aspects of AMR reporting with an OH vision in Belgium were tested. This has a strong link to the OHEJP glossary (WP1), to WP2Int, and to WP3. From a scientific perspective, the overall result of this WP, a comprehensive knowledge base, will support scientists to better understand the surveillance systems in different sectors and to include this information in future publications.

From a management perspective, the knowledge hub is an important source of information as it provides an overview on surveillance systems beyond the current available databases (e.g. EFSA, ECDC). Furthermore, the development of the inventories identified some important obstacles to collaboration and exchange between different sectors. E.g., it was not possible to create a common table to collect surveillance systems for all sectors due to different terms. The glossary developed in WP1 is an important step to harmonize terminology, and for mutual understanding.

Multiple collaborations and information exchange within and outside the EJP consortium were part of this WP. Important partners are EJP COHESIVE, EJP MATRIX, EFSA and ECDC.

3.2.3. WP2 - NGS

JIP1-WP2-T4: Inventories and requirement analysis for OH Knowledge Base – NGS (M1-M12)

This task was completed in M12. The main target for this task was to figure out what information was needed to be able to use sequencing for surveillance purposes. The work in this task was completed through several means. We first performed a literature review, both of peer-reviewed papers and grey

literature, to get a view of the landscape. This review included documents produced by both the COMPARE project and the ECDC and EFSA regarding the state of the art. Based on this, we created a questionnaire that was sent out to project partners. We also conducted several site visits and meetings with domain experts at various veterinary and public health labs. Our main focus for these meetings was on exploring the work processes and the best practices that these labs had gathered in their work with establishing sequencing as a tool at their institutions. The labs we visited in person were Public Health England (PHE), Statens Veterinærmedicinska Anstalt (SVA) and Folkhalsomyndigheten (FOHM), both in Sweden, and also Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale dell'Abruzzo e del Molise (ISZAM, Teramo, Italy). Additionally, we had an online meeting with Statens Seruminstitut (SSI) in Denmark. This work formed the basis for the Knowledge base, which for WP2-NGS has resulted in the handbook described in the next task.

JIP1-WP2-T5: Improving OH Knowledge Base – NGS (M13-M24)

Bioinformatics is a rapidly developing field, and thus the work with the handbook (<https://oh-sfs-handbook.readthedocs.io/>) that forms the basis of the WP2-NGS knowledge base has continued to the end of the project.

Through the mapping work done in the first year of the project, it was established that there were especially four areas in which it would be particularly useful to catalogue knowledge for new practitioners within the field. These areas were infrastructure, pipelines, typing methods and how to perform surveillance with such results. Thus the handbook was developed to cover these areas. The technical framework that was chosen to host the platform was Github in combination with Readthedocs. This technical solution provides a reasonably low threshold for people to contribute to the handbook, and also helps the sustainability of the project.

Within the scope of this task we also set up a cogwheel workshop together with WP3. This workshop was organized in conjunction with the ECCMID conference in Dubrovnik in 2019. For this cogwheel, we identified and invited initiatives that provide tools for WGS-based surveillance. This workshop saw participation from IRIDA, INNUENDO and COMPARE projects, as well as several OHEJP projects. In addition, the EFSA and ECDC were present. This workshop helped foster communication and understanding within the groups present.

JIP1-WP2-T6: NGS OH pilot studies (M7-M39)

There were two pilots associated with this WP: one pilot in Norway, focusing on infrastructure and joint analysis of *Listeria monocytogenes* between the NIPH and the NVI, and one in Denmark, focusing on using sequencing data to do surveillance of *Campylobacter*.

The work done in the Norwegian pilot has resulted in new infrastructure set up at the NVI, and thus the work done in this task is still ongoing. The aim for this pilot was to set up facilities for joint analysis between the NIPH and the NVI. We explored the two data management and analysis platforms (DMAPs) that at the time were free and open and available for local installation, these were the IRIDA and the INNUENDO platforms. Through evaluation of the platforms, we chose to use the IRIDA platform, primarily for two reasons: the platform allows for differentiated access to data and it is receiving continued support from Canadian funding agencies.

We subsequently proceeded with installing the DMAP in the Norwegian Research and Education Cloud (NREC), where it is currently being tested out by users at the NVI and the NIPH. The focus pathogen for this project has been *Listeria monocytogenes*, and we have in that connection developed an IRIDA plugin which specifically aims at analysing this pathogen.

A Danish pilot study was set up to promote collaboration among all agencies involved in surveillance of *Campylobacter*. An OH working group was set up for this project. The group includes stakeholders from all sectors that have met with regular intervals to discuss all aspects of the project. This includes

the results from a retrospective WGS study, to set up the real-time study for 2019 and further implement routine OH surveillance system in 2020, based on the evaluation of the first year (2019) of real-time surveillance. Data on *Campylobacter* has been analysed using cgMLST derived from WGS and used to detect genetic clusters among patients. Furthermore, an OH approach was used to detect possible links between food/animal sources and human clusters.

This work resulted in a publication from 2020, “Whole-genome sequencing to detect numerous *Campylobacter jejuni* outbreaks and match patient isolates to sources, Denmark, 2015-2017”.

JIP1-WP2-T7: Evaluation and Recommendations (M31-M42)

The work done on the handbook and in the associated for this WP have gone hand in hand. The experiences collected in the pilots have been collected into the handbook, and information collected in the handbook was used to inform the work done in the pilot. In this way the handbook now contains the knowledge the project has uncovered with regards to using sequencing for surveillance.

3.2.4. WP2 - Integration

The WP2-integration work package has collated and developed proof-of-principles that support following statements:

- One Health Surveillance initiatives already exist and are implemented in EU countries
- Integration of surveillance data, analyses, interpretation and outcome communication a) are feasible, and b) can improve our understanding to control risks and zoonotic diseases
- Development and implementation of One Health Surveillance Initiatives is complicated, and collaboration is the foundation for successful One Health Surveillance.

JIP1-WP2-T7: Inventories and requirement analysis for OH Knowledge Base- integration (M1-M12)

A survey was initially conducted to identify existing and implemented One Health Surveillance Initiatives (OHSIs) in the EU and beyond. The OHSIs were identified using a two-step approach with a screening questionnaire and then approaching a selected subset of responders for semi-structured interviews (for detailed description of methods see Deliverable-JIP1-D2.3 Report on requirement analysis for an "OH Knowledge Base – Integration" (ORION) | Zenodo.

The initial screening questionnaire identified 78 OHSI in 20 EU countries, of which 38 OHSIs matched the project definition of an OHSI, i.e. concern foodborne pathogens, was a surveillance activity and included active collaboration between at least two sectors. A total of 15 OHSIs were included in the final report: Inspiration and ideas: One Health Integration in Surveillance (Ellis-Iversen, 2019 Report on OH Surveillance Initiatives). In the report, each OHSI was described by a one-pager explaining the main objectives, the work carried out, actors, future developments and challenges. It also provided a contact institute for further information.

The 15 examples provide proof-of-principle that OHSI are possible for almost every step in the surveillance pathway except for ‘sample collection’, which no OHSI in our survey addressed. The cross-sector laboratory initiatives were implemented either for rare diseases or when applying a novel/advanced analysis, so all strains of one species may be sent for typing or sequencing in one sectoral laboratory specialized in the methodologies. Multi-sectorial expert groups used to discuss and interpret surveillance result were also reported from several countries. In two countries, these were established groups to deal with new, emerging or changing pathogens, and to generate prioritized advice on response and control; these groups included risk-managers and decision-makers as well as scientific experts. Other countries reported cross-sector groups that meet regularly and discuss the current situation, outbreaks and interpret or explain changes together.

Publishing a joint report on zoonoses from multiple sectors was common in the screening questionnaires. Some variation was reported between countries on how much the sectors shared data, collaborated on result interpretation and on the collation of the report. A cross-sector governance structure for zoonotic or AMR surveillance was also reported from several countries. The governance structures were all at national level and were responsible for varying levels of strategy, optimization, communication and prioritization of response.

The survey was not comprehensive nor randomised to provide representativeness, but it showed clearly that OH surveillance is feasible and already implemented throughout the EU and beyond. It provides ideas and inspiration to other countries, and specific examples are now available as proof-of-principle, when advocating for a new OHSI in a country. The catalogue of OHSIs can be found here: [Report on OH Surveillance Initiatives](#)

JIP1-WP2-T8: Improving OH Knowledge Base – Integration (M13-M24)

WP2-integration hosted three pilot project workshops between June 2019 and March 2021 to support the pilot project leaders, to ensure planning and structured outputs and to facilitate collaboration and knowledge sharing between the pilots. WP2-integrations pivotal role in anchoring the pilot projects within ORION allowed us to improve the OH knowledge base with additional OHSIs, but also to understand what challenges OHSIs face between the initial idea and implementation. The three workshops were used ensure coherence between the pilots, identify integration opportunities, avoid overlaps and share ideas between the studies.

The first workshop in June 2019, co-hosted with WP1, focussed on finding commonalities and potentials for collaboration between pilot projects. The need for a generic way to document the planned pilot and expected outcomes was also identified, and a template for pilot project description was developed and agreed. Furthermore, the OHS Codex was introduced, and its potential to become a central outcome of ORION was established (Filter et al, 2021).

The next pilot project workshop was co-organised with WP3 in January 2020. The pilots were now progressing. The project leads presented progress and preliminary outcomes, and we discussed how the outcomes of the different pilot projects would fit into the OHS Codex, and thereby, become anchored within the ORION project. A discussion on how to evaluate the outcome of pilot studies was also initiated, and WP3 and WP2integration developed frameworks for OH progress evaluation for each pilot study to apply.

The last workshop in March 2021 focussed on the lessons learned from each pilot project, and how these could be incorporated into the OHS Codex. The ORION leads for each pillar in the OHS Codex collated the relevant lessons and chaired the discussion on lessons within their pillar. It was decided that each pilot project delivered a report using a template developed by the Coordination Team and WP2-integration to ensure capture of lessons learned.

Twelve pilot projects were completed during the time of ORION, and most of them can be considered either newly developed OHSIs, improvements to current OHSIs or as tools that can be used by OHSIs to improve cross-sector working. They all improved the knowledge base on OHSIs and provided proof-of-principles in multiple countries. Details on all the pilots projects can be found in the [ORION Knowledge Hub](#).

JIP1-WP2-T9: Integration OH pilot studies (M7-M39)

Integration between all the ORION pilots projects was achieved by the workshops and templates already described in the previous section (JIP1-WP2-T8). WP2-integration also contributed to the knowledge base with two pilot studies, with great success and large impact. One of these was a considerable OH improvement to an existing OHSI and the other has the potential to become a new OHSIs providing proof-of-principle for the additional value of surveillance data integration. The third

pilot was commenced and planned, but terminated mid-way due to COVID-19 demands on resources. The remaining resources at DTU were used in pilot 2 instead.

WP2-integration pilot 1: Increasing the One Health interpretation of AMR and AMU surveillance

In 2019, this DTU and SSI pilot generated a One Health-focussed way of reporting AMR for *Campylobacter* by integrating data from the five relevant data streams of: AMU for treatment in humans and animals and AMR in animals, food and people. In 2019 the group worked on the *Campylobacter* section and in 2020, the work focussed on reporting AMR for *Salmonella*. Each year, the project group met early in the year to agree the objectives, plan the flow in the chapter and in each section. Over the summers, data was analysed and the text written and the reports were published in October 2019 and October 2020, respectively.

In short, this pilot study aimed to explore, whether the zoonoses chapter of the DANMAP report could report to One Health objectives, and whether further integrated analyses and interpretations would enhance the One Health conclusions for decision-makers and other users of the report. The OH integration consisted of several steps: 1) Identify the antimicrobial drug classes relevant for treating human patients with acute gastroenteritis; 2) present the resistance levels to the relevant drug(s) for all populations in one figure; and 3) discuss the use the relevant antimicrobial drug(s) in animals and their OH implications.

The new OH focused structure of the DANMAP chapter was well-received by the users the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration expressed: *“The overall target of our efforts on AMU and AMR in the food production is to support human health and ensure that it is and will be possible to treat human illnesses with antimicrobials. To achieve this target, we aim to reduce or maintain a very low level of AMR throughout the food production, focusing on the critically important antimicrobials. When reporting the status of AMU and AMR surveillance it is important, that the impact and trends concerning the risk posed to human health, by foodborne AMR is addressed and if possible assessed. The enhanced One Health focus in the zoonoses chapter of DANMAP 2019 supports this agenda.”*

The outcomes of the pilot project can be found in:

- DANMAP 2019 on DANMAP.org
- The ORION Knowledge Hub as ORION_WP2_INT_PILOT_1_DK
- The final deliverable from WP2 Integration D2.9 (<https://zenodo.org/record/5062452>)
- As a resource in the OH Codex as “Guidance on reporting antimicrobial resistance in a One Health perspective” (<https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/5-the-dissemination-principle.html#national-ohs-report-templates>)

3.2.5. WP2- integration pilot 2. Does One Health integration of surveillance data improve surveillance and disease control? - Integrating national *Campylobacter* surveillance data to establish proof-of-principle

This pilot project was developed to investigate the usefulness of integrating surveillance data across sectors, and to explore whether we could establish a proof-of-principle that could be used by others. At the same time, we wanted to support the Danish National *Campylobacter* Action Plan with any potentially useful outputs. The pilot project used data from two *Campylobacter* surveillance data streams: animal health and food safety, and used a model to estimate the effect of changes in public health. This was investigated through three studies:

- Study 1 explored surveillance outcomes across data streams by comparison of *Campylobacter* prevalence at flock and carcass levels and assess whether adjustments are needed.

- Study 2 investigated whether any new information on public health risk arises from data stream integration by testing the agreement of surveillance outcomes for individual flocks and carcasses, and how this information could feed into the National Campylobacter Action Plan
- Study 3 designed a risk-based control programme by using information from the data streams and assessed the value of risk-based control by combining it with a public health risk model to measure the effect on public health.

The outcomes showed that it was possible integrate the data and analyse it across sectors and populations, but that adjustments of the estimates increased the precision and interpretability. Furthermore, we learned that when you integrate data, you can improve the understanding of the risk and may find new relevant surveillance points. The last outcome of the project demonstrated the additional value of data integration, and proposed a more cost-effective way of controlling Campylobacter in poultry in Denmark. The outcomes are currently under discussion between the authorities and the poultry industry for implementation in the Danish National Campylobacter Action Plan. A detailed description of the project and its outcomes can be found in the final deliverable from WP2 Integration D2.9 (<https://zenodo.org/record/5062452>) and two papers are being prepared for peer-reviewed publication.

Pilot 3. Descriptive surveillance framework farm-to-patient

The aim of this study was to develop a template for describing national OH surveillance systems. The project was abandoned due to COVID-19 resource drain and staff changes.

JIP1-WP2-T10: Evaluation and Recommendations - Integration (M30-M42)

The 3rd pilot project workshop had focus on evaluating, what we learned from all the ORION pilots. The main advantage of conducting pilot studies within the ORION project instead of only gathering information from literature or interviews, was the opportunity of learning through the process, and learning lessons about the applicability of the OH approach in practice. This acquired knowledge may guide others in developing OHSs in the future and is included in the OHS Codex and in the individual pilot project reports in the final deliverable from WP2 Integration D2.9 (<https://zenodo.org/record/5062452>).

Already by the time of the 2nd workshop, many pilot projects experienced that lack of tools, methodology or technical solutions were often not what hindered or complicated integration across sectors. It was often 'individuals', 'the human factor' or 'sensitivities' that slowed things down or hindered implementation of novel solutions. This emphasised the importance of understanding and facilitating a collaborative culture and nurturing positive attitudes for successful OH surveillance initiatives.

WP2-integration was the lead on gathering lessons learned about collaboration from all the ORION pilot projects. Positive lessons and tools that facilitated collaboration and characterised successful outcomes were: frequent meetings/workshop between partners, mutual and clear definitions and goals from the beginning of the project agreed between all partners, templates/check lists/schematic drawings, data-sharing agreements in place and that the project addressed a mutual need/interest. Other things that motivated good collaborations were piggy-backing on existing partnerships and previously established trust; when political interest or pressure existed, and if equal priority/interest/buy-in/enthusiasm from the participating organisations was present. Clear areas of responsibilities and a continuous focus on the outcomes and goals rather than on detailed process and resources, were also experienced as positive in building collaborations.

Some pilot projects saw collaboration grow after having 'planted the seed' a while ago. However, this approach is not well-suited for a project with a specific timeframe such as funded (researchtype)

projects. In general, it was recognised that an OHSI take time to develop and establish itself, which does not always fit well with academic project funding streams and deadlines. Some pilot projects experienced that success in starting up an OHSI could be very person-dependent and convincing individuals to integrate their expert topics with others could be difficult and occasionally a barrier.

Inability to enlist leadership support both internally in the organisations and externally was highlighted as problem. For some of the OHSI-developing pilot projects, it could be difficult to get buy-in from or within organisations without proof-of-principle. Interestingly, in contrast our tool-developing pilot projects found that, despite offering and demonstrating an actual tool, it was also difficult to obtain adoption in existing OHSI.

The lack of concept-of-principle to facilitate advocacy and agreement within and between agencies and up the management ladder is the problem addressed by this work package. We have gathered a catalogue of pre-existing initiatives to inspire and provide proof-of-principle. We have further nurtured collaboration and knowledge-sharing between the ORION pilot projects, and anchored them within the ORION project, whilst ensuring some level of standardisation allowing lessons to be shared in an effective way. These pilot projects and the lesson learned has updated and improved our knowledge base on One Health in Surveillance. WP2-integration have further conducted two pilot studies improving the OHS in Denmark, whilst providing proof-of-principle of the additional value of data integration and OH-focused dissemination.

3.2.6. WP3 - OH Surveillance Harmonisation Infrastructure

WP3-T1: Inventories and requirement analysis for OH Harmonisation Infrastructure (M1-M12)

This task provided a detailed overview of the needs and requirements in OH data interoperability through three main tasks:

1. A literature review, which is currently under peer-review.
2. A joint ORION “Requirement Analysis” workshop (hosted by WP4). In that workshop a decision was made to focus this WP on the development of a “knowledge base” - an ontology for surveillance, plus a surveillance dataset instantiated following the ontology model.
3. A written survey and interviews with surveillance data experts from within the consortium, which were summarized in the first deliverable JIP1-3.11.

The results of these three sub-tasks were used to, in the fourth subtask, construct a vision for an Harmonisation Hub that addressed the main gaps in data interoperability in OHS. It was defined in year 1 that WP3 should fulfil these gaps by working in the following tasks to deliver three main outputs:

- 1) the ontology itself;
- 2) a dataset of public surveillance data published as linked-open data (LOD), marked up following the ontological model developed;
- 3) a proof-of-concept workflow to adopt the ontology in practice, which can be used by any other country to expose, as LOD, their surveillance data already shared with other MS

To fulfil this vision, the WP was split into 3 main tracks: the ontology track, concerned with the development of the ontology to be used; the practice of surveillance track, which was responsible for the OH pilot task described further below; and a technical track, responsible for building the technical architecture needed to achieve this use of an ontology in the practice of surveillance.

WP3-T2: Improving OH Surveillance Harmonisation Infrastructure (M13-M24)

During year 2, within Task 2, we reviewed and aligned terminology from the ECDC, EFSA and previous key projects in animal health surveillance design (RISKSUR and AHSURED), as well as current EFSA

projects on surveillance reporting (SIGMA). All relevant concepts were added to the ontology developed, which was named Health Surveillance Ontology, and made publicly available in various locations:

- A globally unique and eternally persistent identifier: <https://w3id.org/hso>. This address is subjected to content negotiation: humans accessing this link via browser will be referred to a page listing all ontology documentation and additional resources, such training materials. Software agents pointed to the same address will find the machine-readable codes for the knowledge model (written using the Web Ontology Language – OWL).
- Bioportal: <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/HSO>
- A persistent uniform resource locator (PURL) under the Open Biomedical Ontologies Foundry: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/hso.owl>

An Excel plug-in was developed, so that surveillance data can be annotated with the ontology using simple Excel templates. The Excel plug-in is free and open source, and it was developed in conjunction with the RealEstateCore project in Sweden. Codes for developers, as well as a guide to install the plugin for users are available at <https://github.com/RealEstateCore/ExcelRDF>. ExcelRDF is a Visual Studio Tools for Office (VSTO) plugin.

JIP1-WP3-T3: One health pilot (M7-M39)

In Year 1, active discussions have led to the decision of focusing the OH-pilot in three main chapters of the Swedish surveillance report: Campylobacter, Salmonella, and VTEC/EHEC. During months 13-18, the surveillance practice followed closely the production of the surveillance report for these three zoonotic agents, conducting workshops that gathered AH, PH and FS surveillance officials to discuss opportunities for data sharing, joint data analysis, and publication of main findings that highlighted the OH aspects of the activities and findings of the previous year.

During year 2 the OH-work with the report was extended to include all zoonotic chapters in the report. The work during year one was evaluated and the experiences were incorporated into the following year. As a result, a new process was introduced, and new instructions were produced to clarify the role of the main responsible author of each chapter. To improve the OH work in all zoonotic chapters it was mandatory for the main authors to contact the other authors for a meeting to discuss the results of the previous year's surveillance and what to highlight in the report. The report was published in June and in this issue several of the zoonotic chapters had special In-focus sections, highlighting an unusual finding, an outbreak or a more detailed description of a method.

JIP1-WP3-T4: Evaluation and Recommendations (M31-M42)

This task was extended to M42, following ORION's extension. During the last project year (and the 6 months extension) we focused on improving the outputs based on the lessons learned from the pilot in Sweden, and across the ORION project; and in disseminating these outputs and making them publicly available in sustainable online locations.

For the second main output planned for this WP, a “dataset of public surveillance data published as linked-open data (LOD), marked up following the ontological model developed”, we used data gathered during the pilot to publish a dataset with results of 10 years of Campylobacter surveillance in Sweden (animal and public health) as a full FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) resource. The dataset has its own URI (https://data.sva.se/dcat/surveillancereport/campylobacter_surveillance_sweden.rdf) and it is also published in the Swedish data portal for public sector information: https://www.dataportal.se/en/datasets/59_1684/campylobacter-surveillance-in-sweden.

While the ExcelRDF plugin had been delivered in year 2, in year 3 we further improved the third main deliverable, “a proof-of-concept workflow to adopt the ontology in practice” by creating automated workflows using the KNIME Web Server infrastructure provided by ORION’s coordinator institute, BfR.

The Linked Data Toolbox workflows are available at <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/one-healthlinked-data-toolbox/>.

3.2.7. WP4 - Coordination, Communication, Training and Sustainability

JIP1-WP4-T1: Internal project coordination (M1-M42)

The project coordination accomplished the project coordination tasks with great support from all project partners. As technical infrastructure for project management the project used in the beginning the ORION Virtual Research Environment (VRE) and towards the end of the project the web-based infrastructure provided by EJP.

Over the whole duration of the project the coordination held trimonthly web meetings for the whole ORION consortium (including EFSA, ECDC, EJP WPs and interested other EJP project leads) and a monthly call for the WP leaders & deputy leaders.

JIP1-WP4-T2: External project integration (synchronized with EJP WP5) (M1-M42)

The project coordination contributed to relevant overarching EJP activities and continued to extend collaboration and information exchange specifically with the new EJP projects. EFSA / ECDC were actively informed on project results via the “EJP ORION WP1 & WP3 supra-national pilot with EFSA & ECDC”. ORION successfully applied and conducted the 2021 CPD Module that took place from 15th to 19th February 2021. ORION also supported the ASM2021 Satellite workshop on 7th June 2021

ORION kept close collaboration with a number of other EJP projects, specifically JIP COHESIVE and JIP MATRIX, and exchanged experiences through dedicated meetings. ORION also kept close collaboration with the JRP NOVA, focused on surveillance.

JIP1-WP4-T3: Sustainability roadmap (M7-M42)

For most ORION solutions first activities were undertaken to guarantee the short-to-medium term sustainability. This included a number of dissemination and publication activities as well as the adoption of technical infrastructure that supports long-term maintenance and collaboration. A Sustainability roadmap, describing the planned steps towards such long-term sustainability, was provided as a dedicated deliverable in M42.

JIP1-WP4-T4: Training and Dissemination (M1-M42)

JIP1-WP4-T4-ST2: Knowledge integration (web portal, Wiki, curricula, tutorials, videos, sample data) (M7-M42)

Continuous updates performed on ORION’s main online platform “OHS Codex” as well as on individual web resources that each partner created for their specific solution, e.g. for OHEJP Glossary linked resources the website <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/ohejpglossary/> was created and updated regularly.

See the list of Dissemination and communication activities provided in this report.

3.3. Project self-assessment

The ORION project has fully accomplished its project objective to “establishing and strengthening inter-institutional collaboration and transdisciplinary knowledge transfer in the area of surveillance data integration and interpretation, along the One Health (OH) objective of improving health and well-being”. As planned in the project proposal the ORION project developed a framework that supports the implementation of the One Health paradigm in all areas linked to the harmonization of One Health Surveillance (OHS) data and solutions. This framework has been named the “OHS Codex” and was implemented as a continuously updateable online resource (<https://ohsurveillance-codex.readthedocs.io>). It builds on the joined understanding that surveillance data integration in a One Health context requires a number of individual actions by various stakeholders along the full surveillance pathway. This finding also opened up the way to integrate a broad spectrum of ORION solutions, resources and findings into a consistent overarching framework. Other specific project objectives outlined in the ORION project plan were accomplished as well, like the development of “a high-level framework for harmonised, cross-sectional description and categorisation of surveillance data covering all surveillance phases and all knowledge types” which was finally named “One Health Report Annotation Checklist” (OH-CRAC). In WP2 “a cross-domain inventory of currently available data sources, methods/algorithms/tools, that support OH surveillance data generation, data analysis, modelling and decision support” was developed and integrated into the OHS Codex as the “Knowledge principle” (<https://oh-surveillancecodex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/3-knowledge-principle.html>). In WP3 a number of “practical, infrastructural resources forming the basis for successful harmonization and integration of surveillance data and methods” were developed and integrated into the OHS Codex under the “Data principle” (<https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/4-the-dataprinciple.html>).

Over the course of the ORION project it turned out, that the originally designed project structure with a number of well-defined work packages and several, flexible national pilots were a very good choice. In this way, the project could adapt to the specific needs in each project member country and the involved national stakeholders giving all project partners the opportunity to contribute with specific and relevant solutions to the overarching ORION framework. This flexibility also helped to overcome a number of challenges that the ORION project had to face, e.g. frequent changes of project staff, delays in the hiring process of new staff, and the COVID pandemic. Even though for some pilots and some sub-tasks not all of the initially planned activities could be accomplished as planned, the overall number of solutions and resources developed by the ORION project overcompensated this. In sum, the ORION project accomplished its core objective to create impact on national and international level in improving One Health surveillance data harmonization and integration.

3.4. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

3.4.1. Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
ORION	D-JIP1-1.1	Report on requirement analysis for “OH Surveillance Codex”	M12	M12		https://zenodo.org/record/3754468	1,2
ORION	D-JIP1-1.2	Draft on OH Surveillance Codex	M24	M24		https://zenodo.org/record/3754474	1,2
ORION	D-JIP1-1.3	Revised OH Surveillance Codex, including lessons learned from the OH pilots	M42	M42		https://zenodo.org/record/5062641	1,2
ORION	D-JIP1-2.1	Report on requirement analysis for an “OH Knowledge Base – Epi”	M12	M13		https://zenodo.org/record/3754572	2,5
ORION	D-JIP1-2.2	Report on requirement analysis for an “OH Knowledge Base - NGS”	M12	M14		https://zenodo.org/record/3754649	2,5
ORION	D-JIP1-2.3	Report on requirement analysis for an “OH Knowledge Base – Integration”	M12	M14		https://zenodo.org/record/3754596	2,5

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
ORION	D-JIP1-2.4	Status report on OH Knowledge Base – Epi	M24	M24		https://zenodo.org/record/3754600	2,5
ORION	D-JIP1-2.5	Status report on OH Knowledge Base – NGS	M24	M24		https://zenodo.org/record/3754604	2,5
ORION	D-JIP1-2.6	Status report on OH Knowledge Base – Integration	M24	M24		https://zenodo.org/record/3754609	2,5
ORION	D-JIP1-2.7	Revised OH Knowledge Base - Epi, including lessons learned from the OH pilots	M42	M42		https://zenodo.org/record/5062653	2,5
ORION	D-JIP1-2.8	Revised OH Knowledge Base -NGS, including lessons learned from the OH pilots	M42	M42		https://zenodo.org/record/5062329	2,5
ORION	D-JIP1-2.9	Revised OH Knowledge Base - Integration, including lessons learned from the OH pilots	M42	M39		https://zenodo.org/record/5062452	2,5
ORION	D-JIP1-3.1	Report on requirement analysis for an “OH Harmonisation Infrastructure Hub”	M12	M12		https://zenodo.org/record/3754615	4
ORION	D-JIP1-3.2	Status report on OH Harmonisation	M24	M24		https://zenodo.org/record/3754621	4

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
		Infrastructure Hub					
ORION	D-JIP1-3.3	Revised OH Harmonisation Infrastructure Hub, including lessons learned from the OH pilots	M42	M42		https://zenodo.org/record/5062410	4
ORION	D-JIP1-4.1	Two internal training workshops for ORION partners	M12	M9		https://zenodo.org/record/5062531	8 (training)
ORION	D-JIP1-4.2	Draft on Sustainability Roadmap	M18	M18		https://zenodo.org/record/5062531	8 (sustainability)
ORION	D-JIP1-4.3	Two training workshops for other EJP: Training workshop "Nextflow" for EJP, NVI ORION Webinar	M24	M24		https://zenodo.org/record/3754627	8 (training)
ORION	D-JIP1-4.4	Revised Sustainability Roadmap	M42	M42		https://zenodo.org/record/5062617	8 (sustainability)
ORION	D-JIP1-4.5	OHS Knowledge Hub populated with resources from WP1, WP2 and WP3	M42	M42		https://zenodo.org/record/5062623	4,7
ORION	D-JIP1-4.6	Two additional training workshops and two webinars	M42	M42		https://zenodo.org/record/5062493	8 (training)

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities ; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

3.4.2. Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
ORION	M-JIP1-1	Requirement analysis synchronization workshop	M4	Yes		Workshop held in Berlin, 18 th -20 th April 2018.
ORION	M-JIP1-2	Prioritization workshop	M15	Yes		Workshop held in Uppsala on 16 th - 18 th January 2019
ORION	M-JIP1-3	ORION evaluation workshop	M39	Yes		Workshop held online from 9 th -11 th March 2021

3.5. Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Data interoperability in health surveillance: a literature review to support the development of One Health frameworks (SUBMITTED)	yes		planned as gold access in the Journal of Biomedical Semantics - JBSM-D-20-00030
Stelzer S, Basso W, Benavides Silván J, Ortega-Morad LM, Maksimov P, Gethmann J, Conraths FJ, Schares G. <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> infection and toxoplasmosis in farm animals: Risk factors and economic impact, DOI: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fawpar.2019.e00037 Zenodo : https://zenodo.org/record/3693772	yes		yes (1580 €)
Filter M, Buschhardt T, Dorea F, Lopez de Abechuco E, Gunther T, Sundermann EM, et al. One Health Surveillance Codex: promoting the adoption of One Health solutions within and across European countries. One Health. 2021;12:100233. https://zenodo.org/record/4709670	yes		Yes (3330€)
Houe, H., Nielsen, SS., Nielsen, LR., Ethelberg, S., Mølbak, K. (2020). Opportunities for Improved Disease Surveillance and Control by Use of Integrated Data on Animal and Human Health. <i>Frontiers in Veterinary Medicine</i> , 6: 301, pp. 1-8. DOI: https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2019.00301	yes		yes
Joensen, KG., Kiil, K., Gantzhorn, MR., Nauerby, B., Engberg, J., Holt, HM., Nielsen, HL., Petersen, AM., Kuhn, KG., Sandø, G., Ethelberg, S., Nielsen, EM. (2020). Whole-Genome Sequencing to Detect Numerous <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> Outbreaks and Match Patient Isolates to Sources, Denmark, 2015–2017. <i>Emerging Infectious Diseases</i> , 26(3), 523-532. DOI: https://dx.doi.org/10.3201/eid2603.190947	yes		yes

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Jeevan Karloss Antony-Samy, Georgios Marselis, Eve Zeyl Fiskebeck, Taran Skjerdal, Camilla Sekse, Karin Lagesen (2021). Practical aspects of implementing the IRIDA system as a solution for One Health bioinformatics analyses. ARPHA Conference Abstracts, 2021 http://doi.org/10.3897/aca.4.e68913	Yes		Yes, (no cost)
Joensen KG, Schjørring S, Gantzhorn MR, Vester CT, Nielsen HL, Engberg JH, Holt HM, Ethelberg S, Müller L, Sandø G, Nielsen EM. Whole genome sequencing data used for surveillance of Campylobacter infections: detection of a large continuous outbreak, Denmark, 2019. Eurosurveillance - Volume 26, Issue 22, 03 June 2021. doi: 10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2021.26.22.2001396	Yes		Yes
Buschhardt T et al. A One Health glossary to support communication and information exchange between the human health, animal health and food safety sectors. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2021.100263 https://zenodo.org/record/4769914	yes		Yes (3330€)
Lopez de Abechucuo E et al. One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist (OH-CRAC): a cross-sector checklist to support harmonized annotation of surveillance data in reports (submitted)	yes		Planned as gold access (3500€) in the Zoonoses and Public Health journal
Scaccia N, Günther T, Lopez de Abechucuo E, Filter M (2021). The Glossaryfication Web Service: an automated glossary creation tool to support One Health community. Research Ideas and Outcomes 7: e70183. https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.7.e70183	yes		Yes (535€)
Inspiration and ideas: One Health Integration in Surveillance. Technical University of Denmark. Report on OH Surveillance Initiatives https://www.food.dtu.dk/-/media/Institutter/Foedevareinstituttet/Publikationer/Pub-2019/Rapport-One-	yes		Yes (no cost)

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Health-Integration-in-Surveillance.ashx?la=da&hash=7E90900F125AF0EFAB8E6EEA415AAB82EF465CF3			
DANMAP 2018, chapter 6. Resistance in zoonotic bacteria and animal pathogens. www.DANMAP.org https://www.food.dtu.dk/-/media/Institutter/Foedevareinstituttet/Publikationer/Pub-2019/Rapport-DANMAP-2018.ashx?la=da&hash=1E02D03F74A26651CF1B53BB280626DA5666A080	verbally		Freely available online (no cost)
Foddai, Nao Takeuchi-Storm, Johanne Ellis-Iversen. Integrating Danish Campylobacter surveillance data streams to investigate broiler flock prevalence and potential cross-contaminations at slaughterhouse. In preparation for submission to peer reviewed journal	yes		Planned
Foddai, Maarten Nauta, and Johanne Ellis-Iversen. Risk-based control of Campylobacter spp broiler farms and slaughtered flocks to mitigate risk of human campylobacteriosis - A One Health approach. In preparation for submission to peer reviewed journal-	yes		Planned
Korsgaard, H. B., Ellis-Iversen, J., Hendriksen, R. S., Borck Høg, B., Ronco, T., Attaubi, M., Boel, J., Dalby, T., Hammerum, A. M., Hansen, F., Hasman, H., Henius, A. E., Hoffmann, S., Ilan, M. B., Kaya, H., Kjerulf, A., Kristensen, B., Kähler, J., Rhod Larsen, A., ... Laursen, M. (2020). DANMAP 2019 - Use of antimicrobial agents and occurrence of antimicrobial resistance in bacteria from food animals, food and humans in Denmark. Statens Serum Institut og Technical University of Denmark. WWW.DANMAP.ORG	yes		Freely available online (no cost)

Additional output

- OHS Codex – an online resource collecting various ORION resources, tools and lessons learned: <https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>
- ORION Pilot reports – available via the public EJP project group ORION Knowledge Hub (and as attachments to corresponding the ORION deliverables)
- WBVR/RIVM: Surveillance of a disease/pathogen often includes several institutes and/or departments. Within the national ORION pilot study on Hepatitis E surveillance, a template was made, named “Country Map”, to describe and visualize institutions, projects and data flows. This template consists of a MS Visio document and a Excel document. With the Country Map the existing but also currently missing links between institutes, data sources and data streams are visualized. The Country map can be found on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4767400>)
- PHE/APHA: as part of the national ORION pilot project on Salmonella data sharing across the OH domain in the UK a “data sharing protocol template” and exemplar “case studies” detailing the approaches to and utility of real time One Health surveillance data sharing were developed and made available in the public EJP project group ORION Knowledge Hub
- The *Listeria* plugin created for IRIDA: <https://github.com/NorwegianVeterinaryInstitute/irida-plugin-listeria-typing>
- The ORION WP2-NGS handbook: <https://oh-sfs-handbook.readthedocs.io/>
- OHEJP Glossary and Glossaryfication Web Service: <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/ohejp-glossary/>
- One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist (OH-CRAC) web service: <https://aflex.vrac.iastate.edu/checklist/?t=OH-CRAC>
- One Health Linked Data Toolbox (OH-LOD) – a set of prototypic web services that facilitates the semi-automatic mapping of concepts from the EFSA’s SSD catalogues into the new HSO, to convert Excel-based surveillance data into the data exchange format RDF by exploiting HSO and to make those RDF files accessible for semantic search technologies and services: <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/one-health-linked-data-toolbox/>
- All available Swedish reports on “Surveillance of infectious diseases in animals and humans” (2006 to 2020) were published with unique identifiers in the Swedish data portal (www.dataportal.se) for open public information. For a full list of all individual URL’s, please visit: <http://datadrivensurveillance.org/campylobacter-surveillance-in-sweden/>
- One dataset compiling all surveillance data available in the reports, including surveillance methods annotated according to the OH-CRAC principles¹ developed in ORION (consensus report annotation checklist), was also published in the Swedish data portal in both human readable format (comma separated values, CSV) and machine readable format (RDF). The latter is explicitly annotated with machine readable surveillance concepts from the Health Surveillance Ontology. All permanent unique identifiers created are listed at: <http://datadrivensurveillance.org/campylobacter-surveillance-in-sweden>
- ‘Surveillance inventory’ - publicly accessible in a user-friendly, purposefully set-up, web application: https://shiny.fli.de/ife-apps/EJPOrion_WP2Epi/.

¹ <https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/5-the-dissemination-principle.html>

- Web-based database on tools and methods to plan and analyse surveillance systems:
 - <https://shiny.fli.de/ife-apps/toolsdatabase/>

Webinars:

- Webinar: first version of ORION glossary. 6 November 2018. Recording available here: <https://goo.gl/sUWj2c>.
- Webinar WP1 OHEJP Glossary. 4 September 2019. Recording available here: <https://svasweden.adobeconnect.com/pm7lzofjjogo/>.
- ORION KnowledgeHub Webinar. 6 December 2019. Recording available here: <https://svasweden.adobeconnect.com/p90575ar1eht/>.
- ORION Cogwheel workshop. 5 October 2020. Recording available here: <https://svasweden.adobeconnect.com/p1wuf07ym9pu/>.
- The OHEJP Glossary - A Tool to Support Cross-sectoral and Transdisciplinary Communication in One Health Surveillance. One Health EJP Continuing Professional Development Module 2021: 15-19 February 2021, online workshop. <https://bfr-elearning.de>.
- The Glossaryfication web service: an automated glossary creation tool to support the One Health community. One Health EJP Continuing Professional Development Module 2021: 15-19 February 2021, online workshop. <https://bfr-elearning.de>.
- Linked Open Data. One Health EJP Continuing Professional Development Module 2021: 15-19 February 2021, online workshop. <https://bfr-elearning.de>.

Conference and poster presentations:

- T. Buschhardt, T. Guenther, F. Dorea, M. Filter. The One Health Surveillance Codex. A high level framework to facilitate efficient information exchange across One Health sectors. ICPMF11 conference (poster presentation): 17-20 September 2019. Braganza, Portugal. <http://esa.ipb.pt/icpmf11/>
- T. Buschhardt, T. Günther, F. Dorea, V.H.S Oliveira, V. De Waele, M.E. Filippitz, S. Stelzer, J. Gethmann, M. Torpdahl, T. Skjerdal, L. Larkin, S. Aabo, I. Boone, M. Filter. The ORION Glossary - An Essential Tool to Support Cross-sectoral and Transdisciplinary Communication in One Health Surveillance. ASM Scientific conference 2019 (oral presentation): 21-24 May 2019, Dublin.
- T. Buschhardt. Das One Health EJP Glossar - eine web-basierte Lösung zur Unterstützung der sektor-übergreifenden Kommunikation im „One Health“ Bereich. Symposium „Zoonosen und Lebensmittelsicherheit (oral presentation). 4-5 November 2019, Berlin.
- E. Lopez de Abechuco (BfR): Introduction to ORION project. Cogwheel workshop, 28th April 2020. Link to presentation: <https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-json/pm/v2/projects/128/files/20376/users/1051/download>
- M. Filter, T. Buschhardt, T. Günther, E. Lopez de Abechuco, E. M. Sundermann, J. Ellis-Iversen, J. Gethmann, K. Lagesen, V. De Waele, G. Boseret, F. Dórea. The OH Surveillance (OHS) Codex - a high level framework supporting mutual understanding and information exchange between One Health sectors. OHEJP ASM 2020, 27th-29th May; Link to presentation: <https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-json/pm/v2/projects/128/files/20372/users/1051/download>
- E. Lopez de Abechuco, F. Dorea, T. Buschhardt, T. Günther, E. Sundermann, N. Scaccia, A. Foddai, M. Dispas, M. Umaer, M. Holmberg, J. Gethmann, M. Filter. One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist (OH-CRAC): a generic checklist to support harmonization of

- surveillance data reports. OHEJP ASM 2020, 27th-29th May (Oral presentation). Link to presentation: <https://onehealth.ejp.eu/wp-json/pm/v2/projects/128/files/20371/users/1051/download>
- N. Scaccia, T. Guenther, T. Buschhardt, L. Valentin, M. Filter. Text mining technology as added-value infrastructure to the One Health EJP Glossary. OHEJP ASM 2020, 27th-29th May (Poster). Link to poster: <https://onehealth.ejp.eu/wp-json/pm/v2/projects/128/files/20373/users/1051/download>
 - T. Günther, E. Lopez de Abechuco, N. Scaccia. BfR internal colloquium (oral presentation): “Der "Glossaryfication" Webdienst - automatisierte Glossarerstellung zur Unterstützung des One Health Ansatzes“. 20 October 2020, Berlin.
 - N. Scaccia, E. Lopez de Abechuco, T. Günther, F. Dórea, M. Filter. 38th meeting of the Scientific Network for Zoonoses monitoring data, EFSA, (oral presentation). 19th – 20th October 2020. “Join Integrative Project ORION EFSA-ECDC supra-national pilot”, online event. Link to presentation: <https://onehealth.ejp.eu/wp-json/pm/v2/projects/88/files/20651/users/1898/download>.
 - E. Lopez de Abechuco, F. Dorea, T. Buschhardt, T. Günther, E. Sundermann, N. Scaccia, A. Foddai, M. Dispas, M. Umaer, M. Holmberg, J. Gethmann, M. Filter. One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist (OH-CRAC): a framework for harmonization of surveillance data reports. World One Health Congress (poster presentation): 30th October-3rd November 2020, online event.
 - N. Scaccia, T. Guenther, T. Buschhardt, L. Valentin, M. Filter. The Glossaryfication web service: an automated glossary creation tool to support the One Health community. World One Health Congress (poster presentation). 30th October-3rd November 2020, online event.
 - E. Lopez de Abechuco, N. Scaccia, T. Günther, M. Filter. The Glossaryfication Web Service – an automated glossary creation tool to support One Health communication. One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM) Satellite Workshop 2021. 7th June (Oral presentation). Link to abstract: <https://aca.pensoft.net/article/68843/>
 - T. Günther, M. Filter, F. Dórea. Making Linked Data accessible for One Health Surveillance with the “One Health Linked Data Toolbox”. One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM) Satellite Workshop 2021. 7th June (Oral presentation). Link to abstract: <https://aca.pensoft.net/article/68821/>
 - J. Gethmann et al. Poster Presentations during the ASM Scientific conference 2020: The ORION project – OH knowledge base “surveillance systems” OHEJP ASM 2020, 27th-29th May (Poster).
 - F. Dorea et al. Presentation in the Integrated Food Ontology Workshop (IFOW), part of the 11th International Conference on Biomedical Ontologies (ICBO 2020). Proceedings paper and video recording freely available in this link <https://foodon.org/icbo-2020-food-workshop/>. Title: Health Surveillance Ontology: supporting semantic interoperability in One-Health.

Outcomes

- One Health Surveillance Codex: <https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>
- Ontology and Linked-Open-Data instructional and dissemination materials: <http://datadrivensurveillance.org/ontology/>

- A One Health glossary to support communication and information exchange between the human health, animal health and food safety sectors. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2021.100263>

All ORION project results were at least discussed in one of the involved national authorities, as all project partners used their national ORION pilots for that. The ORION solutions that were already integrated into operational work at national or international level are described in the One Health Impact section of this report.

3.6. One Health impact

The following ORION solutions created impact on the national and/or international level:

The OHEJP Glossary has been integrated into the OHEJP Data Management Software, is used by the BfR to improve the own internal glossary and by Sciensano to establish a national OH glossary.

- In Norway, the first cross-sector IRIDA (<https://www.irida.ca/>) NGS data analysis platform could be implemented at the Norwegian Research and Education Cloud (<https://www.nrec.no/>) including a working pipeline for L. monocytogenes. As a result, there is an increased collaboration and information exchange between the veterinary and public health sectors in Norway.
- In Norway, ORION work promoted increased collaboration between NVI and the ARIES EU reference lab with regards to the development of pipelines, and also with EFSA regarding the harmonization of pipeline outputs. The project has also facilitated extensive collaboration with other IRIDA users, including the IRIDA developers themselves, and other users in South Africa and in the UK.
- In Denmark, the Danish *Campylobacter* pilot project has had a significant impact on the OH-approach for surveillance of *Campylobacter*. The Danish surveillance system has undergone real-time changes during the lifetime of this project, as new insights were gained as the project developed. The project showed that it is possible to detect clusters, outbreaks and link to sources based on comparison of sequences in an OH setting. During the project, the source of several outbreaks was found and control measurements implemented, not only at slaughterhouse level but also in the broiler production. The study resulted in national and international recognition of sequencing based *Campylobacter* surveillance being of high value, also compared to "older" methods used. The project will be continued with the development of a platform for real-time sharing of data and surveillance. An OH working group was set up in connection with the project and the working group will continue after the project has ended. Results from this study has been presented nationally as well as at internationally and data used for annual reporting as well as published in a peer-reviewed journal for international dissemination. A seminar on control of *Campylobacter* in broilers was set-up to improve knowledge sharing with industry, universities and agencies. Funding has also been granted for continuous use of WGS to examine the diversity and transmission within/between chicken flocks, farms, etc.
- In Denmark, improved integrated, OH reporting was implemented, e.g. in the *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* chapter in DANMAP 2019, and the Danish national surveillance system for AMR and AMU (<https://www.danmap.org/>). The enhanced OH-focus contributed to a better

understanding of the OH perspectives in AMR among all report users and encouraged OH policy actions.

- In Sweden, a OH-driven process has been developed and implemented for the annual reporting on surveillance of zoonotic diseases. The report is now produced in close collaboration with the public health-, animal health- and food safety sector. The food safety sector in Sweden was not a part of the ORION project but has been involved in the ORION work with the report. The new process is already implemented in the work with the annual surveillance report and is no longer dependent on resources from the ORION project to continue. The revised approach resulted in significantly improved understanding between OH sectors regarding surveillance activities and results.
- In Sweden, the revision of the surveillance reporting process helped to address bottlenecks in cross-sectoral interoperability and FAIRness of the surveillance output data. Innovative data interoperability solutions as well as the new instructions and guidelines to facilitate future reporting practices contributed to the improvements. All tools developed, as well as the workflows for their application, can be reused.
- In the Netherlands, the two Dutch ORION partners strengthened their collaboration regarding HEV surveillance. Several meetings took place, and first steps for joint analysis of human and veterinary HEV data were made. Furthermore, both institutes evaluated their surveillance programmes leading to recommendations for improvement. The steps already taken will also help to build and strengthen contacts with other institutes in the field of hepatitis E.
- In Belgium, an interactive online tool has been developed that maps the main stakeholders in antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and consumption (AMU) covering the veterinarian, human, food and environment sectors in Belgium, as well as their activities on these topics. Activities helped to implement and promote One Health multi- and transdisciplinary approaches in the process of developing the national OH AMR report to increase the acceptability and feasibility of interventions. In parallel, the OHEJP Glossary was used to support the creation of a national OH glossary.
- In UK, a new Data Sharing Protocol was implemented between APHA and PHE that facilitates data sharing on Salmonella isolate/sequence and associated metadata to defined levels of granularity/ sensitivity as per the Data Sharing Protocol.
- In Germany, the OH-CRAC was presented to the German Federal Office of Consumer Protection and Food Safety (BVL) as a potential solution to further improve the interpretation of surveillance data on a national level. The OHEJP Glossary and the Glossaryfication Web Service was extended to include German glossaries relevant for German agencies (BAUA, BfR, BVL, EFSA, RKI, BfArM and Schülke glossaries)
- On international level, there were an extensive knowledge exchange with EFSA and ECDC during the WP1-WP3 supra-national pilot with 10+ web meetings leading to a better understanding on potential application scenarios for a number of ORION solutions. In addition, NVI collaborated with EFSA regarding the tool set for pipelines for WGS analysis of L. monocytogenes. Additionally, a number of ORION solutions were also integrated into the Surveillance and Information Sharing Operational Tool (SISOT) of WHO/FAO/OIE.
- Several ORION partners were able to synchronize with national or international projects outside OHEJP to create synergies, e.g. BfR (SafeConsume, SISOT team from WHO/FAO/OIE, COMBACTE-MAGNET EPI-Net network), NVI (IRIDA, SEQ-TECH), SVA (IRIDA, SIGMA, Vinnova, FORMAS), DTU (PAHO-WHO workshops, Fleming Fund Fellows in establishing integrated AMR surveillance in Africa and in requested consultancy to policy and scientists in South East Asia).

3.7. Data Management Plan

The ORION DMP has been uploaded to the EJP portal group ORION.

4. JIP2 - COHESIVE

4.1. Summary of the work carried out

The mission of COHESIVE was to develop **sustainable One Health approaches** with respect to *signalling, assessing and controlling zoonoses* at the national and regional level **within EU countries and across borders**.

One of the goals was to support countries with setting up or strengthening human-veterinary-food-environmental collaborations, with the aim to improve the organisation of One Health signalling, risk assessment and response (risk analysis) to zoonoses. A web-based guideline has been developed with the title 'One Health: Setting up a risk analysis system for zoonoses' and can be found at www.ohras.eu and www.onehealthguidelines.eu. The guideline provides a stepwise approach to implement such a One Health risk analysis system (OHRAS) or part of it. For this purpose, an application has also been developed to give guidance in the design of a (partial) OHRAS. In a OHRAS certain OH activities (signalling, risk assessment, feasibility assessment, risk management and risk communication) are organised. In the guideline, information on the OH activities is given, as well as input for Terms of References, suggestions for tools to use, experiences are shared, and guidance on how to handle several barriers. Several pilots were organised to test the stepwise approach and to have the experiences feedback into the guidelines. In two countries, Norway and Portugal, the pilot reached step 3 (out of 5) of the implementation process, as planned. Although the next step has not been taken yet, impact has been achieved by bringing people from different sectors together, building trust and relations and talking about the current situation and what can be improved. Participants in both countries are enthusiastic to continue upon this first workshop. The guideline 'One Health: setting up a risk analysis system for zoonoses' will be coupled to the MedVetNet association website to be able to maintain the guideline also after OHEJP ends.

Through in-depth interviews in six European countries, hindrances and factors facilitating sharing of early signals of zoonotic events within and between sectors (public health, animal health, food safety), within and between countries were explored. The importance of personal contacts was emphasised from all sectors and all levels. Early informal contacts were often taken before formal reporting. These contacts go hand in hand with the need for formal systems and technical as well as legal solutions for sharing data. This scientific approach confirms the outcomes of the needs assessment done before developing the guidelines and are included. The first step within risk analysis is the identification of a potential risk. In addition to classical information i.e. from monitoring systems, horizon scanning might provide essential information. An inventory and assessment of tools for Horizon Scanning (HS) appropriate for One Health were made. Two pilot HS exercises identified potential drivers for emerging zoonotic risks, such as an ageing population, trade, increase of travel, new consumption habits. These drivers can be taken into account when planning surveillance programmes and control activities.

An additional aim of the project was to enhance informal low-threshold exchange of information on signals of zoonoses between countries and across disciplines. Within the project three digital workshops on exchange of information were organized, discussing issues around topics such as *Brucella canis* and zoonoses in pet rats. This way of informal sharing was appreciated among the

participants. An informal group has been formed which aims to continue with this activity also after the COHESIVE project has been finished.

Within the project several free and open-source web tools were developed to improve the efficiency of risk analysis, including risk assessment and outbreak management especially by integrating information from different sources and sectors allowing more in depth and One Health analysis of data. The prototype [COHESIVE Information System](#) (CIS) was developed to help integrate pathogen information (whole genome sequencing data and related metadata) from the human and veterinarian side at country level. The CIS can be very supportive in risk assessments providing graphical and interactive dashboards where spatial and temporal maps are combined with WGS analysis results. Three feasibility studies of such integration have been conducted among institutes in Italy, The Netherlands and Norway. Demo versions of CIS are published and available for the three involved countries.

The [FoodChain-Lab web application](#) as a joint output of EJP COHESIVE and EFSA projects helps tracing suspicious food items along complex global supply chains during foodborne incidents. It unifies tracing data visualisation, analysis and reporting in one modular framework and is already used by several food safety authorities.

The developed [shiny Rrisk](#) application is a web application supporting risk assessors in conducting probabilistic quantitative risk assessments. This is achieved with the provision of a rich state-of-the-art toolbox. Shiny Rrisk is part of the European Food Risk Assessment Training Programme (EU-FORA), which is an important initiative to prepare for future risk assessment needs. There are many methods that can be used for risk assessments, the shiny Rrisk application is just one example. Which method to use depends upon the needs but it may be difficult to determine which method fits best. Therefore, an [online decision support tool](#) was developed to help users decide on the most appropriate risk assessment method to use given their specific situation. The tool will direct users to different approaches depending on their needs. Attached to each approach is a list of related guidance documents, tools, and models, for instance the above mentioned shiny Rrisk application. The tool is designed so that it can be updated as new risk assessment resources emerge and improvements will continue to be made as they are identified through feedback.

During a risk analysis process, the pros and cons of suggested approaches need to be weighed. Also, how to include economic factors can be part of such a feasibility assessment. To facilitate this informed decision-making between different approaches in a field that is multidisciplinary and complex, a systematic review of economic analysis for foodborne zoonoses was performed with the aim to build on previous experience of economic analysis. We categorized a range of economic analysis approaches, grouping papers by where they applied similar or different approaches. We described the advantages and disadvantages of each approach. By doing so, we provide a strong starting point for any practitioner looking to conduct economic analyses for foodborne zoonoses. It is hoped that assembling this information will help improve and standardise future economic analyses.

Another aim of the project was to learn from past experiences with respect to zoonotic outbreaks. A systems mapping of the UK public information system around Q-fever was conducted, at that time a non-reportable disease in the UK. All UK-government publications relating to Q-fever were compiled and their data-sources tracked and mapped. A general European-level Q-fever surveillance map was

made in a similar way, using input from consortium members and available online publications. Process mapping through interviews with response teams following an outbreak was also conducted to understand how Q-fever cases were reported and identify weaknesses in its reporting pathway. This identified several gaps in the Q-fever reporting structure and supported the designation of Q-fever as a reportable disease in the UK in 2021.

Within COHESIVE a number of activities were performed to share knowledge both ways with international stakeholders such as EFSA, ECDC, FAO, WHO and OIE. For instance, EFSA was actively involved in the development of CIS, FCL Web and shiny Risk tools. Also, a close collaboration is established with the Tripartite, FAO, WHO and OIE who are developing the Surveillance and Information Sharing Operational Toolbox (SISOT). Several COHESIVE tools are and will be integrated in this toolbox.

In conclusion, within the project we have gathered and disseminated acquired knowledge, developed useful tools, and built capacity both within and between countries. There is a broad application for these results and tools, of which some are already used in practice such as the shiny Risk tool at BfR, the CIS in Italy and FCL Web internationally. For others, still some promotion and implementation activities are needed and planned. In addition, other OHEJP projects such as MATRIX and BeOne will continue upon the work done within COHESIVE. We see it as a mission to promote the importance of sustainable One Health approaches in risk analysis. This was done already in many ways during the project, but certainly will be continued afterwards in conjunction with implementation activities.

4.2. Work carried out in the JIP, scientific results, and integrative outcomes

4.2.1. WP1: Coordination, communication and sustainability

JIP2-WP1-T1: Coordination (M1-M36)

COHESIVE originally started with 17 partners from 9 countries. During the project PHE had to leave the project due to lack of capacity. On the other hand, three new partners were welcomed, INIAV (Portugal), VRI (Czech Republic) and ANSES (France).

A steering group was formed consisting of WP leaders and task leaders. The steering group has had regular online meetings varying from once every six weeks to weekly meetings depending on the need. In these meetings all tasks were discussed shortly, including (possible) problems. Also, general tasks were discussed and decided upon, such as annual meetings and reports.

The progression of COHESIVE was hampered strongly by the COVID-19 pandemic in several ways, such as no availability of key personnel, sickness, travel restrictions and local lockdowns. Therefore, two extensions of half a year each were granted.

Regular online meetings were organised between the contact persons of EFSA and ECDC and the coordinator of COHESIVE. There are links with other OHEJP projects such as ORION, NOVA, IDEMBRU, BEONE and MATRIX and links to initiatives of the Tripartite FAO, WHO, OIE such as SISOT and 'Multisectoral Coordination Mechanism' (MCM) working groups. At the start of the project, it became clear that three projects had identified the problem of using different terminology between sectors. It

was decided to develop a glossary. This was done together with NOVA and ORION, who has led the development and resulted in a publication (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2021.100263>).

JIP2-WP1-T2: Communication/dissemination (M1-M36)

Many communication and dissemination activities took place during the project. Below a selection of those activities related to the overarching project are mentioned. Most activities can be found in the list at the bottom of this report including the activities related to specific tasks.

During the project six meetings were organised for the whole consortium, a kick-off meeting, four annual meetings (two in 2019) and an end symposium. Those meetings were also open to (and attended by) other OHEJP members and other stakeholders such as EFSA, ECDC, ministries, FAO, WHO, OIE. Sometimes, specific sessions were organised for stakeholders. A meeting in 2018, consisting of two workshops organised by WP2/3 and WP4, was also open to all OHEJP members and stakeholders. EFSA, ECDC, PMT members, people from other OHEJP projects as well as people from five other partners attended this workshop, of which VRI and INIAV joined COHESIVE after the workshop.

There has been good contact with the communication team of OHEJP. COHESIVE actively provided information on the project for newsletters (eight times) and made announcements of activities in the agenda. Also, Twitter and LinkedIn were used. A factsheet of COHESIVE was produced at the beginning of the project to provide some general information about the project and was spread during live events, such as OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting.

COHESIVE was presented on many occasions, for instance at PMT and POC meetings, at the ASM in Dublin (2018), at the 6th One Health World Congress, at the IAFP European Symposium on Food Safety conference (2021), at the Annual research day at SVA in Sweden (2019), at EFSA meeting for new EU partners (2021), to Canadian public health and veterinary organisations (2021), to the SISOT working group of the Tripartite (2019). As a spin off, a workshop on systems thinking, originally planned as a satellite workshop before the ASM in Prague was developed and took place online on October 8, 2021. There was a lot of interest for this workshop (~140 applicants), therefore it is intended to give two additional workshops in 2022. COHESIVE has been involved in two OHEJP summer schools and was involved in organising a CPD module for PhD students on outbreak preparedness. This is a particularly important topic which fits very well within the key issues COHESIVE wants to address (be prepared in a One Health fashion for emerging zoonoses) and which is more than ever relevant.

4.2.2. WP2. Integrated risk-analysis at the national level

JIP2-WP2-T1: Development of guidelines for national One Health structures (M1-M26)

The main goal of this task is to develop guidelines to support countries to set up **national** One Health systems (such as present in for instance The Netherlands and UK) or other ways to strengthen human-veterinary collaborations. The aim is to improve signalling, risk assessment and response by better communication, (early) exchange of information, sharing of knowledge and joint forces. This is important for (re)emerging pathogens, but also the response to notifiable pathogens will profit from better collaboration. Since countries are very different in many aspects, no blueprint can be made for such One Health systems. In an integrated approach web-based guidelines were developed with the title 'One Health: Setting up a risk analysis system for zoonoses'. The URLs are www.ohras.eu and www.onehealthguidelines.eu. To get there, a co-creative process was followed. This started with a

needs assessment consisting of workshops, focus groups, questionnaires, and interviews. The main conclusion was that there is a need for such guidelines which should focus on operation and implementation. Key principles such as respect, trust and responsibility are considered important as they can drive behaviour, decision-making, collaboration, and governance processes in relation to setting up a One Health Risk Analysis System (OHRAS)([see poster](#)). In the first two years a lot of (physical) workshops were organised, gathering information. This was a highly effective approach, which was disturbed by COVID. After postponing physical workshops a couple of times, at a certain moment it was concluded that physical meetings were no longer an option and virtual workshops were organised instead. These were very labour intensive to organise and less efficient.

The guideline consists of five steppingstones that countries can follow to set up or improve the human-veterinary-food-environment collaboration in the area of risk analysis of zoonoses, namely set priority and goal, stakeholder analysis, systems mapping of the current situation, designing a OHRAS, implementing a OHRAS. For designing and implementing a OHRAS, information is given on six essential One Health activities namely OH Signalling, OH Risk Assessment, OH Feasibility Assessment, OH risk Management, OH Coordinated Communication and OH Governance. The guideline is web based to facilitate easy searching of dedicated information, based on the needs of the user for instance when only wanting to implement a OH Risk Assessment team. During the needs assessment barriers hampering One Health collaboration were identified and confirmed by another method in WP3.1. Suggestions are made on how to deal with four of them, gaining political will, obtaining trust, sharing information and communication. The guideline can be seen as a toolbox harboring a set of tools, such as the systems mapping workshop, an interactive tool to design a OHRAS, Terms of Reference guidance with prefilled formats. Also links to other useful tools, including tools developed in other COHESIVE workpackages. There has been close collaboration with the SISOT working group of the Tripartite FAO, OIE and WHO. There will be cross reference between the SISOT toolbox and the COHESIVE guidelines for risk analysis of zoonoses. The guidelines will become part of the SISOT toolbox. The guidelines will be linked to the MedVetNet Association (MVNA) website, to secure long-term sustainability.

JIP2-WP2-T2: Development of structured decision making (M1-M24)

The deliverable for this task was delivered in late-2019 and the tool finalized in mid-2020. We produced a decision-support tool to help the user decide on the most appropriate method to use when tasked with conducting a risk assessment for a specific situation. The tool has been significantly improved since the delivery in 2019. The tool is designed so that it can be updated as new risk assessment resources emerge. This has been done once already with the integration of the tripartite joint risk assessment tool. The tool will direct the user to one of fifteen risk assessment approaches and provide relevant guidance documents, tools and models under each one. The decision-tree questions were based on decision-making themes, such as time availability, which were identified from a workshop exercise with other members of the COHESIVE consortium. The approaches were finalized by sourcing the broad experience of risk assessors from the Animal and Plant Health Agency. Through linkage with task 3.5, the decision-tree has incorporated economic analysis methodologies. The tool was showcased at the EJP annual science conference in Copenhagen, and again at the COHESIVE final symposium. A paper has also been written to accompany the tool, now [published](#) in the One Health journal. The most recent updates to the contents of the tool are being carried out based on feedback from the COHESIVE final symposium.

JIP2-WP2-T3: Knowledge transfer and dissemination (M25-M35)

The aim of this task is the pilot-testing of the developed tools, specifically the guidelines developed in WP2.1. The guidelines focus on implementation and operationalisation. The idea was to have pilots in several European countries to start with implementing or strengthening the collaboration between the human-veterinary-food domain in the area of risk analysis of (a group of) zoonoses. By doing that during the project experiences within the pilots could feed back to further improve the guidelines. Four countries showed interest, Norway, Portugal, Belgium, and Italy. As indicated under WP2.1, the guidelines exist of five steppingstones. The idea was to support the countries with these steps, defining the group of zoonoses and goal, performing a stakeholder analysis in a small group followed by a systems mapping workshop to give insight into the current situation. This systems mapping workshop is a highlight and crucial in the implementation process in which the most important stakeholders are engaged and made enthusiastic about an OH approach for risk analysis in the chosen group of zoonoses. This can be seen as a short-term mission in which moderators from COHESIVE visit the pilot country and support the local organisers. Having a physical meeting is important to get support, trust and get to know each other. Due to COVID-19 the progression which was on scheme beginning of 2020 was stopped abruptly. However, eventually Norway and Portugal were able to have successful physical systems mapping workshops in September and November 2021, respectively. In Belgium, the workshop should have taken place on March 27 2020, but was cancelled a few days in advance. After several postponements, it now will take place in 2022. Italy did part of the stakeholder analysis, but also postponed due to COVID priorities. These experiences will be used to improve the guidelines and the systems mapping workshop itself. Unfortunately, hardly any time will be left for the following steps, reducing the impact of these show cases for other countries. Luckily, the OHEJP project Matrix will proceed with the guidelines, using feedback from these pilots, following up on the pilots and performing additional pilots. The systems mapping workshop for Denmark and Sweden are being planned.

4.2.3. WP3: Towards an EU zoonoses structure

JIP2-WP3-T1: Explore current ways for exchanging signals between countries and cross disciplines – pathway analysis (M1-M24)

The original aim of the task was to perform a pathway analysis of the exchange of zoonotic signals across disciplines and countries. The methods to perform this task were not specified in the application. Thus, physical workshops were held to clarify the aim and to discuss how to perform the task. The following aim was decided: 1) to identify factors that contribute to well-functioning systems for sharing signals of zoonotic events, 2) to identify barriers of sharing signals, and 3) suggest improvements for signal sharing, within and between countries in Europe. The participants of the task from Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Sweden, and the UK agreed on a qualitative approach. The intention was to perform in-depth interviews of persons working at local, regional, or national level within the sectors of animal health, food safety and public health. The purpose was not to obtain a full overview of systems for signal sharing, but rather to ask experienced professionals of their experiences of signal sharing. A common interview guideline was developed. The participants aimed at interviewing a minimum of five persons per country. Purposeful sampling was applied for selection of the interview persons. The task participants in each country chose which functions, institutions, or persons to approach for an interview. The interviewees were informed about the aim of the study, and that the information would be treated pseudonymised both at country, institute, and individual level and they were encouraged to speak freely. All interviews were recorded and transcribed. The interview

material was analysed thematically: first at a national level, and then jointly at a multi-country level. Nine themes were identified, and findings were remarkably similar between countries. In summary, formal systems (procedures, routines, legislation) for signal sharing both at the national and international level were seen as important. Roles and mandates were sometimes unclear, and there was a need for understanding between sectors. Significant barriers for data sharing, both technical and legal, and both within and between sectors, were highlighted. The main finding was the importance of personal contacts for sharing of signals, and early informal contacts were described as pivotal. Regular meetings, both at national and international level, enable personal contacts and are beneficial for signal sharing, whereas disruption of networks e.g. through reorganization or lack of funding to arrange meetings were described as negative for signal sharing. Concern of overreaction at the recipient of the signal (in another country or sector) was raised, with potential negative consequences for e.g. trade interests. In relation to this, a reluctance to report into anonymous systems without knowing who receives the signal, unless being certain that there was a true outbreak was raised. From the analysis it was clear that formal systems, data access and technical solutions go hand in hand with personal networks, trust and understanding of each other's roles and mandates. One cannot replace the other and both are important for well-functioning sharing of signals.

JIP2-WP3-T2: Horizon Scanning Pilot Exercise (M1-M24)

The aim of the Task 3.2 was to make an inventory and assessment of tools for Horizon Scanning (HS) appropriate for One Health. Horizon scanning is a foresight methodology that can be used to identify issues of concern or impact in a medium or long-term time span. A literature review was undertaken to explore which horizon scanning tools and methods are in use. A questionnaire prepared within COHESIVE and sent to EJP member institutes in 2018 contained some questions on the use of horizon scanning. Of the 24 respondents 8 had experience of horizon scanning but only within their sector, not across sectors.

The international organisations FAO, OIE and WHO have applied horizon scanning tools for foresight predictions but the experience at country level seems to be scarcer. Within the task two pilot horizon scanning exercises were undertaken. In the first exercise at the meeting in Uppsala, Sweden in April 2019 the participants were introduced to the concept after which an exercise on stakeholder views was done. In November 2019 at the annual meeting of Rome a second exercise was performed. In the second exercise a longer list of issues of importance within One Health was compiled, after which the issues were categorised in themes. The issues identified as potential drivers for emerging zoonotic risks were for instance an ageing population, trade, increase of travel, new consumption habits, new pathogens and the interface between wildlife and humans. The pilot exercises performed by a multi-country and multi-sectorial team resulted in issues of importance and provided a model possible to be fine-tuned to be used for planning of surveillance and control activities within and across countries and sectors.

JIP2-WP3-T3: Retrospective systems analysis of detection of outbreaks (M6-M30)

The aim of this task is to learn from past experiences with respect to zoonotic outbreaks. Since public information systems (PIS) are a large part of the response to non-reportable diseases, the first task was to develop a systems map of the PIS in place for Q-fever in the UK (at the time this was a non-reportable disease). This was built by searching the public domain for public facing information related to Q-fever, published by government organisations. The data sources of these were then traced back, logging the primary data sources, and organisations involved in producing and analysing these data

and illustrating these using a systems map. A workshop was carried out to observe the general structures of these PIS in other consortium member states. This was compiled into a larger systems map and will be updated following interest from stakeholders at the final symposium. Collaboration with participants in adding detail to this map will improve its quality and impact. Following these systems mapping exercises, process mapping was carried out to understand the process by which Q-fever cases are reported in the UK. This was done by verifying the pathway by which symptomatic animals lead to confirmed cases and the formation of outbreak response teams with experts at the Animal and Plant Health Agency working closely with the disease. This identified gaps in the reporting structure, particularly if samples are sent to private laboratories rather than government laboratories. This finding has helped support a legislative change to make Q-fever reportable across the UK.

JIP2-WP3-T4: Pilot One-Health Early Warning System (M25-M36)

The aim of this task was to enhance informal exchange of signals. According to the application this task was to be performed during the last year of the project and build on experiences gathered within the previous tasks. The participating institutes APHA, RIVM and SVA organised a digital 2.5 h workshop via Microsoft Teams on February 3, 2021 to share experiences on some low-level threats in Europe. A total of 21 persons from eight countries (Czech Republic, Denmark, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Sweden, United Kingdom) participated in the workshop. Three topics were discussed in the workshop: an increase of food-borne cryptosporidiosis, monitoring of antimicrobial resistance and increase of incidents of *Brucella canis* in dogs. The workshop clearly showed a need for further activities on brucellosis in dogs since several of the participants were clearly facing the same challenges. A spin-off digital workshop in collaboration with the OHEJP project IDEMBRU was conducted on May 18, 2021 on brucellosis in dogs. The workshop attracted over 170 participants from a range of countries within and outside Europe. The participation of persons from many different disciplines from different sectors (epidemiologists, diagnostic experts, risk assessors, operational risk managers, bacteriologists, food safety experts) was very fruitful. Prior to the workshop, IDEMBRU and COHESIVE participants created an online survey with questions on analytical methods, notification status, surveillance, for instance and sent it to the NRL Brucella contact persons. IDEMBRU and COHESIVE have continued co-operation and are summarising the outputs of the workshop and establishing clear data-gaps for continued international collaboration in this area. IDEMBRU, COHESIVE with some other partners are currently preparing a scientific manuscript on the results. A third digital workshop was organised on December 15, 2021. In this workshop zoonotic risks of *Salmonella* and Hantavirus in pet rats and feeder rats were discussed among the 30 participants as well as the risk of introduction of Crimean Congo Haemorrhagic Fever via ticks of *Hyalomma* species. The task participants have created Terms of Reference for this forum and intend to continue with this collaboration although the COHESIVE project is finalised in December 2021. This group will make use of MS Teams to share information. Also, quick access to the tools developed in this project is facilitated. The aim of the group is not to affect the existing systems of data exchange or notifications, but to provide a channel to raise issues that currently lack a cross-sectorial platform.

JIP2-WP3-T5: Development of a tool for systematic cost-benefit analysis (CBA) (M25-M36)

The aim of this task was to compile and categorise various methods of economic analysis used to analyse foodborne zoonoses. This is hoped to help future economic analysts understand the available methodologies better and apply them in their own economic studies which could improve the quality of future assessments. Also, it may help standardize the highly diverse portfolio of approaches currently used. Initial work began assembling members of the COHESIVE consortium with experience

of economic analysis. Once a working group was established, a systematic review was conducted to find relevant economic analysis papers, focusing on those looking at zoonotic pathogens spread through the consumption of meat and animal products, defined by us as foodborne zoonoses (though they included some pathogens not traditionally considered foodborne such as Q-fever and MRSA). This yielded 1,515 articles. Of these were 578 duplicates and 888 were removed because they were not economic analyses or did not fit our criteria of foodborne zoonoses. Finally, nine were removed because there was no full text available or they were not written in English. The final forty papers were analysed by members of the team and data on the methodologies used in each were extracted by the different team members. This was used to describe the breakdown of papers with regards to pathogen, animal species, approach, and intervention they focused on. From this high-level image, the approaches were then explored deeper to categorise them and to describe the key features of each. This enabled comparisons to be drawn on the similarities and differences between papers and approaches, but also importantly, the advantages and disadvantages of using each given approach. All findings were collated in the [deliverable report](#) for this task. A presentation showcased these findings at the COHESIVE final symposium.

4.2.4. WP4: Data platform to facilitate risk-analysis and outbreak control

In WP4, free and open source webtools for outbreak situations and risk assessment were developed to support One Health stakeholders in their tasks. Interoperability with the main data exchange systems at EU level was ensured.

JIP2-WP4-T1: Molecular typing data and metadata – database creation

The objective of this task is to improve tasks efficiency on surveillance and outbreak management of One-Health organizations at the Member State level. This is achieved by integrating pathogens Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) data and related metadata from the human and veterinarian organizations of a country.

For this purpose, first, a survey has been conducted to gather detailed information on existing databases and information systems for WGS data management and analysis adopted or available among the Member States. Second, a feasibility study has been proposed to volunteer countries to evaluate costs and issues of data harmonisation among organisations at country level. It is important to underline that only technical aspects and no political ones have been evaluated.

The survey

The survey represented a first step for the evaluation of the technical feasibility of the interconnection of genetic data produced by the laboratories and metadata archives available in each country, as well as provided a reasoned list of the available Information Systems for WGS data and associated metadata. Eight countries answered the questionnaire: Sweden, Norway, Belgium, Portugal, The Netherlands, Austria, Czech Republic and Germany. Of the countries, 75% reported that no OH surveillance system is in place at the moment, but WGS data sharing exists. The questionnaire is available at <https://www.zenodo.org/record/3457753#.YbnUYpHMJhF>

Additionally, as a request of stakeholders, a clearer description of the Task 4.1 phases has been formulated and presented to EFSA representatives in March 2019 and during the stakeholder meeting at the COHESIVE Annual Meeting (held at Uppsala, April 2019). This led to a new version of the WP4.1

description. After the presentation of the revised WP4.1 description, EFSA declared that the task purpose is both clear and interesting to them.

The feasibility study

The steps of the feasibility study were:

1. Choice of pathogen species for the study
2. List of the involved organizations
3. List of all the useful information sources,
4. A prototype system to let the Member State evaluate the expected improvements, i.e., (i) the integration of the systems and (ii) the possibility to provide EU harmonized output.

For the last point, the prototype COHESIVE Information System (CIS) has been developed. This system allows (i) storing of WGS data and related metadata; (ii) launching of bioinformatics analysis (iii), and retrieving of WGS analytical results together with metadata using graphical and interactive dashboards.

Three feasibility studies have been conducted among public institutions of the following countries: Italy, The Netherlands and Norway. Consequently, three CIS instances have been provided to the involved countries:

- Italy: https://cohesive.izs.it/cis_italy/
- The Netherlands: https://cohesive.izs.it/cis_holland/
- Norway: https://cohesive.izs.it/cis_norway/

Details of the studies have been reported on Deliverables [D-JIP2-4.1.2](#) and [D-JIP2-4.1.3](#).

The COHESIVE Information System (CIS)

An important result of the Task is the COHESIVE Information System (CIS, see [Deliverable D-JIP2-4.1.1](#)). Starting as a part of the feasibility study, it has been enriched to become a prototype of a full-featured One-Health Information System for microbial pathogens. The CIS allows (i) storing of WGS data and related metadata; (ii) launching of bioinformatics analysis and (iii) retrieving of analytical results together with metadata using graphical and interactive dashboards.

It is a WEB based information system designed to integrate and harmonize pathogens information from the human and veterinarian organizations of a country. For this reason, it has a highly flexible database schema, able to accommodate any specific organization needs. Moreover, the outputs of the integrated system have been designed to be as compatible as possible with EFSA/ECDC systems.

The CIS can be also configured to launch custom bioinformatics analysis and pipelines. To install specific tools on CIS demo versions, partial information was gathered from the involved Member States. Additional specifications have been taken from the deliverable of the OHEJP ORION project “The One Health Sequencing for Surveillance Handbook” (<https://oh-sfs-handbook.readthedocs.io/>). Leveraging on such information, we assembled a pipeline, named NgsManager (available at <https://github.com/genpat-it/ngsmanager>), able to analyse bacterial strains in general, and *Listeria monocytogenes* in particular. Additionally, NgsManager is also able to manage SARS-CoV-2 samples. NgsManager has been configured on the CIS demo instances (See [Deliverable D-JIP2-4.1.4](#)).

Finally, the CIS provides some powerful graphical and interactive dashboards allowing cluster analysis of samples combining WGS data with spatial and temporal maps.

The interoperability between CIS and the two BfR software tools (FCL – FoodChain-Lab and shiny Risk) has been tested using a CIS demo version available for BfR (https://cohesive.izs.it/cis_bfr/). Some CSV files can be extracted from the demo and imported into FCL through a specific FCL procedure.

The project has been released as open source project on GitHub (<https://github.com/genpat-it/CIS>). A demo version of the final version of the system is available at the address <https://cohesive.izs.it/>

JIP2-WP4-T2: Development of a platform-independent tracing framework

As a requirement analysis for the tracing framework, a comprehensive search was performed to evaluate available tracing approaches, algorithms and tools and their usefulness for an integrative tracing framework (subtask 1). The result is a report ([D-JIP2-4.5](#)) and a [web-based interactive table comparing the functionalities of the tools](#) retrieved from the search. In subtask 2, the **FoodChain-Lab web application** (FCL Web) was developed as modular tracing framework. For this, a server platform for the test and production environment including a continuous integration pipeline as well as a restricted user area and the legal framework were designed and developed. Based on the results from subtask 1, several modules relevant for tracing – in part developed in the framework of other projects - were integrated in FCL Web: an interactive visualisation and analysis module, a reporting module, a synchronisation module with the FCL desktop version and other tracing tools. Since November 2020, FCL Web is in production mode (<https://fcl-portal.bfr.berlin>). A second release including new functions and a performance optimisation became available in August 2021. Details can be found in [D-JIP-4.2.2](#), [M-JIP2-10](#), and in the COHESIVE annual reports. In subtask 3, additional meaningful surveillance and outbreak data were integrated in FCL Web after clarification of data needs with public and veterinary health institutes. A data format for sample and case data was developed in JSON and in csv format, depending on the data source. It is possible to display sample results (e.g. phylogenetic distance obtained from the COHESIVE Information System (WP4.1)) of cases, products or companies within the tracing network scores and visualise them via different colors in the network as well as in the reporting module. Case and sample data visualisation was tested in the framework of case studies. In addition, the NOVA likelihood tool was integrated into FCL Web in a local test system. Details are described in [D-JIP2-4.2.3](#) and [M-A2.COHESIVE.4.10](#). With FCL Web as a joint outcome of EJP COHESIVE and the EFSA-BfR cooperation, a powerful, easily accessible and intuitive tracing tool became available for Member States and European authorities to facilitate a fast and reliable investigation of foodborne incidents. It is already in use by several Member States, EFSA and U.S. FDA. In 2020 FCL Web became part of the SISOT tool box of OIE, WHO and FAO. The achievements and the spirit of COHESIVE (integrativeness, information sharing) will contribute to future projects on traceability together with EFSA e.g. by integrating FCL Web into a European framework of tracing tools and by developing a universal tracing data exchange format.

JIP2-WP4-T3: Development of a platform-independent risk-assesment framework

The shiny Risk application (WP4.3) is a Web-based tool to support risk assessors in the definition of quantitative risk models and in the uncertainty analysis of exposure assessment. The software consists of several modules which together compose a framework for probabilistic risk assessment. Shiny Risk Shiny supports model building (setting up variables, parameters, equations), 1- and 2-dimensional Monte-Carlo Simulation to separate uncertainty and variability, data fitting, model visualization, schema for the assessment of uncertainties (according to the EFSA guidance), ensures transparency through identity between the model and its documentation, includes auto-reporting, and provides

state-of-art risk modelling methodology through rich and extensible functionality (resampling, bootstrapping).

In a requirement analysis ([D-JIP2-4.3.1](#)) building blocks have been identified that support quantitative stochastic risk assessment, advanced simulation techniques, documentation and extended usability.

Based on the results of this analysis it was decided that the tool should be an R (www.r-project.org) web application hosted on the server side at BfR. Clients access the application via the internet. This way was chosen for several reasons. a) The web application can be maintained more easily and package dependencies are easier to handle. This is an important aspect, as shiny Risk uses code from various models in the R universe, in addition to newly developed code. This creates dependencies and the constant further development of non-own modules can lead to problems. b) The web application can be realized in a simple way with R-Shiny and does not require any additional programming knowledge, so that the available staff can realize many modules of the program themselves. c) This ensures that the program can be adapted to the new requirements for quantitative risk assessment in the future. d) Not only shiny Risk will be available as an open-source resource, but also the code itself. Since the program is implemented in R, users will be able to make any necessary adaptations to their own requirements on their own. To make this possible, a large part of the program code was realised as S4 and S5 classes. Since R is a very common programming language, we can address a broad audience.

The shiny Risk program and instructions are available via [Github](#). In time the program will also be made available as a web service via a BfR web server.

The current version of shiny Risk implements ([D-JIP2-4.3.2](#)) access to state-of-the art procedures of quantitative stochastic risk modelling through provision of a GUI (Graphical User Interface) that facilitates the whole modelling process (including the creation of model variables, setting parameters and equations and the documentation). Uncertainty as well as uncertainty and variability can be considered through One- and Two-Dimensional Monte-Carlo Simulations. Fitting of distributions to data is realized without leaving the application.

It should be noted at this point that shiny Risk is in constant development, both with regard to the tools implemented for quantitative risk assessment and with regard to the technical implementation of the programme. This continuous further development is due to the fact that shiny Risk is regularly used as a tool for carrying out risk assessments at BfR. The application results in the need for adaptations and we hope that opening up the programme to users outside the BfR will bring about further adaptations to meet the needs.

The verification and validation ([D-JIP2-4.3.3](#)) of the web application shiny Risk includes both the testing of the frontend, the usability of the GUI and the validation of the backend (correct implementation of the routines). When risk assessment experts used the frontend, they recognized that few input masks were difficult to understand, and appropriate adaptations were made to fix these problems. Of course, it will never be possible to create an application that meets all user requirements. It was therefore decided that a functional e-mail address would be set up at the BfR via which questions about the application of the shiny Risk program could be sent to the person responsible for

maintaining the program. Support regarding the use of the program will also be provided through thomas.selhorst@bfr.bund.de on request.

The shiny Risk application will continue to be used for risk assessments within BfR and will also be available as a tool for other risk assessors. Shiny Risk will be introduced as part of national and international training programs on quantitative risk assessments held regularly (German Universities and The European Food Risk Assessment Fellowship Programme Series (EU-Fora) which will take place annually until 2025, for example).

JIP2-WP4-T4: Dissemination

In WP4.4 many dissemination activities for COHESIVE took place. In the framework of COHESIVE annual meetings, presentations and workshops for WP4 tools were conducted for the COHESIVE community. WP4 tools were presented at the One Health EJP CPD module “Digital Innovation for One Health Practitioners”, the Online Advanced Course on “Innovative tools and methods for ensuring seafood authenticity”, the ASM Satellite Workshop “Online Software Fair” and at One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meetings. Results and impact of COHESIVE in general and particularly of WP4.2 (FCL Web) and WP4.3 (Risk) were presented at the German OH EJP Mirror Group meeting for e.g. the German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture. Details on the dissemination activities are described in the deliverable report [D-JIP2-4.4.1](#).

4.3. Project self-assessment

The mission of COHESIVE was to develop **sustainable One Health approaches** with respect to *surveillance, signalling, assessing and controlling zoonoses* at the national and regional level **within EU countries and across borders**. This has clearly been accomplished. However, due to progressive insights some tasks took a slightly different angle than the original plan to improve or extend the outcome, but all deliverables and milestones were reached.

The development of the guidelines in WP2.1 was a challenge in several ways. The decision to make it a web-based guideline was a good decision. However, that led to some technical challenges and more work than anticipated. This task was also, as many tasks within COHESIVE, hampered by the COVID crisis. First of all several key personnel was unavailable. This was especially the case for scientists working at the public health side, who were underrepresented already. Also, this task largely depended on physical workshops. The ones organised were very fruitful. When COVID started, in first instance those workshops were postponed and for a period less work was done which obviously led to a delay. Eventually, a switch was made to virtual workshops, which were labour intensive to organise with a clear lower yield. Therefore, there was quite a delay. The guidelines are ready for use. Improving them based upon the pilots performed task WP2.3 was not possible because the pilots were only performed at the end of the project and the follow up afterwards did not happen yet. Before starting we hoped to find two countries to volunteer for the pilot, but four countries did. Unfortunately, due to the COVID crisis only two performed the pilot workshop and the two others only did part of the pilot.

The title of task WP2.2 was ‘developing structured decision-making for One Health risk assessment’. This goal could be fulfilled without deviation. The resultant tool provides a framework for structured decision-making, and compiles a broad range of risk assessment approaches, useful in a range of circumstances.

The title of task 3.1 was: Explore current ways for exchanging signals between countries and cross disciplines – pathway analysis. The plan was to identify current processes for data sharing between countries, and key persons as a basis for building a contact-network. During workshops in the start of the project, it was decided to broaden the scope and include sharing of data within countries, not only between countries. With the broadening of the scope, it was further decided to explore hindrances and factors facilitating sharing of early signals, as well as suggested improvements for sharing signals in general rather than analysing current pathways for data sharing. The reason for this change was that such results were assumed to be more general applicable and useful.

The task 3.2 fulfilled the aim of performing an inventory of horizon scanning tools and methods and tested the use of some of the selected tools of horizon scanning in two exercises on expert assessments. The methods could be useful for medium and long-term foresight planning of surveillance or control activities but need to be fine-tuned.

The title of task 3.3 was ‘retrospective system analysis of detection of outbreaks’. This goal could be fulfilled without deviation from the original title, however additional aspects such as the mapping of public information systems for Q-fever provide some additional information not just on how outbreaks are detected, but how public information is used to prevent future outbreaks when a disease is not reportable. The process mapping exercise on the surveillance system for Q-fever in the UK following an outbreak fits strongly into the original project proposal, finding weaknesses in the surveillance process through this retrospective analysis.

The task 3.4 fulfilled the aim of enhancing the exchange of signals across sectors and countries. For this, an informal international group has been set up with Terms of Reference, which will continue to meet after the project ends. The first workshop on sharing signals showed that many countries experienced similar kind of issues around *Brucella canis*, indicating the added value of such exchange of information between countries. In the dedicated *B. canis* workshop more than 170 persons from different disciplines from many sectors came together (epidemiologists, diagnostic experts, risk assessors, operational risk managers, bacteriologists, food safety experts) which was very fruitful. Within the task no platform for tools developed in the other tasks was created, as indicated in the application, but the existing tools of MS Teams are used. The members of the group will have easy access to the developed tools. The last workshop organised further confirmed the usefulness of the informal information sharing and the group intends to continue with the forum. The way of working of the group will be further refined along the way as holds also true for getting acknowledged for its added value by the One Health community.

The title of task 3.5 was ‘development of a tool for systematic cost-benefit analysis’. The scope of this project needed to be adjusted to better fit the research need in this area and to account for severe resource limitations in personnel due to COVID-19. It was realised that cost-benefit analysis makes up a small part of the wider context of economic analysis in the One Health sector. Other approaches exist, such as cost-effectiveness analysis, partial budget analysis and cost-of-disease analysis. It was thought that a systematic review that could assemble all relevant approaches and help describe each to provide a picture of what had been done before, could be more beneficial and more achievable at this stage as a tool for future economic analysis in this sector.

For task 4.1, EFSA/ECDC asked at the beginning of the project for more details and confirmation that this task did not overlap with their activities. A clearer description of the task 4.1 phases has been presented to EFSA representatives in March 2019 and during the stakeholder meeting at the COHESIVE Annual Meeting (held at Uppsala, April 2019). This led to a new version of the WP4.1 description (see AWP 2019). After the presentation of the revised WP4.1 description, EFSA declared that task purpose is both clear and interesting to them. The task itself was not changed, only described otherwise.

COVID-19 crisis blocked for long time the sub-task titled “Linking of the national databases with the COHESIVE prototype information system and the epidemiological analysis tools”, leading to less advanced linkage than hoped for.

With respect to WP4.2 and 4.4, all project aims were met. With respect to WP4.3 the ‘Development of a platform-independent risk modeling framework’ is completed, but the program could not be deployed yet to a BfR server due to internal procedures to ensure web security. Until this issue is solved, the program is available at <https://github.com/RobertOpitz/shinyRisk>.

There was a pleasant cooperative atmosphere throughout all teams in the project. In both WP2 and WP3 one of the main topics was that ‘knowing each other’ is important for (One Health) collaboration and is a major message. We have succeeded in that ourselves as well by organising many physical workshops. This ‘knowing each other’ helped us further down the project in the period physical workshops were no longer possible. A lot of people of many organisations and countries have been working together on this, leading to extended networks also important for further collaborations. Already new collaborations are in place, so also a collaboration with the OHEJP Matrix who will build upon results of COHESIVE. Throughout the project there was a lot of exchange of experiences between organisations/countries, which really benefitted the project. All together, we are proud of what has been achieved within COHESIVE. We hope that our developed tools and the insight and knowledge gained are of use to the One Health community.

4.4. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

4.4.1. Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-1.1	Kick-off meeting	3	3	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3754064	1, 4, 5, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-1.2	Website/platform operational	6	N/A	As the website of the overarching One Health EJP fulfilled our needs, no general COHESIVE website was developed	
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-1.3	Annual meeting	14	16	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3754232	1, 4, 5, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-1.4	Annual report	16	13	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3754249	1, 4, 5, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-1.5	Annual meeting	35	35	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5799269	1, 4, 5, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D- JIP2-1.6	Annual report	28	25	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5799297	1, 4, 5, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D- JIP2-1.7	Closing symposium	47	47	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5801635	1, 4, 5, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D- JIP2-1.8	Annual report	36	35	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5799384	1, 4, 5, 8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
COHESIVE JIP2	D- JIP2-1.9	Annual report	48	48	This report	1, 4, 5, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-2.1	Inventory of tools for systematic risk-assessment via questionnaire	8	8	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5786462	1, 5, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-2.2	Inventory and ambition workshop	12	11	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3754286	1, 5, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-2.3	Development of tool for systematic risk-assessment	18	24	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5786490	1, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-2.4	Thematic workshops	20	19	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3754296	1, 5, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D- JIP2-2.5	Development of common procedures and tools	46	48	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5801881	1, 5, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D- JIP2-2.6	Knowledge transfer and dissemination	48	48	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5802044	1, 5, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-3.1	Inventory and ambition workshop	12	11	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3754324	5, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-3.2	Thematic workshops	20	18	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3754391	5, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-3.3	Pathway analysis of exchanging signals	36	36	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5796809	5, 8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-3.4	Inventory and analysis of tools for horizon scanning	18	18	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5796567	8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-3.5	System analysis of detection of outbreaks	46	46	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5796567	4, 7, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-3.6	Knowledge transfer and dissemination	47	48	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5799719	5, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-3.7	Drivers of change in One Health– a horizon scanning exercise (new deliverable)	36	36	Additional deliverable https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5799763 .	8
COHESIVE JIP2	D- JIP2-3.8	Tool for systematic cost-benefit analysis	47	47	Additional deliverable https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5786026	2, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-4.1.1	Implemented database	17	18	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3257121	4, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-4.1.2	Description of the links and the linked databases	21	21	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3465248	4, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-4.1.3	Databases containing the country data	26	27	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3725941	4, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-4.1.4	Description of the pipelines	47	47	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5764231	4, 8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		implemented to feed the analysis tools with the data stored in the three databases of this project				
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-4.2.1	Report of available tools and algorithms and ranking of most valuable features	12	18	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3754450	4, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-4.2.2	FoodChain-Lab with integrated network analysis module as a web-service browser-ready, open source and implemented in the BfR cloud	32	32	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5767104 FCL Web is accessible at https://fcl-portal.bfr.berlin	4, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-4.2.3	Integration and analysis of epi-data from 4.1 → WGS-Epi module and selected features from IA-1, WP2, WP3	47	47	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5764213 FCL Web with integrated outbreak and epidemiological data is accessible at https://fcl-portal.bfr.berlin	4, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-4.3.1	Report section about user requirements,	10	18	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3754456	4, 8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
		relevant modelling modules and final specification for a modelling tool				
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-4.3.2	Populating a model project model repository. Harmonised graphical user. Interface prototypes. Technical documentation and user guidance.	47	47	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5792876	4, 8
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-4.3.3	Final testing design elaborated. Report section about testing results (internal standards). Report section about testing results using external comparative models). Final release (open access).	42	47	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5792901 Shiny Risk available at https://github.com/RobertOpitz/shinyRisk	4, 8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
COHESIVE JIP2	D-JIP2-4.4.1	Each subtask conducts workshops, provides documentation and tutorials	48	48	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5797526	4, 8

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities ; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify); Co-creation of common procedures, tools and information to support One Health risk-analysis of zoonoses (national and international)

4.4.2. Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	Comments
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M1.1	Website/platform operational	6	NA	As the website of the overarching One Health EJP seems to fulfil our needs we did not develop our own website
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M1.2	Annual report	16	Yes	
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M1.3	Annual report	28	Yes	

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	Comments
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M1.4	Closing symposium	47	Yes	
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M1.5	Annual report	36	Yes	
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M1.6	Annual report	48	Yes	
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M2.1	Development of tool for systematic risk-assessment	18	Yes	
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M2.2	Development of common procedures and tools	46	Yes	
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M2.3	Knowledge transfer and dissemination	48	Yes	
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M3.1	Development of common procedures and tools for horizon scanning	26	Yes	
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M3.2	Pathway and system analysis of signal exchange and outbreak detection	24	Yes	
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M3.3	Local dissemination	42	Yes	
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M4.1	Initial workshop	2	Yes	
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M4.2	Prioritization of requirements for risk modeling framework	6	Yes	

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	Comments
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M4.3	Prioritization of most valuable features of available tracing tools	12	Yes	
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M4.4	Databases for WGS data consistent with COMPARE standards, for the metadata of the samples included in the WGS database, and for the data collected by classical epidemiology investigations (case-control studies)	17	Yes	
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M4.5	Fully operating and linked databases	21	Yes	
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M4.6	Prototype for tracing framework ready	24	Yes	
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M4.7	Databases containing the country data	26	Yes	
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M4.8	Prototype for risk modeling framework ready	30	Yes	
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M4.9	Availability of the pipelines from the databases to the analysis tools	40	Yes	
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M4.10	Analysis of epi-data into tracing framework enclosed	40	Yes	
COHESIVE JIP2	M-JIP2-M4.11	Final release of risk modeling framework	40	Yes	

4.5. Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
<p>Rob Dewar, Christine Gavin, Catherine McCarthy, Rachel A. Taylor, Charlotte Cook, Robin R.L. Simons, A user-friendly decision support tool to assist one-health risk assessors (2021). <i>One Health</i>, 100266, ISSN 2352-7714, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2021.100266 Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5215753#.YR0iAI5KjIV Tool: http://cohesive.onehealthiejp.eu/</p>	Yes		Yes. £1330
<p>Buschhardt T, Günther T, Skjerdal T, Torpdahl M, Gethmann J, Filippitzi ME, Maassen C, Jore S, Ellis-Iversen J, Filter M; OHEJP Glossary Team. A one health glossary to support communication and information exchange between the human health, animal health and food safety sectors. <i>One Health</i>. 2021 May 8;13:100263. doi: 10.1016/j.onehlt.2021.100263. PMID: 34041347; PMCID: PMC8141924. A one health glossary to support communication and information exchange between the human health, animal health and food safety sectors Zenodo</p>	Yes		Yes. Processing charges covered by ORION
<p>Iolanda Mangone, Nicolas Radomski, Adriano Di Pasquale, Andrea Santurbano, Paolo Calistri, Cesare Cammà, Kitty Maassen; Refinement of the COHESIVE Information System towards a unified ontology of food terms for the public health organizations. <i>IFOW 2021 Integrated Food Ontology Workshop, September 15-18, Bolzano Italy</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5645679 http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2969/paper11-IFOW.pdf</p>	Yes		Yes

Additional output

In this integrative project, the most important output in addition to the output of deliverables such as guidelines and tools, are the activities to promote the mission of project with the eventual goal to get the results implemented. For this purpose we have performed many dissemination activities in the

shape of presentations, workshops and such. Also, COHESIVE general meetings were open for all OHEJP members and stakeholders.

Only the oral and poster presentations at 'official' meetings as well as webinars are mentioned in this section. Other dissemination activities are mentioned in the dissemination forms. Also several publications are in preparation.

Oral presentations:

Dealing With (re)Emerging Zoonoses: A One Health Approach in The Netherlands. Catharina Maassen, Mathilde Uiterwijk Margreet te Wierik , Hendrik-Jan Roest. *OHEJP ASM, 24-05-019, Dublin, Ireland.*
[OneHealth ASM 2019 Proceedings.pdf \(onehealthejp.eu\)](#)

One Health Actions Implementation Guide (Guia de Implementação de Ações Uma Só Saúde). Sandra Cavaco Gonçalves. One Health Day Celebration Seminar - When "ONE HEALTH!" Happens. (SEMINÁRIO DE COMEMORAÇÃO DO DIA MUNDIAL DA UMA SÓ SAÚDE - Quando acontece "UMA SÓ SAÚDE!"), 04-11-2019, Lisbon, Portugal

Shiny.R.risk ein neues webbasiertes Modellierungstool für quantitative Risikobewertungen. Christin Wallstab. DACH Epidemiologietagung 2019, 04/06-09-2019, Freising Weihenstephan, Germany

COHESIVE project, task 4.1. Adriano De Pasquale. WGS-based surveillance: a cog-wheel workshop to detect links and promote collaboration among OHEJP projects and external initiatives, 16-09-2019, Dubrovnik, Croatia

COHESIVE: Development of implementation guidelines to support countries with early warning, response and control of (emerging) zoonoses in a One Health fashion. Frank Koenen, Sandra Cavaco Gonçalves, Solveig Jore, Charlotte Cook, Elina Lahti, Karin Nyberg, Malin Jonsson, Frits Vlaanderen, Ines Mogami, Mathilde Uiterwijk, Rosangela Tozzoli, Kitty Maassen on behalf of the COHESIVE WP2 consortium. OHEJP ASM, 27-05-2020, virtual.
<https://onehealthejp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/D3.12-OHEJP-ASM-2020-Abstract-book.pdf>

Factors affecting signals sharing of zoonotic events: a qualitative exploratory study in Italy. Michele Luca D'Errico, Maria Nöremark, Chiara Cattaneo, Rosangela Tozzoli, Gaia Scavia. OHEJP ASM, 27-05-2020, virtual. <https://onehealthejp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/D3.12-OHEJP-ASM-2020-Abstract-book.pdf>

The COHESIVE Information System: a cross EJP projects example. Adriano Di Pasquale, Fernanda Dorea, Karin Lagesen, Francesca Cito, Alessio Di Lorenzo, Paolo Calistri, Kitty Maassen. OHEJP ASM, 27-05-2020, virtual. <https://onehealthejp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/D3.12-OHEJP-ASM-2020-Abstract-book.pdf>

COHESIVE: Development of implementation guidelines to support countries with early warning, response and control of (emerging) zoonoses in a One Health fashion. Frank Koenen, Sandra Cavaco Gonçalves, Solveig Jore, Charlotte Cook, Elina Lahti, Karin Nyberg, Malin Jonsson, Frits Vlaanderen, Ines

Mogami, Mathilde Uiterwijk, Gaia Scavia, Kitty Maassen. World One Health Conference, 01-11-2020, Edinbrough, Scotland

One Health: Setting up a risk analysis system for zoonoses. Sandra Cavaco Gonçalves, Zuzana Nordeng, Solveig Jore, Charlotte Cook, Rob Dewar, Carmen Marco Castillo, Elina Lahti, Karin Nyberg Malin Jonsson, Cecilia Wolff, Ed van Klink, Geraldine Boseret, Renata Karpiskova, Gaia Scavia, Rosangela Tozzoli, Tineke Kramer, Mathilde Uiterwijk, Frits Vlaanderen, Kitty Maassen on behalf of the WP2.1 team of COHESIVE. OHEJP ASM, 09-06-2021, Copenhagen, Denmark. [OHEJP2021_Abstractbook.pdf \(onehealthhejp.eu\)](#)

A user-friendly decision support tool to assist one-health risk assessors. Rob Dewar, Christine Gavin, Catherine McCarthy, Rachel A. Taylor, Charlotte Cook, Robin R.L. Simons. OHEJP ASM, 09-06-2021, Copenhagen, Denmark. [OHEJP2021_Abstractbook.pdf \(onehealthhejp.eu\)](#)

FoodChain-Lab Web: An integrative modular software to visualise and analyse complex global food supply chain networks during foodborne incidents. Gottschald M, Lewicki B, Falenski A, Rügen M, Gerber I, Fusiak J, Tölle D, Käsbohrer A, Weiser A. OHEJP ASM, 09-06-2021, Copenhagen, Denmark. [OHEJP2021_Abstractbook.pdf \(onehealthhejp.eu\)](#)

Cohesive: Organizing Risk Analysis for (re-) Emerging Zoonoses: A One Health Approach. Sandra Cavaco Gonçalves, Zuzana Nordeng, Solveig Jore, Charlotte Cook, Rob Dewar, Carmen Marco Castillo, Elina Lahti, Karin Nyberg Malin Jonsson, Cecilia Wolff, Ed van Klink, Geraldine Boseret, Renata Karpiskova, Gaia Scavia, Rosangela Tozzoli, Tineke Kramer, Mathilde Uiterwijk, Frits Vlaanderen, Kitty Maassen on behalf of the WP2.1 team of COHESIVE. IAFP 27-04-2021, virtual. [\(Program and abstract\)](#)

One Health: setting up a risk analysis system for zoonoses (OHRAS). Sandra Cavaco Gonçalves, Zuzana Nordeng, Solveig Jore, Charlotte Cook, Rob Dewar, Carmen Marco Castillo, Elina Lahti, Karin Nyberg, Malin Jonsson, Cecilia Wolff, Ed van Klink, Geraldine Boseret, Renata Karpiskova, Gaia Scavia, Rosangela Tozzoli, Tineke Kramer, Mathilde Uiterwijk, Frits Vlaanderen, Kitty Maassen. One Health in the 21st Century 2021 Conference on International One Health Day, 03-11-2021, Oslo, Norway. [\(Recording presentation\)](#)

Poster presentations:

New Browser-based Tool for Quantitative Risk Assessment. Christin Wallstab, Christine Müller-Graf, Thomas Selhorst, Matthias Greiner. *DACH Epidemiologietagung 2021, 1. – 3. September 2021, Bern, Switzerland.* [\(Poster\)](#)

Deciding on a Method: A Decision Support Tool for OneHealth Risk Assessment. Rob Dewar. *HAIRS One Health Workshop, 7-11-2019, Birmingham Repertory Theatre, Birmingham*

COHESIVE: Understanding the needs for European implementation guidelines for a One Health Risk Analysis System for zoonoses. [Ines Mogami-Asselin](#), Caroline Ribeiro, Malin Jonsson, Frank Koenen, Ewa Pacholewicz, Bart Regeer, Hendrik-Jan Roest, Simon Rüegg, Mathilde Uiterwijk, Frits Vlaanderen, Cecilia Wolff, Kitty Maassen. *OHEJP ASM, 27/29-05-2020, virtual.* <https://onehealthhejp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/D3.12-OHEJP-ASM-2020-Abstract-book.pdf>

To share or not to share - the exchange of signals of zoonotic events within and between countries in Europe. [Maria Nöremark](#), Sandra Cavaco Gonçalves, Charlotte Cook, Michele Luca D'Errico, Rob Dewar, Gry Marysol Grøneng, Malin E Jonsson, Trude Marie Lyngstad, Ines Mogami Asselin, Karin

Nyberg, Ewa Pacholewicz, Gaia Scavia, Barbara Schimmer, Cecilia Wolff, Elina Lahti. *OHEJP ASM, 27/29-05-2020, virtual.* <https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/D3.12-OHEJP-ASM-2020-Abstract-book.pdf>

Horizon scanning pilot exercise regarding One Health. Rickard Knutsson, Elina Lahti, Renata Karpiskova, Ivana Kolackova, Ludovico Pasquale Sepe, Rosangela Tozzoli. *OHEJP ASM, 27/29-05-2020, virtual.* <https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/D3.12-OHEJP-ASM-2020-Abstract-book.pdf>

CgDIST a new methodology to inferring phylogeny. Adriano Di Pasquale, Iolanda Mangone, Antonio Rinaldi. *OHEJP ASM, 27/29-05-2020, virtual.* <https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/D3.12-OHEJP-ASM-2020-Abstract-book.pdf>

The FoodChain-Lab Web application – an integrative tracing tool to analyse complex global food supply chains in foodborne crises. Marion Gottschald, Birgit Lewicki, Alexander Falenski, Marco Rügen, Isaak Gerber, Dominic Tölle, Annemarie Käsbohrer, Armin Weiser. *OHEJP ASM, 27/29-05-2020, virtual.* <https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/D3.12-OHEJP-ASM-2020-Abstract-book.pdf>

European guidelines for a One Health Risk Analysis System for zoonotic diseases: a needs assessment using implementation theory. Mogami Asselin Gonzalez Ines Kuniko; dos Santos Ribeiro, Carolina; Jonsson, Malin; Koenen, Frank; Pacholewicz, Ewa; Regeer, Barbara J.; Roest, Hendrik-Jan; Rüegg, Simon R.; Uiterwijk, Mathilde; Vlaanderen, Frits; Wolff, Cecilia; Maassen, Catharina B.M.; On behalf of WP2 COHESIVE, Part of One Health EJP. *World One Health Conference, 01-11-2020, Edinbrough, Scotland*

Building political will for One Health Risk Analysis System. GIK Mogami-Asselin, Claire Hilgenga, Ludovico Sepe, Zuzana Nordeng, Kaylee Myhre Errecaborde, Frits Vlaanderen, Mathilde Uiterwijk, Kitty Maassen. *OHEJP ASM, 09/11-06-2021, Copenhagen, Denmark.* [OHEJP2021 Abstractbook.pdf \(onehealthjep.eu\)](#)

The FoodChain-Lab web application as integrative tool to trace food along complex global food supply chains in foodborne crises. Gottschald M, Lewicki B, Falenski A, Rügen M, Gerber I, Fusiak J, Tölle D, Käsbohrer A, Weiser A (2021). Abstract accessible [OHEJP2021 Abstractbook.pdf \(onehealthjep.eu\)](#). Poster accessible via <https://epostersonline.com/ohejp2021/node/487?view=true>

Building political will for One Health Risk Analysis System. GIK Mogami-Asselin, Claire Hilgenga, Ludovico Sepe, Zuzana Nordeng, Kaylee Myhre Errecaborde, Frits Vlaanderen, Mathilde Uiterwijk, Kitty Maassen. *One Health in the 21st Century 2021 Conference on International One Health Day, 03-11-2021, Oslo, Norway.* [\(Poster\)](#)

Involvement in courses, workshops and webinars

Setting up a OH risk analysis system. Kitty Maassen. Involvement in organisation, presentations and guidance of One Health EJP CPD module “Outbreak Preparedness”, 16/17-11-2020. [CPD 2020 - One Health EJP](#)

FoodChain-Lab Web: An integrative modular software to visualise and analyse complex global food supply chain networks during foodborne incidents. Gottschald M, Lewicki B, Falenski A, Rügen M,

Gerber I, Fusiak J, Tölle D, Käsbohrer A, Weiser A. Presentation and interactive live demo in the framework of the One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting Satellite Workshop “Online Software Fair”. [Abstract-Book-ASM-Satellite-Workshop2021.pdf \(onehealthjep.eu\)](#). doi: 10.3897/aca.4.e68835

FoodChain-Lab: an innovative tool to increase food safety through supply chain analyses. Gottschald M, Lewicki B, Falenski A, Rügen M, Gerber I, Fusiak J, Tölle D, Käsbohrer A, Weiser A (2021). Interactive virtual event (presentations, interactive live demo, interactive traceability exercise) and e-learning course (developed in a project with EFSA) on FCL Web at the One Health EJP CPD module “Digital Innovation for One Health Practitioners”, 15/19-02-2021 (<https://onehealthjep.eu/cpd-2021/>).

Shiny risk. Thomas Selhorst. Oral presentation at the One Health EJP CPD module “Digital Innovation for One Health Practitioners”, 15/19-02-2021 (<https://onehealthjep.eu/cpd-2021/>).

FoodChain-Lab: an innovative tool to increase food safety through supply chain analyses. Gottschald M, Lewicki B, Falenski A, Rügen M, Gerber I, Fusiak J, Tölle D, Käsbohrer A, Weiser A (2021). Interactive virtual event (presentations, interactive live demo, interactive traceability exercise) on FCL Web at the Online Advanced Course on “Innovative tools and methods for ensuring seafood authenticity”, 26-04/6-05-2021 (<https://edu.iamz.ciheam.org/SeafoodAuthenticity/en/>).

Refinement of the COHESIVE Information System towards a unified ontology of food terms for the public health organizations. Iolanda Mangone, Nicolas Radomski, Adriano Di Pasquale, Andrea Santurbano, Paolo Calistri, Cesare Cammà, Kitty Maassen. Oral presentation at IFOW 2021 Integrated Food Ontology Workshop, 15/18-09-2021, Bolzano, Italy. ([Conference proceedings](#))

One Health EJP workshop : Integrated approaches to zoonoses. Simon Ruegg and Kitty Maassen. Interactive virtual workshop using systems thinking. ([Integrated Approaches to Zoonoses](#))

Outcomes

At the beginning of the project a [factsheet](#) was made for the COHESIVE project. This still can be used to promote the mission of COHESIVE and create awareness for the developed tools.

In WP2.1 web-based guidelines are drafted to support countries in setting up/strengthening the One Health risk analysis of zoonoses. It is important to promote the existence of the guidelines and why it is important to have a One Health collaboration on risk analysis of zoonoses. Therefore, 3 infographics were made that can be used to promote the guidelines and create awareness. The infographics are made available via <https://onehealthjep.eu/outcome-inventory> and are free to be used by everyone. It can be useful for both national and international stakeholders, policy makers and professionals in risk analysis of (emerging) zoonoses & AMR.

In WP2.2 an online decision support tool to help users decide on the most appropriate method to use when tasked with conducting a risk assessment for a specific situation was developed and is available via <http://cohesive.onehealthjep.eu/>. The decision support tool also became part of the Surveillance & Information Sharing Operational Tool (SISOT) initiated by OIE, WHO and FAO in 2020.

FoodChain-Lab Web (FCL Web, <https://fcl-portal.bfr.berlin/>) as a joint outcome of OHEJP COHESIVE WP4.2 and the EFSA-BfR Framework Partnership Agreement is already in use by several Member States, EFSA and U.S. FDA. In the future, it will be interlinked with several tracing tools for various tracing purposes on the local, national and European level. It will be closely connected to future EFSA Rapid Outbreak Assessment production procedures. FCL Web also became part of the Surveillance & Information Sharing Operational Tool (SISOT) initiated by OIE, WHO and FAO in 2020.

Shiny rrsik has been included in the curriculum of the EU-FORA training programme and is a regular part of lectures at the Faculty of Agriculture of the University of Bonn, and in other training programmes on quantitative risk assessment (TiHo Hannover).

Summary of tools developed within COHESIVE:

- Web based guidelines 'One Health: Setting up a risk analysis system for zoonoses' (www.ohras.eu, www.onehealthguidelines.eu)
- Online Risk Assessment Decision Support tool (cohesive.onehealthejp.eu)
- FoodChain-Lab Web(<https://fcl-portal.bfr.berlin/>)
- COHESIVE Information System (CIS) (<https://cohesive.izs.it>)
- Shiny rrsik (<https://github.com/RobertOpitz/shinyRisk>)
- OHEJP Glossary and Glossaryfication Web Service (<https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/ohejp-glossary/>) (together with OHEJP projects ORION and NOVA)

The integrative tracing tool FoodChain-Lab Web (WP4.2) is already in use by several Member States, EFSA and U.S. FDA and it is involved in projects with EFSA that are in part build on the achievements in COHESIVE. In 2020, FoodChain-Lab Web became part of the SISOT tool box of OIE, WHO and FAO. Also the shiny Risk tool is already in use at Bfr and the COHESIVE Information System (CIS) is in practice in Italy.

4.6. One Health Impact

- The development of several tools that significantly will facilitate and improve cross-sectorial risk analysis, leading to more efficient and precise risk analyses. This way disease events hopefully can be prevented resulting in less disease burden in animals and humans as well as financial benefits for all involved sectors.
- In the many dissemination activities, next to the specific topic of the activity, the importance of the development of sustainable One Health approaches in risk analysis of zoonoses was told and promoted.
- The 'Guidelines for risk analysis of zoonoses' is promoted on many occasions. To successfully set up a OHRAS, support of ministries, authorities, public health/veterinary institutes is crucial. Therefore, using the OHEJP consortium to spread the basic message to is of major importance, from researchers, institute directors to ministries (product owners). This was done (I.e., ASM, PMT and POC meetings, COHESIVE consortium meetings, new OHEJP countries) and will be continued, both inside and outside of the OHEJP consortium.
- FAO/WHO/OIE have developed the Tripartite Zoonoses Guide and are developing additional operational tools among which the SISOT tool. This tool provides countries with the opportunity to assess their countries capacity in OH surveillance in depth and supply them with tools to increase this capacity. Several of our tools will be taken up in this toolbox, 'risk

assessment decision making tool', 'COHESIVE information system', FoodChain-Lab tool, Guidelines for risk analysis of zoonoses'.

- The above-mentioned SISOT tool is tested in several pilots, one on each continent. COHESIVE is involved in the European pilot in Romania. This is a possibility to disseminate products of COHESIVE but also other OHEJP projects and will give insight how best to relate to the Tripartite tool.
- In Norway, the systems mapping workshop took place in September 2021, as part of the roadmap/steppingstones of the guidelines in WP2.1. This brought together people from the public health, veterinary and food safety sector from central and local organisations. One of the outcomes was stating the importance of informal networks (which was strengthened by the meeting itself). There was a clear wish for a continued conversation around the OH system for zoonoses in Norway, and to include more stakeholders.
- In Portugal, the systems mapping workshop took place in November 2021. This brought together people from the public health and veterinary sector from central, regional and local organisations. All participants agreed on the importance of this meetings gathering people from different sectors to generate cross-sectoral perspectives, and to develop friendly and informal relationships. The systems-mapping and discussions on the One Health existing infrastructures and operations are very useful, allowing the identification of gaps, as well as strong points. Main conclusions included the need to establish a national community of practice in One Health, the reinforcement of communication and data sharing among sectors, and the reinforcement of One Health culture and awareness. This enthusiastic group will continue to meet.
- For Belgium, a focus was AMR and a National Action Plan was developed. In that line Belgium wanted to be one of the pilot countries for the 'Guidelines' of WP2.1. The first steps were made, but due to COVID the next step is postponed to 2022. There is a lot of interest in this workshop on systems mapping as many accepted the invitation to the workshop which was originally planned in March 2020. As for Portugal and Norway, getting support, building on relation, and gaining trust are major goals of such a physical workshop.
- The OHEJP project MATRIX is very much interested in the developed guidelines in WP2.1 and will continue to improve them. In addition, they will also follow the roadmap / steppingstones. This will be done in Sweden and Denmark. The process including the systems mapping workshops is currently planned.
- EFSA has asked MVNA to assist in 70organizing a One Health module for IPA (Instrument for Pre-Assessing Assistance) formation beneficiary countries. COHESIVE most likely will be involved in 70organizing a workshop based upon the guidelines of WP2.1. COHESIVE already has been presented to EU pre-assessing countries.
- The decision-support tool has gained coverage both within the Animal and Plant Health Agency, and on OHEJP social media. Categorising the range of approaches available and compiling risk assessment resources will help make these resources easily accessible to those new to the field of One Health risk assessments. Navigating the decision-tree will help them understand which approach to use depending on their situation. It should broaden the understanding of risk assessment across One Health.
- In WP3.1 it became clear that awareness of hinders as well as factors facilitating sharing of early signals of zoonotic events within and between sectors are points of departure for improvements. Collecting experience in a structured way provides a basis showing that many

of the findings are general and can be addressed, e.g., through arranging regular meetings between sectors. For instance, in some countries, like in Italy, the study led to building new contacts and raising awareness.

- The task leader of 3.2 participated as an invited expert in a foresight exercise organised by WHO in June-July 2020. In the exercise organised by WHO current and future risks of life sciences were assessed. The tools applied at the COHESIVE exercises were used at the WHO exercise, as well and demonstrated the interest in various organisation to apply HS as a foresight tool.
- Systems mapping of public information systems helps identify how data is collected, used and communicated to the public in the case of non-reportable diseases. This is useful when trying to understand systems outside of your country or sector. Mapping the process for Q-fever surveillance from detection of clinical signs to reporting of a case and subsequent involvement of One Health partners highlighted weaknesses in the reporting structure. This exercise helped strengthen the case for more in-depth surveillance of Q-fever in the livestock sector in the UK to protect food safety and public health.
- A ‘European One Health platform for low-threshold sharing of zoonotic signals’ has been established. This is an informal platform for easy sharing of information cross countries to improve the shared understanding of zoonotic trends and events that do not have to be notified (yet) at EU level as well as related response/policy issues. In addition, ways of working are shared, to avoid having to re-invent the wheel and improve approaches. *Brucella canis* was a topic in the first meeting and it turned out that many countries struggled with similar (regulatory) issues. The workshop that was organised as a spin off attracted over 170 people without the workshop being promotion, indicating the clear need for this kind of interaction. The workshop has raised awareness among small animal veterinary practitioners and physicians in the UK and Sweden, at least. A white paper is in preparation together with IDEMBRU, COHESIVE, and other collaborators (such as Bristol University, University of Nantes).
- The OHEJP Glossary has been integrated into the OHEJP Data Management Software, is used by the BfR to improve their own internal glossary and by Sciensano to establish a national OH glossary. <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/ohejp-glossary/>
- After the presentation of the CIS at the final meeting of COHESIVE, a number of organisations asked to have a separate and deeper presentation of the system. Some see clear possibilities for use of the system. Among others, we mention:
 - RIVM,
 - INSA
 - OHEJP BeONE,
 - OHEJP MATRIX.
- The organisation committee of SIMex, a large OHEJP simulation exercise, has shown interest in CIS and FCL as a tool for participating countries to use during the exercise. This would mean that a large number of institutes will get a chance to get acquainted with the system and its possibilities for use. This is currently being explored.
- The SIMex organisation committee has shown interest in the results of WP3.1 and is exploring the possibility to use them in the exercise.
- A specialised version of the CIS is at the basis of the informatic platform of the Italian National Reference Centre of WGS of pathogen (GENPAT).

- CIS is at the basis of Italian pilot on integration and harmonisation of *Listeria monocytogenes* data between public health and veterinarian organisations.
- There was a large interest for the online systems mapping workshop. Over 140 people applied, also from outside the OHEJP consortium and outside Europe. By performing two (or more) additional workshops more potential 'change agents' can be reached and directed to the guidelines. From the given feedback, people became enthusiastic about systems thinking and said that they would apply it more often.
- The systematic review of economic analysis papers will deconvolute a highly complex and diverse field. It is hoped that by showcasing the different available approaches, and their characteristics, new analysts in the One-Health field, can take a more informed decision on the approach to apply. This may also help standardise the approaches and terminology used in this field.
- The FoodChain-Lab Web tracing portal (FCL Web, WP4.2) combines the effort of several projects on national and European level by integrating their outcomes in FCL Web. The portal also integrates data from food safety and public health and thereby promotes the One Health approach. FCL Web is used in outbreak investigations by Member States, EFSA and U.S. FDA. In the future, FCL Web will be interlinked with other tracing tools on the local, national and European level which serve various tracing purposes. It will be closely connected to future EFSA Rapid Outbreak Assessment production procedures. FCL Web also became part of the Surveillance & Information Sharing Operational Tool (SISOT) initiated by OIE, WHO and FAO in 2020.
- Shiny rrisk is an R application that provides a web application to perform quantitative probabilistic risk assessments. Shiny rrisk is both open source and public domain. Shiny rrisk facilitates setting up a risk model, enables 1- and 2-dimensional, Monte-Carlo Simulation, Data Fitting, model Visualization, and provides a schema for The Assessment of Uncertainties (according to the EFSA Guidance). There is a collaboration with RIVM for the future development of the programme, for testing the applicability and further ideas on risk assessment methodology. Contacts with APHA (Robin Simons) will be continued. The exchange with EFSA (Olaf Moosbach-Schulz, Jose Cortina-Abrahantes) and openanalytis (Tobias Verbeke) started at the beginning of the research project will be continued.
- FAO, OIE and WHO launched the Joint Risk Assessment Operational Tool (JRA OT), introducing the 10 steps of the joint risk assessment (JRA) process divide into 4 modules. This allows different participants to be included in various modules of the JRA (<https://www.who.int/initiatives/tripartite-zoonosis-guide/joint-risk-assessment-operational-tool>), Shiny Rrisk features could benefit the JRA OT module 3. It is stated, that the success of a joint risk assessment (JRA) depends on effective communication among the sectors throughout the process, ideally leading to a consensus on the outcome of the assessment and production of a joint or aligned assessment document (JRAOT, page 3). Because shiny Rrisk has a special focus on documentation it could make a special contribution here. The Tripartite will be contacted to explore the possibilities.
- Shiny Rrisk has been included in the curriculum of the EU-FORA training programme and is a regular part of lectures at the Faculty of Agriculture of the University of Bonn, and in other training programmes on quantitative risk assessment (TiHo Hannover).
- Several publications are in preparation, for instance on the guidelines, on the pilots in Norway and Portugal, and on the signalling pathways

4.7. Data Management Plan

The final version of the DMP has been submitted to the OHEJP leader on time and is currently (12/2021) under review. This version is uploaded at the OHEJP website. All documentation has been uploaded to Zenodo and links are given in this document. Some tools are made available on github. Links are given in this document. All documentation has been uploaded to Zenodo and links are given in this document. Some tools are made available on github. Links are given in this document.

5. JIP3 - CARE

5.1. Summary of the work carried out

In the reporting period of year 4 (9M), CARE updated and adjusted the activities to meet the deliverables and milestones. In realization of the delays, CARE submitted the request for a half year with no cost extension which was granted. In 2021, three new partners joined the CARE consortium. The partners were: ISCIII in Spain (Silvia Herrera Leon), BIOR in Latvia (Gunita Dekšne), and RUOKA in Finland (Saija Hallanvuo).

The quarterly meeting with all partners now also include participation by representatives of EJP MATRIX and EJP OH-HARMONY-CAP. The two lead organizations have participated in integrative activities organized by the OHEJP WP4, thereby promoting and disseminating information about the OHEJP and related activities.

The work in WP1 has been focusing on the first cross sectorial culture-based pilot EQA, W1-T2-ST1, which has successfully been executed. The EQA materials were dispatched from Sweden the 12th of April 2021. The results are currently being assessed and drafting of a report is in process. The second pilot EQA, W1-T2-ST2, on typing/characterization based on WGS has been re-scheduled. The deadline for submitting the results has been postponed due to a hacker attack at DTU. The third EQA on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data, W1-T2-ST3, has also been re-scheduled.

The inventory of available reference material has been finalized based on the need assessment document ([D.2.3](#)) including more than 2500 reference material strains. Currently, WP2/ WP3 focuses on the extended analysis of the identified genomes for AMR, virulence and other typing regimes and the isolates for identification by MALDI-TOF. Institute Pasteur has for half of the genomes already links is in process to stored also in the public repository.

Currently, the inventory of identified reference materials is being converted into a database for which a web interphase is being developed to ensure easy accessibility and visibility of the reference material.

More than 50 individuals from various institutions provided feedback to the risk assessment survey on relevant (meta-)data in relation to quantitative microbial risk assessments conducted by WP4. Thus, feeding into the quantitative microbial risk assessment analysis on data originating from the last five years and provided by 19 OHEJP members or stakeholders including those from ORION and RADAR (D.4.1.2) (no link). The identified (meta-)data in relation to quantitative microbial risk assessments was shared with WP2 and WP3 and stakeholders to assist by increasing the accessibility of data but also to

avoid duplication (D.4.1.3) (no link). Currently, efforts are made towards developing a User guide for accessing relevant data for risk assessment (D.4.2.1) (scheduled for M54 (June 2022)) and R software suite package “rStain Select” to ease the process of selecting suitable reference strains based on exposure and risks. Thus, the User guide and R software will contribute to and support the developed strategy by EU authorities to raise the awareness of relevant reference material microbial risk assessment analysis (D.4.2.2) (scheduled for M54 (June 2022)). The latter issue of what kind of data that is necessary for risk assessment has been discussed with EFSA and will be taken into consideration. In summary, the CARE project progresses more or less as planned reaching milestones and deliverables in time and addresses additional assignments from the OHEJP WP4 in a timely manner.

5.2. Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

5.2.1. WP0 Coordination

WP0-T1 Over-all project coordination

DTU and SSI constitute the management team and have established a comprehensive management system to ensure that all deliverables and milestones for the vast majority are reached in the timeframe envisioned for the project and submitted using the designated OHEJP format. DTU is hosting the secretariat, which is essential for a successful completion of the proposed work programme. Furthermore, DTU has set up and is hosting a CARE share-site for storage of all reports, deliverables, milestones, minutes, and other documentation produced as part of CARE.

In February, ANSES, DTU and SSI organized the CARE interim meeting (M.0.2). The meeting was held as a virtual meeting due to Covid-19 and this was facilitated by DTU. The interim meeting allowed all partners to be updated from the CARE management team, WP-lead and on the DMP plan. External stakeholders were invited, there were presentations of OHEJP integrative projects and the OHEJP management team gave an overview of OHEJP projects and presented links between them. There was allocated time for break-out sessions where the content, progress and adjustment to the work plans were discussed. The minutes of the kick-off meeting were reported and shared in the share site ([D.0.5](#)). CARE status meetings for the management team (DTU and SSI) have been conducted every second week. Furthermore, DTU and SSI organized and conducted work package (WP) lead virtual meetings every 14 days to inform, discuss and delegate news and tasks from the OHEJP management as part of Task: JIP IA 2.1-WP0-T1. In addition, WP-leads reported on the work undertaken in each WP as to progress, deliverables, delays etc. Minutes of all meetings have been reported and shared on the CARE share site. In continuation of the progress management, bi-monthly reports (internal progress reporting templates) have been terminated due to reporting fatigue by the WP-leads. The management team has accepted this and delegated the responsibility to monitor progress within each WP to the leads. The management team has enforced the WP-leads to provide high quality work and a review system has been implemented for this purpose, where WP1 review the work of WP3 and WP2 the work of WP4 and vice versa.

The management team has organized and conducted joint partner virtual meetings every quarter, primarily to allow the 16 partners to provide feedback to progress and accomplishments. The meetings also allowed for dissemination of information not shared already by email. Minutes of these meeting are shared and saved on the share site.

A strong collaboration has been built with the management teams of JIPs, MATRIX and OH-HARMONY-CAP. The three projects are participating in annual/interim meeting sharing knowledge and progress on the projects. CARE had presentations on both the OH-HARMONY-CAP meeting in Dublin (November 10th-12th) and the MATRIX online meeting November 22nd (talks will be stored on the share site). Planning of the collaborative final meeting has been taking place and will be at SSI in week 38, 2022 and will include all involved partners from MATRIX, OH-HARMONY-CAP and CARE.

A joint venture application has been made for hosting the third One Health CPD–module with the theme, Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests in the fall of 2022. Furthermore OH-HARMONY-CAP, CARE and MATRIX are preparing a thematic call for original publications, whether research, perspectives, or policy, in the domain of integrated One Health surveillance. This call will be launched in the Journal Frontiers in Public Health and we expect the call to open early in 2022. We hope that this call might collect some of the intermediate achievements of the OHEJP JIPs OH-HARMONY-CAP, CARE and MATRIX with a special focus on the integrative aspects of the projects' methods and strategies.

5.2.2. WP1 Develop of cross-sectional PT's (proficiency testing)

The overall aim of WP1 is to develop EQA/ PT schemes that can be used to assess the combined performance of the OH sector, i.e., the human, food/feed, and veterinary sectors. The WP is divided into three tasks, a mapping exercise, which is finalized (WP1-T1 Mapping of existing and proposals for new PT schemes), a part where three pilot PTs are organized and documented (WP1-T2 Pilot trials and documentation of outcome), and a third part, WP1-T3 Development of guidance document with suggestions for design of future cross-sectorial PT schemes. This part of the WP has not started yet. The work conducted in Y4 has been focusing on the planning and execution of pilot PTs:

- WP1-T2-ST1 Pilot PT on isolation/detection and characterization of pathogens
- WP1-T2-ST2 Pilot PT on typing/characterization including WGS
- WP1-T2-ST3 Pilot PT on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data

WP1-T2-ST1 Pilot PT on isolation/detection and characterization of pathogens

The aim of this pilot PT is to increase the understanding of the cross-sectorial capabilities to detect and characterize food-borne pathogens in a matrix relevant to the sectors of food safety, veterinary medicine, and public health. The PT has been organized by SVA, FOHM and SLV in Sweden. is currently being executed. The EQA materials were dispatched from Sweden in April 2021. The 15 participating laboratories (12 OHEJP partners and 3 clinical microbiological laboratories from one country) received five vials each containing a sample mimicking an environmental sample from an abattoir, a stool sample, or a composite environmental sample from wild boars. In addition, another five vials containing freeze-dried bacteria of one to three of the target organisms, *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* and *Yersinia* were supplied. The laboratories prepared the samples by mixing the vials with the pathogens and the matrices and analysed the samples. The laboratories were requested to detect and characterize the target pathogens to species level (*Campylobacter*), to serovar level (*Salmonella*) and to species and biotype level (*Yersinia*) according to the methods routinely used by each laboratory. The participants were requested to report their results via a web-based questionnaire at the latest on the 31st of May 2021. In addition to questions on the results of the pilot PT/EQA, the web-based

questionnaire included questions on the laboratory methods applied, on notification practices as well as the type of samples the laboratories usually receive. The deadline for submitting results was May 31. The PT participants were primarily CARE partners supplemented with a few Swedish laboratories, and both the food and veterinary side and the public health side were well represented. A report of the PT/EQA is in progress. The participants of the PT/EQA received a draft report of the PT/EQA on December 22, 2021. A new deadline for the deliverable is M 53. The analyses of the data are currently being done, and feedback to the individual participants will be sent before the end of December Y4. In accordance with the time plan a report/draft publication of the exercise will be finalized in Y5.

WP1-T2-ST2 Pilot PT on typing/characterization including WGS

The second PT in WP1 aims at assessing the quality and comparability of WGS based on a set of WGS quality metrics and looks into the laboratories ability to detect and assign subtypes/attributes from WGS data from bacterial isolates e.g., sero- and sequence types, antimicrobial resistance genes, toxin subtypes etc. The aim is to assess both the individual and the collective performance of the partner participating laboratories.

In Y4, work has been done on developing and documenting the reference material that are used in the PT, i.e., pure strains and FASTQ sequence files from *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* and *Escherichia coli*. An invitation to participate in the PT was sent to the CARE laboratories in September, and instructions and material for the PT was dispatched from DTU, Lyngby, Denmark, in October Y4. The participants have received six live stains, two strains of *E. coli*, two strains of *Salmonella*, and two strains of *Campylobacter*, and six pre-prepared DNA samples corresponding the live cultures. The participants are requested to perform WGS on DNA purified from the live cultures and the pre-purified samples and upload the reads in FASTQ format to a FTP site. The participants are also requested to upload specific details in relation to the test material and details in relation to their sequencing and analytical methods. It is mandatory to identify the overall Multi Locus Sequence Type (MLST) lineage of the cultures and it is also mandatory to identify antimicrobial resistance genes, including genes associated with resistance towards extended spectrum beta-lactam antimicrobials, and point mutations that are conferring antimicrobial resistance. The deadline for submission of results is 21. December 2021. The submitted reads and corresponding results will be evaluated and individual feedback will be provided to each of the participants according to the time plan of WP1.

Partners that provide EQA services will also be granted access to the informatic IT module developed by DTU for the Fleming Fund project "EQASIA" (<https://antimicrobialresistance.dk/eqasia.aspx>) that can be used to evaluate and compare assigned WGS quality metrics and typing characteristics, including nomenclature on different species. This will enable EQA providers to evaluate and compare the performance of their own work streams, pipelines, and nomenclature with other partners working within the field of organizing genomic PTs.

WP1-T2-ST3 Pilot PT on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data

The aim of this pilot is to develop proficiency testing schemes for the analysis of whole genome sequence (WGS) data to detect clusters as might be required during an outbreak response.

The pilot distribution consists of WGS data files, in FASTQ format, from approximately 80 different isolates that include outbreak and background strains of *Salmonella*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, and *Campylobacter*.

A FTP site has been established at SSI for file sharing and work have been conducted to develop a reporting format using the platform hosted by APHA. The participants will be requested to upload data on quality control, (did the sequence pass the QC control pipeline?) and to identify those strains that clusters together and can be regarded as part of an outbreak. For all three species it will be mandatory to report the overall sequence type (MLST) and for Salmonella and Campylobacter the laboratories additionally are asked to report the serotype and species, respectively. The participants are supposed to analyse the sequence data using their routine operational pipelines. The reporting also includes information on the methodology used in the laboratories.

An appropriate number of CARE partner laboratories have been recruited to the PT. Some of these will participate in the outbreak cluster analysis for a single, two, or all three species depending upon their laboratory specialism. The outbreak PT exercise was launched on December 15, 2021, where all participants received instructions and could download the sequences to be analyzed. The deadline for submission of results on the developed platform is January 31, 2022. Feedback to the individual participants will be provided shortly thereafter. The report of the whole typing PT exercise will be provided according to the time plan of WP1.

5.2.3. WP2 Creation of EUROpanelOH, a reference database of strains and genomes for effective quality control analysis in food safety and public health protection across sectors

WP2-T1 Inventory of current use and existence of reference materials across CARE / OHEJP partner institutes, for selected, prioritized pathogens and antimicrobial resistances

The first time period has consisted of collecting a minimum set of descriptive standard information to be associated with individual biological resources among CARE partners. During the kick-off meeting, the bacterial pathogens to focus on in CARE was discussed to ensure feasibility. It was agreed to focus on foodborne bacterial pathogens to align with the scope of the partners official reference laboratory designations, thus, a list of priority pathogens was created. These attributes include qualitative characteristics and physical location of the biological resources as well as contact information of the supplier. An inquiry was made for feedback on the attributes selected by the task leaders. Some additional attributes have been suggested and included in the final excel template of the inventory of resources. Some attributes were considered mandatory information to consider the inclusion of the bacterial strains in the final database, such as the sector of isolation (human, animal, food, feed, and environment), year and country of isolation, while some were instead considered as informative. The template was sent to CARE partners on April, 2020. The duly filled templates were received again in Summer 2020 and analyzed.

A total of 12 partner institutes contributed to the inventory of putative reference materials. Most of them registered more than single pathogens, at least 2 to 3 different pathogens (IP, DTU, SVA, PIWET, IZSAM, IZSLER) to more than 4 to 8 different pathogens (ANSES, UCN, ISS). Finally, 2960 strains have been considered as candidates for inclusion (D.2.1). Some reference materials were provided from OHEJP JRP projects, especially in the frame of Listadapt (for *Listeria monocytogenes*) and Tox detect (for *Bacillus cereus* and *Staphylococcus aureus*).

The database of resources (D.2.1) was analyzed for the content of information given by the partners. There were only eight strains from which no metadata were available due to

confidentiality agreement. Such strains could be used as EQAS materials for dedicated purposes. The compliance with Nagoya protocol regulations has been fully addressed during the inventory timeframe. Countries of origin were unknown or not mentioned for 91 strains. That corresponds to less than 0.03% of the total number of inventoried strains. If the unknown geographical origin of some genetic resources may hamper the future distribution of the strains, it cannot prohibit the handling of the stateless material by CARE partners. Of course, the use and full characterization of such resources will not be favoured in the next phases. It is worth noting that access to the Spanish and French resources will necessitate authorizations from the two National Focal point services.

WGS data were already available for some strains and species. This was not enough, however, to create the sub-database for antimicrobial resistances as initially planned. Indeed, WGS data were available for 66% of *Listeria* strains, 43% of *Campylobacter* strains, 83% of *Bacillus* strains, 25% of *Salmonella* strains, 24% of *E. coli* strains and 15% of *Yersinia* strains. Only four strains were fully WGS characterized for *Staphylococcus* and none for *Vibrio* and *Streptococcus*. The AMR sub-database (D.2.2) (Deliverable is pending) was therefore postponed to December 2021. DTU has worked in 2021 on updating ResFinder to enable and address the need for having a single standardized database that contains all validated AMR genes classified by mechanisms. At the end of 2021, there are 547 strains of the seven pathogens for which we have genome sequences deposited in NCBI or EBI public databases. These genome sequences will be analyzed in the first semester of 2022 to set up the AMR database in relation to the 540 strains integrated in the CARE collection.

WP2-T2 Gap analysis with respect to accessibility, quality and usefulness of existing and potential new reference materials from a One-Health perspective

The task 2 began by sending a letter to all CARE partners for calling experts of the target species in order to select the reference materials in the database of resources. CARE partners reacted swiftly enabling the completion of the need assessment document (D.2.3) intended for conducting the gap analysis. An updated list of strains with information of relevant gap of information identified was circulated to reference contacts for each partner institute, to inform about the strains suggested by the experts for inclusion in the final database and the characterization steps to be performed to fill relevant gaps. It is indeed one of the major purposes of CARE to establish a trustable link between the phenotypes and the genotypes of the strains at the final round of integration in EUROpanelOH.

WP2-T3 Production of additional RM to fill in gaps and/or improve characterization if needed

The updated lists of strains selected for the final database sent to each partner institute contained information on the identified gaps in the characterization that should be filled within the project. Additional analyses could thus be performed at each institute to refine the strains' characterization. Revision of provided data for reference strains, at least for the first round of strain integration, was achieved in the second semester of 2021. There are 547 strains almost completely characterized at the end of 2021.

WP2-T3-ST1 WGS characterization

Sequencing of the strains for which WGS was not available has started as planned at each partner institute in Summer 2021. The WGS files have been uploaded by each institute in international sequence repositories (EMBL ENA). A dedicated folder was also shared for easy files exchange. The sequences will be analysed automatically with CGE analytical services performing the following steps:

quality check, Kmer analysis for species identification, Multi Locus Sequence Typing, ResFinder for inferring antimicrobial resistance, PlasmidFinder for plasmid identification, Seqsero for Salmonella serotyping and SeroTypeFinder for E. coli serotyping. This activity will begin in early 2022 when the sequences will be made available.

WP2-T3-ST2 MALDI-TOF characterization

Maldi-TOF characterization of many strains selected to be part of the final database was missing. It was agreed to focus on the characterization of the strains selected for *Salmonella* (ANSES), *Yersinia* (IP), *Campylobacter* (INRAE) and *B. cereus* (PIWET).

WP2-T3-ST3 Completing metadata and phenotypic data

The updated lists of strains selected for the final database sent to each partner contained information on the required metadata and phenotypic data missing and mandatorily requested for the collection. Follow up actions are being conducted with the partners in collaboration with WP3 for transferring the complete set of information in the final information system curated by WP3.

5.2.4. WP3 Access and sustainability of well-defined microbial reference materials (RM)

WP3-T1 Development of an information system for making RM more widely accessible and visible

The past year has allowed the construction of the minimum dataset that must be associated with the living microbiological Reference Materials (RMs) of the CARE catalogue in order for them to be useful as biological standards and compliant with regulations (D.3.1.1). The work carried out between the partners has also allowed the definition of the principles for the construction of the Information System (IS) that will host the CARE's catalogue of RMs and allow their visibility and distribution (D.3.1.2). The principles governing the construction of the information system (IS) (including database and website) of the EUROpanel-OH-CARE Catalogue of MRs have been defined. Their implementation will allow the visibility and distribution of CARE's RMs. (D.3.1.2). The choice was made to build a relational database using the commercial Biologics system (Bioaware), which is the standard chosen by the pan-European MIRRI consortium and appeared to be a realistic solution for having a functional system within the CARE project timeframe.

The scheme of the CARE database was developed with minimum mandatory information needed for each species to ensure scientific interest, traceability and compliance of the strains with ABS regulation. A corresponding basic version of the CARE website was developed that enabled running basic and advanced searches to access the database information. This work was presented at the Société Française de Microbiologie (SFM) 2021 conference in France. Thereafter, the template for collecting RM data was reiterated to further refine existing data fields, as well as add new ones that improve the overall significance of RMs. RM providers were grouped together according to the species for which they would provide the RMs, and were asked to update and consolidate final RM-related information that would be integrated into the CARE database. Simultaneously, a workflow of collecting and analyzing WGS data of RMs shared by the Providers, was strategized. Moving forward, once the final RM data provided by the Providers is reviewed (for format errors, availability of complete

information, quality of AMR and WGS data), all the RM data will be integrated into the database for all the species. By the first quarter of 2022, the feasibility of a genomic data collection and processing pipeline should be established and, if human and technical resources permit, implemented within first semester 2022.

WP3-T2 Ensure the long-term sustainability of RM collections

The objectives of Task 2 to make the microbiological collections of reference material sustainable have been the subject of extensive discussions among CARE partners. Several key points were raised, notably on the important role that the three official MicroBiological Resource Centers (mBRCs INRAE-CIRM, Institut Pasteur-CRBIP and the BVR biobank of IZSLER) operated by CARE partners. It was decided that the CARE collections would be distributed among these three BRCs. Choices have been made on the physical sites for the conservation of the collections that will be concentrated on three sites hosting mBRCs: CRBIP, IP, Paris; IZSLER, Brescia; CIRM-BP, INRAE, Nouzilly. The distribution of bacterial RM strains between the mBRCs has been optimized by species to simplify sample shipment for suppliers and end users. This organization will help to achieve important aspects of sustainability like in the conservation and distribution of RMs following best practices.

WP3-T3 Ensuring the long-term accessibility of the RM collection and its existence

A number of agreements will have to be settled between partners in the months to come to ensure the long-term sustainability and accessibility of the EUROpanelOH catalogue:

- To allow the transfer of RMs as quickly as possible and the establishment of CARE collections each BRC will use its own Material Deposit Agreement (MDA).
- The CARE partners hosting mBRCs have reached an agreement on the common pricing of strains of the CARE collection. An internal debate led to a consensus that special pricing should be granted to CARE partners that will support the expansion of the collection, its updating and the work of experts beyond the CARE project. However, it seems that this decision violates the principles of equal treatment of customers and cannot be upheld. This point requires legal advice, as CARE's partners believe that a financial benefit to strain providers will provide an incentive to share new resources.
- A Financial agreement to sustain the maintenance of the EURO-panelOH collection (cost of conservation, Biolomics licences fees, data curation, update of CARE catalogue) will be discussed between partners in the coming months.

At the European level, discussions have been initiated by INRAE and IP with the MIRRI (Microbial Research Infrastructure) consortium for exposition of the CARE catalogue through the MIRRI web portal. This option should promote the OHEJP CARE project and give a good visibility to the RM catalogue.

5.2.5 WP4 Investigate, benchmark and improve the availability and the quality of the existing data relevant for risk assessment

WP4-T1 Data and metadata available for risk assessment

WP4 CARE members first established the list of targeted institutes to which the survey was addressed. This list comprised OHEJP members as well as members from EFSA Microbiological Risk Assessment

Network. A small literature review was done to establish criteria to assess the data quality and accessibility in the field of risk assessment.

A survey (D.4.1.1) intended for the OHEJP members and broader from September 2020 to March 2021 to collect information about existing QMRAs from the last 5 years. The questionnaire (DMP ID: JIP-3-WP4-1) was set up on Sphinx online software and was organized into 31 main questions divided into 3 sections.

(https://survey.anses.fr/SurveyServer/s/formation7/questionnaire_RA/questionnaire.htm)

The survey has been fully analysed (D.4.1.3). It revealed that the main hazards assessed were pathogenic *E. coli*, *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Salmonella spp.* While the starting point of the QMRAs study is diverse, the endpoint is mostly at the consumer stage. Survey participants reported using three sources of data in the risk assessments they conducted : data produced by the risk assessor organization itself, data from literature and data from a scientific network. Part of this data is available but not recorded on a dedicated platform.

In the perspective to establish the roadmap for sharing information for pathogens and AMR useful for exposure/risk assessment, contacts were established with other initiatives. CARE's objective has been presented to the JIP ORION, JRP RADAR, Pathogens-in-foods database and RAKIP projects. Information was collected from these projects related to best practices to improve accessibility and quality assessment of data relevant for QMRA.

Meetings have been held with stakeholders (ECDC in September 2021 and in October for EFSA) to present WP4 CARE project and more particularly the results of the survey and the views shared with other projects on data sharing. It was recognized during these meetings that although there are initiatives for data sharing, there are still many challenges to overcome in order to achieve transparent and efficient data sharing in risk assessments.

WP4-T2 Metadata web platform

The resources allocated by DTU partner could not be committed in 2021. For this reason the incorporation of the surveillance data related to antimicrobial resistance and infectious disease data into a web platform (D.4.2.3) has not been carried out during Y4 and will not be done during Y5. The other partners of this task (ANSES and RIVM) propose to carry out the work related to the user guide describing how to access the data available (D.4.2.1) through the extension of the deadlines. In the same way, the two partners will propose in Y5 a guideline document to raise awareness by EU authorities of collecting relevant and high-quality data for risk-assessment (D.4.2.2). This document will be shared and presented to stakeholders. It will be then presented to the Efsa Microbial risk assessment network.

WP4-T3 Dissemination plan

No specific tasks have been carried out related to task 3 during Y4. The results of the two WP4-T1 and T2 will be shared to reach out to national authorities in charge of collecting metadata. The network European network of focal points, the Efsa MRA network will be used to disseminate the results. Among the OH-EJP partners, One Health EJP WP4 Thematic Integrative Meeting will be used for results dissemination.

5.3. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

5.3.1. Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
CARE	D.0.5	Minutes of the interim meeting - 2021	M38	M38		Public (https://zenodo.org/record/4836030#.YS4bjo4zZaQ)	1 (Adm)
CARE	D.1.2.1	WP1-T2-ST1: Report - Pilot Isolation/detection of pathogens	M48		M53; delivery delayed due to persons responsible for the task changing positions and/or leaving	Public (a draft report has been uploaded to the OHEJP CARE website)..	
CARE	D.1.2.2	WP1-T2-ST2: Report - Pilot on typing/characterization including WGS	M48		M54	The delay was caused by a hacker attack at DTU in November 2021. A lot of data are being moved to new servers.	
CARE	D.1.2.3	WP1-T2-ST3 Pilot on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data	M48		M54	The outbreak pilot is based on WGS data from strains from real outbreaks. This means that it had to be ensured that the sequence data could be traced back to patients (GDPR-rules). The legal department at SSI have been overloaded with other assignments and was delayed in granting the permission to conduct the study.	
CARE	D.2.2	Sub-database for antimicrobial resistances	M48		M52	The sub-database is pending collection and analysis of WGS data results	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
CARE	D.2.3	A need assessment document stating what RM we should have	M40	M40		Public (https://zenodo.org/record/4836054#.Yek2pv7MKUk)	2
CARE	D.3.1.3	Searchable online RMs catalogue	M46		M50	This deliverable has been delayed due to difficulties in gathering information on the RMs .	
CARE	D.4.1.2	The establishment of connection of this CARE activity with the databases and initiatives already in place	M45		M47	Public The deliverable will be the minutes of the meeting with stakeholders scheduled for January 2022	8
CARE	D.4.1.3	Report on analyzed survey data regarding the quality and accessibility	M42	M43		Public (https://zenodo.org/record/5882651#.Yek9yP7MKUk)	5
CARE	D.4.2.1	User Guide for accessing relevant data for risk-assessment	M54			Public The resources allocated by DTU partner could not be committed in Y4 and Y5. The other partners of this task propose to carry out the Y4 work related to the user guide describing accessing relevant data for risk-assessment (D.4.2.1) in Y5.	3

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
CARE	D.4.2.2	Implementation of developed strategy to raise awareness by EU authorities	M54			The resources allocated by DTU partner could not be committed in Y4 and Y5. The other partners of this task propose to carry out the Y4 work related to the strategy to raise awareness on data sharing (D.4.2.2) in Y5.	2
CARE	D.4.2.3	Web based exchange platform including antimicrobial resistance surveillance data.	M48			The resources allocated by DTU partner could not be committed in Y4 and Y5. The development of D.4.2.3 (web-platform) is cancelled for that reason.	

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

5.3.2. Milestones

JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from 2020 AWP (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
CARE	M.0.2	Interim meeting 2021	M37	Yes	-	Held in M38 (3-4 February 2021)
CARE	M.2.2	Consensual list of identified gaps	M45	Yes		Each partner has received info about his list of proposed strains, some contacts still ongoing
CARE	M.3.2.1	Training session on microbial collection management	M52			MOOC (https://www.fun-mooc.fr/fr/cours/biobanking/)
CARE	M.3.2.1	Training session done	M52			
CARE	M.4.1.5	Letter to take contact with JIP/EJP project	M37	Yes	-	ANSES and RIVM have contacted the listed project leaders in the deliverable D.4.1.3
CARE	M.4.1.6	TC of the different partners of this project to check for synergy and to avoid duplication of the work	M45	Yes	-	All the identified project leaders have been contacted to present the CARE WP4's objectives and to get their outputs on data sharing. The stakeholders' views have also been gathered during presentation of D.4.1.3
CARE	M.4.2	Data typology and description methodology	M38	No	-	This milestone is no longer relevant as WP 4.2 objectives have been revised

JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
CARE	M.4.2	Data gaps and accessibility analysis	M40	No	-	This milestone is no longer relevant as WP 4.2 objectives have been revised
CARE	M.4.2	Inventory of existing data visualization tools	M45	No	-	This milestone is no longer relevant as WP 4.2 objectives have been revised

5.4. Publications and additional outputs

No scientific publications.

Additional output

- Presentation on the One Health EJP- Online welcome meeting March 3rd, 2021. Cross-sectoral framework for quality Assurance Resources for countries in the European Union (CARE) Proficiency testing and Reference Material. M. Torpdahl.
- Presentation on the One Health EJP CPD Module 2021 Feb. 2021 “rStrainSelect: an R-tool for sampling strains based on metadata in a One Health context Laurent Guillier, French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES)”
- Posters prepared and accepted for presentation at the OH_EJP ASM 2021:
 - ✓ “EJP-OH-CARE: Pilot studies to support guidance and suggestions for cross-sectoral One Health proficiency testing schemes”. Authors: Jeppe Boel, Nick Coldham, Sally Hallam, Paula Johnson, Pernille Gympose, Mia Torpdahl, Elina Lahti, Cecilia Jernberg, Rene Hendriksen, Kees Veldman, Mike Brouwer. Poster at the OHEJP ASM meeting in Copenhagen, Denmark, June 9-11, 2021
 - ✓ “Cross sectoral quality assurance systems, an inventory”. Authors: Lucas Wijnands and Kirsten Mooijman. Poster at the OHEJP ASM meeting in Copenhagen, Denmark, June 9-11, 2021
 - ✓ “Identification of data currently used in quantitative microbial risk assessment”. Authors: Juliana De Oliveira Mota, Henk Aarts, Laurent Guillier, Virginie Desvignes. Poster at the OHEJP ASM meeting in Copenhagen, Denmark, June 9-11, 2021
- EUROpanel OH: Construction of a CARE catalog of Bacteria Foodborne Pathogens Strains used as Reference Materials in the European Union. Authors: Anne Brisabois, Olivier Chesneau, Valeria Michelacci, Forum Shah, Michel-Yves Mistou and the OH-EJP CARE consortium.
- Poster presentation at the SFM (Société française de microbiologie) in Nantes, 22-24 September 2021: EUROpanel OH: Construction of a catalogue of foodborne pathogenic bacterial strains that can be used as reference materials in the European Union. Michel-Yves Mistou (1) Olivier Chesneau (2), Forum Shah (1), Valeria Michelacci (3), Anne Brisabois (4), and the OH-EJP CARE consortium. (1) *MaIAGE INRAE, France*; (2) *CIP, Institut Pasteur, France*; (3) *EURL E. coli, ISS, Italy* (4); *Direction des Laboratoires, ANSES, France*.
- The presentations of the CARE annual meeting have not been made publically available - only the minutes from the meetings are available via the OHEJP website: <https://onehealthjep.eu/jip-care/>
- Presentation on one of the relevant datasets for risk assessment identified in WP4. e-Agrostat 2021 16th Agro-Industry and Statistical Methods congress. De Oliveira Mota et al. “The Third French Individual and National FoodConsumption (INCA3) Survey 2014–2015 and data for microbiological risk assessment: Models for domestic refrigerator temperatures”

Outcomes

Yves Pascal D. VAN DER STEDE (EFSA), Marius Linkevicius (ECDC) and Daniel Palm (ECDC) are all kept in the loop in relation to communication that goes out from EJP CARE, i.e., are informed of activities and also invited for any relevant meetings. A meeting was held in September with WP4 member and

J. Takkinen from ECDC to present WP4 outputs. Another meeting with EFSA Microbial risk assessment network was also done in October 2021.

EJP CARE has good communication with the EJP Matrix and the EJP OH-HARMONY-CAP projects and intends to plan and execute the closing meeting in collaboration with these projects.

5.5. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor intra-project relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	Yes
Other risks (please describe)	No

Additional information

Some delays in work plan execution as well as to duties, tasks and reporting have been observed but also addressed by extending the deadline for the deliverables. Three new partners have been enrolled EJP CARE in 2021. Other risks are being mitigated.

6. JIP4 – OH-HARMONY-CAP

6.1. Summary of the work carried out

OH-HARMONY-CAP (One Health Harmonisation of Protocols for the Detection of Foodborne Pathogens and AMR Determinants) is a 3-year project that aims to: 1. Collect information on current capabilities, capacities, interoperability, and adaptability at both the National Reference Laboratory (NRL) and the primary diagnostic level, across Europe by developing an in-depth OHLabCap survey. 2. The quantitative description of current and best practices and the development of harmonised protocols will identify and possibly close the gaps and suggest future studies on how to best detect and characterise food borne pathogens across the One Health sectors.

This summary will include an overview of the various outcomes and agreements going forward, such as what was decided on the two consortium meetings held in Y4:

- We have applied for a no-cost project extension so the project will terminate M60 and, therefore, the AWP for Y5 was amended and shared with the consortium. Due to the changes to AWP5 participating partners will be able to test the chosen harmonised protocols
- M54-M60 will focus on dissemination, scientific reporting, publishing, participating in conferences, networking and, of course, presentation of scientific results
- We have welcomed three new partners so that the OH-HARMONY-CAP consortium presently comprises 18 partner institutes across 14 countries
- The 59 question OHLabCap was launched in May 2021 by distributing it via several networks and we asked the participants to activate their network. The survey received 122 responses. 32-FHI is analysing the responses to the OHLabCap and the preliminary data has been presented to the consortium. Instead of three dimensions and 10 targets we will use four dimensions (adaptability, capability, capacity, and interoperability) and 15 targets to quantify the data
- We have identified a gap regarding sampling and analyses that are performed on behalf of our food business operators HACCP-based self-control programmes. Therefore, we have included an additional deliverable, lead by 39-SLV, which will survey this sector. We developed and launched an anonymous nine question survey using the EUSurvey tool.
- Surveys of relevant laboratories were designed to collate key information on current characterisation practices. The relevant data was analysed by, 26-Teagasc and 21-APHA, to inform the second and third summary report on characterisation and data management. The deliverable, [D-IA.2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.3.2 \(https://zenodo.org/record/5788415#.Ye_Brf6ZOUk\)](https://zenodo.org/record/5788415#.Ye_Brf6ZOUk), has been concluded
- The evaluation of the collected laboratory protocols has been concluded and the selection of harmonised protocols is ongoing. Experts will decide on the criteria, which will be used for ranking of the protocols. The ranking activity is based on the evaluation tables deployed in JIP4-WP4-T2 and on the original protocols collected. The ranking is ongoing.
- The ranked protocols will be sent to the EURLs for comments and suggestions. Specifically, the ranked *Cryptosporidium* protocols will be sent for comments at the *Cryptosporidium* Reference Unit, Public Health Wales.

- In collaboration with MATRIX and CARE, we have launched a research topic in Frontiers Public Health “One Health Surveillance in Practice: Experiences of Integration among Human Health, Animal Health, Environmental Health, and Food Safety Sectors” as a dissemination platform in 2022
- It was agreed, that the final meeting will be held in Copenhagen September 2022 which includes a joint workshop with CARE and MATRIX

6.2. Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

6.2.1. WP1 Project coordination

JIP04-WP1-T1: Internal coordination

Progress: As part of the internal engagement, it has been important to effectively communicate the progress and status of the project to the OH-HARMONY-CAP participants. At the online Y4 kick of meeting (KOM), we communicated a common understanding of the roles and responsibilities, output specifics and expectation.

- Several emails to all participants with project overview, status, and decisions
- Frequent conference meetings between the project leaders of WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP5
- Three conference calls with OH-HARMONY-CAP project group (WP leads and deputy leads). Including a welcome online meeting with new partners on May 27th
- Two consortium meetings; 1. online January 13th and 2. November 9-11th in Dublin, Ireland

The three new partners; The Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII), Spain, The Institute of Food Safety, Animal Health and Environment (BIOR), Latvia, and The Finnish Food Authority (RUOKA), Finland, joined the OH-HARMONY-CAP in May 2021. At the OH-HARMONY-CAP welcoming meeting (May 27th), the WP leaders presented their work packages and identified tasks where BIOR, ISCIII, and RUOKA could contribute. Following the meeting BIOR, ISCIII, and RUOKA were asked to fill in a document listing all the tasks. Consequently, all OH-HARMONY-CAP email lists and budgets have been updated to include the new partners.

Note: We moved our planned consortium meeting in Dublin, Ireland, from September 2021 to November 9-11th to increase the chance of travelling. We had a successful hybrid meeting where we went through all the current running tasks in each WP. This was presented by the WP leads and co-leads. The updated workplan for Y5 was discussed and all the upcoming milestones and deliverables for Y5 communicated. As such, we have a plan and overview for meeting our deliverables going forward.

JIP04-WP1-T2: External coordination, outreach and engagement

Progress: As part of the external engagement and to, effectively, find synergies with other projects, disseminate our project, progress and results, OH-HARMONY-CAP has participated and presented

- Arranged and participated in a meeting on possible synergies between the FWD AMR-RefLabCap
- (Food- and Waterborne Diseases Antimicrobial Resistance - Reference Laboratory Capacity) project and OH-HARMONY-CAP. January 21st, 2021
- Participated in 1st DiSCoVer Stakeholder Web-meeting. January 22nd, 2021

- Presented at OHEJP Welcome meeting to integrate new members / preparatory TC with the OHEJP Coordination team, WP4 and JIPs leaders. February 8th, 2021
- Update meeting between CARE and OH-HARMONY-CAP. February 11th, 2021
- Participated in DiSCoVer STEC meeting. March 2nd, 2021
- Participated in DiSCoVer WP2-T4 meeting. March 16th, 2021
- Update and overlap meeting between MATRIX and OH-HARMONY-CAP. April 21st, 2021
- Presented at the One Health EJP internal meeting at Statens Serum Institut (SSI) (Joint meeting between all the EJP projects that SSI is involved in). May 4th
- Hosted and presented, together with CARE and OHEJP WP4, at the One Health EJP Thematic Integrative Meeting (TIM) “EU surveillance frameworks and infrastructures in a harmonized One Health perspective”. May 21st. Note, The report was published in D4.21”
- Oral presentation (Flemming Scheutz) at One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021. June 10th
- Poster presentation (WP4, Rosangela Tozzoli, and Melanie Gay) at One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021
- Presented and participated in the panel discussion at the One Health Session for EPIET and EUPHEM, August 25th
- Stayed connected with key stakeholders; by inviting them to the TIM panel discussion and to comment on surveys and questionnaires
- Reached out to the Cryptosporidium Reference Unit, Public Health Wales for distribution, and input, of the OHLabCap
- Collaborated with other OHEJP projects, including TOXOSOURCES, MATRIX, DiSCoVer, and CARE
- Participated in the One Health EJP 8th Cogwheel workshop, September 29th
- Presented at the One Health EJP internal meeting at Statens Serum Institut (SSI) (Joint meeting between all the EJP projects that SSI is involved in). October 3rd
- Presented and participated in panel discussion at the MATRIX consortium meeting, November 22nd
- Presented at the 8th Stakeholder committee meeting of the One Health EJP, November 22nd
- Participated in the One Health EJP - Online joint meeting of Programme Managers Committee and Programme Owners Committee, November 24th

Note: A strong collaboration has been built with the management teams of JIPs, MATRIX and CARE. Therefore, throughout the year, there have been several calls and meetings between MATRIX, CARE and OH-HARMONY-CAP.

JIP04-WP1-T3: Data management

Progress: The list of data covered in OH-HARMONY-CAP DMP was specified during the first and second year of the project. DMP is a living document during the lifetime of the project. The first DMP version (D-IA.2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.1.1, https://onehealthejp.eu/?get_group_doc=126/1607675945-D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.1.1.pdf) included four research datasets. The deliverable describing the DMP is available at Zenodo. The final DMP will be published at the end of the project lifetime. The DMP was updated in January 2022 and include 23 entries.

6.2.2. WP2 Development of the OHLabCap

WP months: M25-M54. WP Leader: 13-SSI. Deputy WP Leader: 30-RIVM

WP2 participants: All OH-HARMONY-CAP participants

The aim of WP2 is to develop a benchmarking instrument “OHLabCap”, by surveying OneHealth laboratory interoperability, capacity and capability across EU. The focus will be on the detection and typing of selected priority foodborne pathogens, AMR determinants, and priority parasites across each sector (AH, PH, and FS). The main deliverable will result in the establishment of an OHLabCap instrument that is generic, adjustable and sustainable at both an EU and National level.

JIP04-WP2-T1: Development and testing of the pilot survey

Task month: M25-M30

Task Leader: 13-SSI. Deputy Task Leader: 30-RIVM

Task Participants: All OH-HARMONY-CAP participants

Progress: Concluded. Deliverable, D-IA.2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.2.1

<https://zenodo.org/record/4381330#.Yfpo1eqZNPY>

JIP04-WP2-T2: Scoring of Collected Data and Chosen Indicators

Task month: M31-M38

Task Leader: 32-FHI. Deputy Task Leader: 30-RIVM

Task Participants: All OH-HARMONY-CAP participants

Progress: Concluded. Deliverable, D-IA.2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.2.2.

<https://zenodo.org/record/4588483#.YfppGeqZNPY>

JIP04-WP2-T3: Development and testing of an adjusted survey

Task month: M37-M42

Task Leader: 13-SSI. Deputy Task Leader: 30-RIVM

Task Participants: All OH-HARMONY-CAP participants

Task description: The outcome of JIP04-WP2-T2 will generate several recommendations, which will be incorporated into the pilot survey in order to develop the OHLabCap.

Progress: Several modifications to the pilot survey was undertaken and incorporated into the OHLabCap survey:

- Continue with the EUSurvey tool as a survey platform
- The number of target parasites includes the top 5 highest ranked foodborne parasites: *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)*, *Echinococcus multilocularis*, *Toxoplasma gondii* and *Trichinella* spp.
- Questions targeting laboratory adaptability have been included
- The survey was routed on several levels *i.e.*, organism, laboratory functionality and methods
- The classification and scoring of indicators, measuring capacity, capability, interoperability, adaptability, and communication has been clarified
- The “NA” option has been added to several questions

- The final revised tool is now able to target score distribution by discipline (human, animals, food/feed) and dimension scores (human, animal and food/feed) by country (maps)

After multiple reviews and pilot tests, the OHLabCap survey was distributed on May 7th with a July 31st deadline. The survey link was accompanied by a letter of invitation and a “how to save the survey document”. To ensure an optimal response, the OHLabCap was distributed via the OH-HARMONY-CAP consortium, Cryptosporidium Reference Unit, FWD-network, OHEJP JIPs/JRPs and the Scientific Steering Board, EURL-VTEC, EURL-Listeria, EURL-Campylobacter, and EURL-Salmonella. Concurrently, OH-HARMONY-CAP recipients were also asked to help with the distributions and circulation of the OHLabCap survey, particular outreach to in-country primary laboratories. Identifying laboratory contact points have been a challenge. The survey was concluded on August 31st and we received 122 responses.

Progress: Concluded.

JIP04-WP2-T4: Scoring of collected data and chosen indicators

Task month: M43-M54 (ongoing)

Task Leader: 32-FHI. Deputy Task Leader: 13-SSI

Task Participants: All OH-HARMONY-CAP participants

Description of the task: JIP04-WP2-T4 will evaluate, assess, and score the collected data from the OHLabCap to prepare the One Health map of the levels of system capability/capacity/interoperability/adaptability for the National reference and primary diagnostic laboratories in each of the EU/EEA countries and dissemination. The overall outcome will be an integrated One Health map of the levels of system capability/capacity/interoperability/adaptability for each of the chosen organisms for the NRLs and primary diagnostic laboratories in the EU/EEA countries. This tool will not include an evaluation of surveillance capacities and capabilities (EUEpiCap), which is included in MATRIX.

32-FHI is currently analysing the responses to the OHLabCap survey and the preliminary data was presented at the November Dublin meeting. When designing the OHLabCap we used the EULabCap as a model which applies three dimensions and 10 targets. However, the EULabCap is very broad and the OHLabCap focuses on fewer pathogens. Therefore, in order to quantify the data from the OHLabCap survey we used four dimensions (adaptability, capability, capacity, and interoperability) and 15 targets. At the Dublin meeting participants were divided into “dimension” groups to go over the results and provide 32-FHI with comments and analysis.

Progress: 32-FHI and 13-SSI expect a draft report M50 and the deliverable in M54.

JIP04-WP2-T5: Development of a survey targeting the food sectors self-control

Task month: M37-M50 (ongoing)

WP Leader: 39-SLV. Deputy WP Leader: 13-SSI and 9-BfR

Task participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 33-NVI, 35-INIAV, 30-RIVM, 44-BIOR, 45-Ruoka, 43-ISCIH

Task description: The primary aim of this task is to provide an overview of the sampling and analyses that are performed on behalf of our food business operators’ HACCP-based self-control programmes.

The rationale for this survey was that similar investigations are conducted in the framework of national monitoring programmes or as part of official investigations, that include food sampling and laboratory testing by competent authorities. However, the results obtained in these investigations differ largely from the results derived from food business operators' investigations. This survey is – to our knowledge – the first of its kind. It is expected to give a first glimpse of which food categories that are examined, the number of positive samples for each of the pathogens, and will provide information on accreditation, participation in EQA programmes and storage and/or sharing of positive samples.

We will use this information to identify gaps and needs necessary to develop and implement harmonised and compatible protocols for the detection and typing of foodborne pathogens across One Health. It is our hope that this initiative will encourage further communication between private food business operators and One Health authorities.

Like the OHLabCap, this nine-question survey was focused on the analyses of microbiological samples of the following six priority bacteria: *Salmonella* spp., *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Campylobacter* spp., Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC), *Shigella* spp. and *Yersinia* spp.; and five priority parasites: *Trichinella* spp., *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Echinococcus granulosus* (*Sensu lato*), *Echinococcus multilocularis* and *Toxoplasma gondii*.

Note: This is an additional task not described in the original work plan. However, it is described in the DMP. This task was finalised at the January 13th 2021 consortium meeting.

Progress: The survey was adapted to the EU online survey tool, drafted covering sampling and analysis performed in food business operators HACCP-based self-control programs. It was developed in the period of February to April 2021, and later distributed in the participating EU/EEA countries in the period of May to July 2021.

Interested OH-Harmony-Cap partners received a letter of invitation, and link to the survey, for the distribution to relevant food laboratories in their own countries. In the letter of invitation, it was clearly stated that participation in the survey is anonymous. Additionally, the gathered information will be; 1) included in a technical report, and 2) the results of the survey will be open source data and will be published on <https://onehealthjep.eu/jip-OH-HARMONY-CAP/>, and 3) data will not be used for commercial purposes.

The initial deadline to fill out the survey was June 25, 2021. However, this deadline was changed to July 31st to accommodate the new partners. We received 44 responses and the preliminary results were presented at the Dublin meeting. The deliverable (D-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP 2.5) will be a report in M50. Nine member states participated in the survey, obtaining an overall of 44 respondent laboratories and a draft report was sent (December 13th 2021) to participants involved in this task, asking for comments before January 14th 2022. Following this, the report will be shared within the OH-HARMONY-CAP consortium for comments. Thereafter, we will send a draft report to stakeholders for comments. The final report will also be sent to the participating laboratories.

6.2.3. WP3 One Health Laboratory Interoperability Guidance

WP months: M25-M54 (ongoing)

WP Leader: 26-Teagasc.

WP Deputy Leader: 36-INSA

WP3 Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 26-Teagasc, 27-ISS, 30-RIVM, 33-NVI, 34-PIWet, 35-INIAV, 36-INSA, 39-SLV, 40-FOHM, 41-SVA

The overall aim of this WP is to examine current and best practice in the One Health sectors (public health, veterinary & food/environment testing labs) in 'Sampling & testing', 'Characterisation of isolates' and 'Data management & harmonised reporting' including the identification of current knowledge gaps and propose new studies and/or methods to fill them. With the ultimate aim of providing guidance for the development of a more efficient and harmonised system the following issues are being addressed:

Sampling and testing

current and best practice in designing statistically based sampling plans
the most appropriate sampling methods
currently available testing (detection) methods
how these are applied
the latest technologies/technological developments

Strain characterisation

- current routine strain characterisation in Europe
- gaps in strain characterisation that are inhibiting food safety regulation/policy in the EU
- recommendations on what typing methods, AMR and virulence gene testing, etc. should be undertaken as part of a future harmonised approach to strain characterisation
- recommendations on how this harmonised strategy should be implemented

Data management

- current used data management systems in Europe
- a harmonised data management system for the future
- recommendations on how this system should be implemented (hard ware, software, motivating MSs, etc.).
-

For the purposes of this work, four target pathogens were selected including:

1. Shiga Toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC)
2. Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC)
3. *Cryptosporidium*
4. AMR for *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*

JIP04-WP3-T1: Sampling and Testing

Task month M24-M36

Task Leader: 26-Teagasc. Deputy Task Leader: 36-INSA

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, , 27-ISS, 30-RIVM, 33-NVI, 34-PIWet, 35-INIAV, 36-INSA, 39-SLV, 40-FOHM, 41-SVA

Progress: Concluded. Deliverable, D-IA.2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.3.1

<https://zenodo.org/record/4381374#.Yf00-eqZNPY>

JIP4-WP3-T2: Characterisation

Task month M37-M48

Task Leader: 21-APHA. Deputy Task Leader: 36-INSA

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 26-Teagasc, 27-ISS, 30-RIVM, 33-NVI, 34-PIWet, 35-INIAV, 36-INSA, 39-SLV, 40-FOHM, 41-SVA

Task description: The primary aim of this task is to establish what characterisation of the target pathogens is performed in public health, veterinary and food/feed/environmental testing laboratories throughout the EU. A secondary aim is to harmonise this work to ensure the data required for food safety policy development and more efficient risk assessment/management is supported in the future.

Progress: A survey of relevant laboratories throughout the EU was undertaken in the previous period using a questionnaire, which was designed to collate key information on current characterisation practices in these laboratories. The relevant data from this questionnaire was analysed for the summary report, which forms the deliverable for this task. Teams of participants collated this information (JIP4-WP3-T2S1). This output was combined with information from a literature review, focusing on recommendations contained in relevant EFSA Opinions, FAO reports, etc and the expertise within the project team to draft the summary report, covering; 1) current routine strain characterisation (typing, AMR & virulence gene testing) in Europe; 2) gaps in strain characterisation that are inhibiting food safety regulation/policy in the EU; 3) typing methods, AMR & virulence gene testing as part of a future harmonised approach to strain characterisation and 4) how a harmonised strategy should be implemented.

Task concluded. Deliverable, D-IA.2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.3.2

<https://zenodo.org/record/5788415#.Yf0PceqZNPY>

JIP4-WP3-T3: Data Management

Task start month: M46 (ongoing)

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: 26-Teagasc. Deputy Task Leader: 36-INSA

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 26-Teagasc, 27-ISS, 30-RIVM, 33-NVI, 34-PIWet, 35-INIAV, 36-INSA, 40-FOHM, 41-SVA

Description of the task: This task aims at describing harmonised reporting including foodborne pathogen data management within individual MSs and data transfer to EFSA and ECDC.

Sub-task WP3-T3-ST1 (M46-M50): The responses to the questionnaire (sub-task WP3.T1.S1) will be used to establish current data management practices with individual MSs and how this data is communicated to EFSA and ECDC.

Sub-task WP3-T3-ST2 (M49-54): Experts from data management companies will be invited to present their data management systems to a panel of personnel (with relevant experience) from within the project and external experts (eg. personnel in EFSA and ECDC who collate and analyse this data).

Recommendations will be developed on the best practice that should be used to form the basis for a harmonised system for recording, storing and transferring data with the EU.

The deliverable will be a summary report (drafted by the WG but reviewed by all project participants) describing; [1] currently used data management systems in Europe; [2] a harmonised data management system for the future and [3] recommendations on how this system should be implemented (hard ware, software, motivating MSs, etc.).

Note: Work has commenced on task 3 and it was also discussed during the Dublin meeting in November. In the period under review the questionnaire data was analysed and drafting of the report, which will cover currently used data management systems in Europe and the design, development and application of harmonised data management and reporting throughout the EU, has commenced.

6.2.4. WP4 Harmonisation of Protocols

WP months: M25-M50. WP Leader: 27-ISS. WP Deputy Leader: I-ANSES

WP participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 27-ISS, 32-NIPH, 30-RIVM, 33-NVI, 34-PIWet, 35-INIAV, 36-INSA, 39-SLV, 40-FOHM, 41-SVA, 44-Bior

The aim of WP4 is to produce recommendations on how to harmonise the methodology for the detection and typing of the model pathogens. These pathogens will be selected as examples for the project's purposes, and identified candidates include Shiga toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC), enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC) and *Cryptosporidium* and AMR for *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*. The strategy and the approaches adopted in the framework of WP4 activities may be transferred to other pathogens, enabling harmonisation of methodologies in use in the EU/EEA laboratories

JIP4-WP4-T1: Collection of the Laboratory Protocols for Model Organisms

Task start month: M25-M33

Task Leader: 27-ISS. Deputy Task Leader: I-ANSES

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 27-ISS, 32-NIPH, 30-RIVM, 33-NVI, 34-PIWet, 35-INIAV, 36-INSA, 39-SLV, 40-FOHM, 41-SVA, 44-Bior

Progress: Concluded.

JIP4-WP4-T2: Evaluation of the Collected Laboratory Protocols

Task month: M31-M39

Task Leader: 41-SVA. Deputy Task leader: 1-ANSES

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 27-ISS, 32-NIPH, 30-RIVM, 33-NVI, 34-PIWet, 35-INIAV, 36-INSA, 39-SLV, 40-FOHM, 41-SVA, 44-Bior

Task description: Evaluation of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing of selected foodborne pathogens, including STEC, ETEC, *Cryptosporidium* and AMR for *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* in use in the laboratories operating in public health and veterinary sectors. The information about the methodologies applied in the EU/EEA laboratories will be circulated among the WP4 participants and will be assessed with the purpose of identifying differences and similarities in the methodological approaches applied in the different laboratories. This will be the basis for the definition of harmonised protocols.

Progress: The evaluation of the protocols collected was initiated as scheduled and finished on M39. In particular, the activities of this task concerned the evaluation of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing of selected foodborne pathogens, including STEC, ETEC, *Cryptosporidium* and AMR for *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* in use in the laboratories operating in public health and veterinary sectors. This primary evaluation would be the basis for identifying similarities among the protocols applied and for the definition of harmonised procedures.

The task has been subdivided in three subtasks:

WP4-T2-S1: Evaluation of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing of pathogenic *E. coli* STEC/ETEC

WP4-T2-S2: Evaluation of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing for AMR *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*

WP4-T2-S3: Evaluation of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing of *Cryptosporidium*

Three groups consisting each of about four to six experts in pathogenic *E. coli*, *Cryptosporidium* and AMR, participating in OH-HARMONY-CAP project, have been formed, with the aim of facilitating the comparison of the procedures collected in the framework of task JIP4-WP4-T1. To do so, evaluation tables have been deployed by task JIP4-WP4-T2 leaders and agreed within the groups of experts, to aid the primary assessment of the protocols. The following protocols have been evaluated:

WP4-T2-S1: 53 protocols STEC/ETEC

WP4-T2-S2: 10 protocols for AMR *Campylobacter* and 9 protocols for AMR *Salmonella*

WP4-T2-S3: 18 protocols for *Cryptosporidium*

Three evaluation tables corresponding to each subtask have been produced and stored in the same folder with the original protocols received, which will be an important output to be used in the JIP4-WP4-T3.

This task has been concluded.

JIP4-WP4-T3: Ranking and choice of laboratory protocols

Task months: M39-M50 (ongoing)

Task Leader: 34-PIWet. Deputy Task leader: 1-ANSES

Task description: The aim of this task consists in choosing and proposing harmonised protocols. To do so, experts participating in WP4 will be enrolled for the ranking of the procedures collected and preliminarily evaluated in JIP4-WP4-T2. The major outcome and impact of this task will be the proposal for harmonised procedures for the model microorganisms evaluated in this WP, namely Shiga Toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC), Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium* and AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*.

WP4 participants has been enrolled in the preparation of the protocols according to their area of expertise. They will rank and evaluate the harmonised laboratory protocols for the detection and typing of "model organisms". The protocols has been distributed to the Medical and Veterinary Laboratories participating in the WP4 and those who participated in the collection of the protocols (JIP4-WP4-T1). Further, the EURLs were involved in WP4 task 1 when asked to reach their networks for

the collection of protocols. In WP4 task 3 subtasks on pathogenic *E. coli* and *Cryptosporidium* there are experts from the relevant EURLs. Moreover, once the proposed procedures will be available, they will be shared with the Directors of the EURLs too to make them available in the networks

Progress JIP4-WP4-T3 takes place in Y4 as scheduled, and particularly in M37-M48. The WP4 leads, JIP4-WP4-T3 lead, and the project leader discussed (June 8th) the possibility of prolonging this task to M50 due to the pandemic. This has been updated in the annual work plan Y4 and Y5. The outcome of this task will be used directly in JIP4-WP5-T3, which is dedicated to practical workshops and E-learning on the harmonised protocols.

Since the beginning of Y4, three meetings have been held among WP4-T3 leader, co-leader, WP4 coordinator and OH-HARMONY-CAP coordinator, to discuss the roadmap of this task. Moreover, a specific meeting with WP4 participants was held in M40, to discuss the progress of the WP activities and to present the outcomes of JIP4-WP4-T1 and JIP4-WP4-T2 and, further, decide on the criteria, which should be used for the ranking of the protocols. In particular, the strategy put in place to rank the protocols collected consisted on defining indicators to assign scores to the different methods, and a ranking table was prepared. Small groups of experts were enrolled for each of the target microorganism, with the aim of refining the ranking table also in consideration of the characteristics of each microorganism and testing it. In particular, indicators such as sensitivity and specificity, as well as aspects such as duration of the analysis, easiness in implementation, equipment required, were taken into account for assigning the scoring. Currently, the ranking of the methods for detection and typing of ETEC and STEC (a total of 53 protocols evaluated), *Cryptosporidium* (18 protocols in total) and AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* (18 protocols overall) is expected to be concluded in M49 within the team of WP4 experts participating in each subtask, with the support of the evaluation tables prepared in WP4 task 2 and on the basis of the original protocols received in WP4 task 1. Our aim is to have the proposed harmonized procedures available for a pre-test and provide them for the training sessions organized in Y5 in WP5.

NOTE: Challenges and lessons learned in WP4-T3 – Cryptosporidium

The public health importance of *Cryptosporidium* is high and the parasite ranked among the top five parasites in the EU (Bouwknegt M, et al 2018). Despite the major public health implications, there is no normalised/ standardised method that can be applied to test for *Cryptosporidium*.

The WP4 T3 task aimed to evaluate the existing methods used in the *Cryptosporidium* test in the area of Public Health (PH), Animal Health (AH) as well as Food and Feed Safety (FS). This task was carried out based on the results of WP4 T2. As part of this task, 11 research protocols on *Cryptosporidium* were evaluated. The protocols were sent mainly by the National Reference Laboratories as well as by the European Union Reference Laboratory. The team's work began in March 2021 with the aim to develop tools for the evaluation of research protocols. Scoring tables were used for evaluation and the following criteria were taken into account: Specificity, Sensitivity, Method recognition, Ease of implementation, Equipment and facilities, Manhours, Analysis duration, Sample collection and storage (including transport), Flexibility (Can the targets used in the method easily be changed), Number of critical control points, Complexity/preparation of sample, Proficiency testing programs, Commercial kit, Accredited method, Ease of result interpretation and finally Comparability of results across the OH sector. The collected methods were divided in subgroups according to their principles : Sample preparation, Microscopic detection, Detection by PCR and Typing.

To check the effectiveness of the developed evaluation tool (scoring table), the following exercise was performed: a group of six experts from the following Institutes: EURLP, ANSES, BIOR, ISS and PIWet was selected. Each subgroup of methods areas was assessed independently by 2 experts. And the collected results were discussed at a working group meeting in Dublin in November 2021. The obtained results were discussed among most parasitologist partners from WP4. While discussing the results of the exercise, it was pointed out that there are gaps that hinder the proper assessment of the methods. The provided protocols were very diverse in terms of the contents of the method description. Some of them were complete and contained additional information, such as validation results, others were weaker in the description and did not allow to fill in all criteria. Sometimes even the aim of the protocols and/or the use by the laboratories were not really clear. The diversity of the content of the protocols was a significant obstacle in their assessment by specialists.

Lesson learned: While discussing the results of the evaluation, the partners realized that asking for protocols was not sufficient to be able to rank and compare them afterwards. They concluded on the need to build a questionnaire to be joined to the protocol request. This will allow for a much easier and more precise evaluation of the methods.

As such, this questionnaire should include questions about the matrix, method validation - and the results of validation, accreditation, participation in PT research and more. The application of microbiological standards is often impossible and impractical for parasites. These observations apply not only to the methods used in the *Cryptosporidium* study but also to other non-standardised methods used in diagnostics and surveillance.

Lesson learned: During the discussion, a significant difficulty was indicated in recommending one method that could be used for various purposes only based on the evaluation results obtained. In December 2021, a meeting was held, where it was established that due to the specificity of this parasite, which is found in various matrices, in infected humans or animals faeces, in soil, food, water, wastewater, contaminated surfaces or other sources, and to the variety of methodology depending on the needs and the direction of research for medical, veterinary, inspection, diagnostic, monitoring, surveillance or confirmatory purposes it is not possible to use one universal test method for all purposes. This exercise clearly showed the role and importance of a diagnostician in the research process. Therefore, at the December meeting, the role and importance of training in the diagnosis of *Cryptosporidium* were emphasized.

Lesson learned: During the December meeting, it was agreed that the developed method evaluation tables may be useful in selecting the method implemented in the laboratory, however, it must be preceded by an analysis of the assumed goals and applications. 41-SVA stressed the importance of applying One Health approaches to the investigation of *Cryptosporidium* as a zoonosis. Especially pointing to the role and importance of the person deciding the direction of the study and using the method, since cryptosporidiosis, has a relatively short incubation period (5–7 days), quick appropriate investigation and proper decision are important.

The importance of the experience of the person performing this test is of particular importance for the final result. Therefore, rather than applying scoring results, training and decision tree might be helpful in the selection of diagnostic methods. Consequently, and unlike the other model organisms, the

outcome of WP4-T3 for *Cryptosporidium* will not be a ranking table but a decision tree on which method to apply depending on the matrix, the aim and capabilities.

6.2.5. WP5 Training sessions on harmonised protocols

WP5 leader: 27-ISS. Co-Leader: 13-SSI.

WP months: M40-M60 (ongoing)

WP5-T1 participants: All OH-HARMONY-CAP participants. WP5-T2 participants: All CARE, OH-HARMONY-CAP, and MATRIX participants. WP5-T3 participants: 13-SSI and 35-INIAV

The aim of this WP consists in increasing EU capacity to deal with foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats across the One Health interface through partner-to-partner delivery of training. The training will provide opportunities for better communication, knowledge exchange, and knowledge integration within the One Health interface, and not just for the OH-HARMONY-CAP participants. As such, two workshops will be held during the final meeting in Copenhagen.

JIP4-WP5-T1 Facilitation and communication of the OHLabCap and T2 Joint workshop between CARE, OH-HARMONY-CAP, and MATRIX

Task months: M40-M57 (ongoing)

Task Leader: 13-SSI. Co-leader: 27-ISS

Task participants: All OH-HARMONY-CAP participants

Task descriptions: A workshop for communicating and discussing the outcome of the OHLabCAP survey and the joint meeting between the three joint integrative projects, CARE (IA2.1), OH-HARMONY-CAP (IA2.2), and MATRIX (IA2.3) and the joint research project DisCoVer

Progress: the planning of the workshop for communicating and discussing the outcome of the OHLabCAP survey conducted in the framework of WP2 (T1) and the joint meeting between the three integrative projects, CARE (IA2.1), OH-HARMONY-CAP (IA2.2), and MATRIX (IA2.3) (T2) have started. The project leaders of all three projects have agreed to postpone the exit meeting until September 2022. The meeting will be organised by 13-SSI in Copenhagen, week 38. The first meeting to plan the two workshops is scheduled for January 13th, 2022.

JIP4-WP5-T3: Practical workshops (S1) and e-learning activities (S2)

Task months: M40-M60 (ongoing)

Task Leader: 27-ISS. Co-leader: 13-SSI

Task descriptions (*JIP4-WP5-T3S1*): Three practical workshops, focusing on the model organisms (STEC, ETEC, *Cryptosporidium*, and AMR for *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*) considered in this project, will be held at ISS and SSI.

Task descriptions (JIP4-WP5-T3S2): Development of *e-learning* activities dedicated to the application of the harmonised protocols developed in WP4 on a set of foodborne pathogens.

Progress: Two meetings (February and September 2021) have been held between the WP5 leader, co-leader, WP4 coordinator and OH-HARMONY-CAP coordinator to plan out and discuss the practical workshops. The following was agreed:

- The practical workshops will be held M54-M60
- Webinars based on presentations and videos, with emphasis on the critical control points (CCP) of the harmonised method/s. It was suggested to develop a common template (ex: ISO standards, SOPs) to be applied to all harmonized protocols developed in WP4. The webinars will be delivered before the practical training, with the aim of eliciting the participant interest. We will aim at inviting EURLs and PH-NRLs
- Presentations and videos on the harmonised protocols to be published on a dedicated web-page on the OHEJP web site (with the help of the communication team), in order to disseminate the project achievements.
- All the training delivered will have a final step of assessment of the achievement of the learning objectives.

The above was presented at the Dublin meeting for feedback and discussion from the meeting participants:

- E-learning sessions, it would be very useful to make them available prior the onsite training events.
- Video-tutorials anticipating the contents on the on-site trainings and describing the harmonized procedures will be prepared and used to deploy e-learning tools for the dissemination of the harmonized protocols, which would be constituted of some theoretical and practical explanations.
- It would be preferable to anticipate crucial parts of the lab procedures, by means of video-tutorials or other e-learning tools before the participation in person to the practical workshops
- The possibility to enrol professional film-makers will also be evaluated.

For the practical workshops the following has been agreed:

- The trainings will consist on three days of laboratory activities on the application of the harmonised procedures developed in WP4.
- Four participants in two separate rounds will attend to this training (in total 8 participants)
- Training course for AMR determination. Held at 13-SSI (Copenhagen, Denmark)
- Training course for pathogenic *E. coli*. Held at 27-ISS (Rome, Italy)
- Training course on *Cryptosporidium* detection and characterization. Held at 27-ISS (Rome, Italy)

Based on WP4-T3 for *Cryptosporidium*, it was agreed, that the training will be conducted on the most common matrix (fecal infected samples) used for the detection. Furthermore, the test samples will be processed in parallel with one of the conventional microspic assay and with a molecular procedure that leads to the identification and typing of the specific isolate. The choice of the specific protocols to apply in the training course will be based on harmonized protocols selected by the WP4 expert group. Moreover, the latest findings on molecular methods originated from the OHJP-PARADISE project on *Cryptosporidium* will be considered to propose an updated molecular method for detection and typing.

Note: As of September 2021 Tosini Fabio, 27-ISS replaced Patrizia Rossi as WP5 leader.

6.3. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

6.3.1. Deliverables

JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
OH-HARMONY-CAP	D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.2.2	Technical report of the survey results	38	38		https://zenodo.org/record/4588483#.YJt4wldxc2w (public)	2, 4, 6
OH-HARMONY-CAP	D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.2.3	Adjusted survey	42	41		10.5281/zenodo.5464722 (public)	2, 4, 6
OH-HARMONY-CAP	D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.2.5	Food sector survey	42	42		10.5281/zenodo.5465061 (public)	2, 4, 6
OH-HARMONY-CAP	D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.3.2	List of methods used to characterised pathogens	48	48		https://zenodo.org/record/5788415#.Yf0PceqZNPY (public)	2,6

** Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);*

6.3.2. Milestones

JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
OH-HARMONY-CAP	M-IA2.2. OH-Harmony-Cap.5	WP3-T2 completed	46	Yes		
OH-HARMONY-CAP	M-IA2.2. OH-Harmony-Cap.6	Assessing protocols for detection and typing of the selected foodborne pathogens	39	Yes		

6.4. Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Characterization of Clinical Escherichia coli Strains Producing a Novel Shiga Toxin 2 Subtype in Sweden and Denmark Microorganisms 2021 Bai X Characterization of Clinical Escherichia coli Strains Producing a Novel Shiga Toxin 2 Subtype in Sweden and Denmark supplementary Microorganisms 2021	Yes	November 17 th , 2021	
Characterisation of atypical Shiga toxin gene sequences and description of Stx2j, a new subtype	Yes	Submitted to JCM and in revision	

Additional output

At the OHEJP ASM 2021 two OH-HARMONY-CAP WPs were disseminated; 1) Oral presentation “OH-HARMONY-CAP: Development of an OHLabCap tool” (Flemming Scheutz, 13-SSI), and 2) poster presentation “Collection of protocols for the detection and characterisation of Shiga toxin-and enterotoxin producing Escherichia coli (STEC/ETEC), Cryptosporidium spp. and antimicrobial resistance in Salmonella and Campylobacter” (Rosangela Tozzoli, 27-ISS and Melanie Gay, 1-ANSES)

Outcomes

First, the development of the first OHLabCap tool using the EU online survey tool is in itself a major achievement, which is open for adaptation by other key stakeholders in the OH field such as FAO and WHO, who are conducting similar surveys. The inclusion of private food operators and laboratories in the mini survey of this project is – to our knowledge - the first of its kind and could potentially represent an improvement in the communication between the private sector and One Health authorities. Both parties could benefit from the results. The involvement of these stakeholders could in return serve as inspiration for the further development of tools intended to measure the dimensions and targets in the OHLabCap tool (D-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP 2.4, M54).

Second, the proposed harmonised procedures will have an impact either in the activities of this project, as they will not only be the subject of training sessions, but also represent methodologies available to the scientific community through the dissemination of the WP4 results. The strategy designed in WP4 for ranking protocols can represent a tool that may be applied, following ad hoc remodulation, for the definition of fit-for-purpose procedures for microorganisms other than those considered in this project.

Third, the e-learning sessions will represent an important outcome, being available also for a large public far beyond the project’s participants. In fact, these video documents will be published on the OH-HARMONY-CAP website to ensure the maximum dissemination of the contents and impacting in the transfer of knowledge to a larger scientific community.

Fourth, the results of OH-HARMONY-CAP will improve One Health interoperability across NRLs on three target areas: Sampling & testing, characterisation, and data management & harmonised reporting. By identification of gaps, the project supports best practices to detect and characterise foodborne pathogens across the One Health sectors. Surveillance strategies can then be adjusted based on the developed guidance for improvement of One Health interoperability across NRLs. From a societal point of view, OH-HARMONY-CAP contributes to the decrease of AMR burden and of exposure to foodborne zoonotic agents through improved surveillance, diagnosis and data analysis.

Finally, all the work packages have underlined the importance of being able to adjust and adapt to the ongoing and ever-changing challenges in the field of microbiology.

6.5. Contacts and co-operation with national or international projects, organisations (e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), networks, or national ministries

A strong collaboration has been built with the management teams of JIPs, MATRIX, CARE, and OH-HARMONY-CAP. The three projects are participating in annual/interim meeting sharing knowledge and progress on the projects. OH-HARMONY-CAP had presentations at both the MATRIX online consortium meeting November 22nd and the CARE online meeting, September 24th. Planning of the collaborative final meeting has been taking place and will be at SSI in week 38, 2022 and will include all involved partners from MATRIX, OH-HARMONY-CAP and CARE.

A joint venture application has been made for hosting the third One Health CPD–module with the theme, Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests in the fall of 2022. Furthermore, OH-HARMONY-CAP, CARE and MATRIX are preparing a thematic call for original publications, whether research, perspectives, or policy, in the domain of integrated One Health surveillance. This call will be launched in the Journal Frontiers in Public Health and we expect the call to open early in 2022. We hope that this call might collect some of the intermediate achievements of the OHEJP JIPs OH-HARMONY-CAP, CARE and MATRIX with a special focus on the integrative aspects of the projects' methods and strategies.

On May 21st, OH-HARMONY-CAP co-hosted a Thematic Integrative Meeting (TIM) “EU surveillance frameworks and infrastructures in a harmonized One Health perspective” in collaboration with JIP CARE and OHEJP WP4. More than 80 people participated and the meeting concluded with a panel discussion with representatives from ECDC and EFSA. A set of questions, as agreed by CARE and OH-HARMONY-CAP, were sent to the panel in advance and they included:

Do ECDC, EFSA and the Commission see the outcome of the Joint Integrative Projects (JIPs) as a part of an EU strategy going forward?

What are the plans for OH networks on the organisms that are targeted in OH-HARMONY-CAP and CARE?

In general, how do we further coordinate with WHO and FAO?

How will ECDC, EFSA and the Commission use the output from the JIP's? Are there any plans for sustainability?

Does the EU have plans to develop a bacterial/parasitological analytic manual for diagnostics?

If so, will it be done in a OH-health environment?

There was a wide agreement, that there is a need for a continuation of the activities performed in the JIPs. Further, there is support from ECDC representatives for activities needed to implement the results (JIP outcome). Specific actions could be considered such as, implementation projects, including developing electronic support systems, training sessions and on site guidance. Importantly, The OH-HARMONY-CAP WP5 is dedicated to the dissemination of results and we are very aware of the need for sustainability measures.

Collaboration with EURLs and the PH-NRLs includes ongoing sharing of outputs, reports, meeting minutes allowing the opportunity for these stakeholders to suggest and comment on activities related to the OH-HARMONY-CAP project.

6.6 List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	Yes
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	Yes
Lack of commitment of partners	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor intra-project relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	Yes
Other risks (please describe)	Yes

Additional information

Since the planning of the project, the OH-HARMONY-CAP group has proactively identified, assessed, responded, and managed key dependencies and risks.

Selected Key Risk	Mitigation
COVID-19 pandemic	Flexible workplan to work around potential delays
Low workshop in-person attendance	E-learning
Low response to the adjusted survey	Proactive email and other communications
Unclear survey questions	Mini pilots and quality control prior to launch
Loss of key staff	Deputies nominated for all key tasks, group work

7. JIP5 - MATRIX

7.1. Summary of the work carried out

JIP05-MATRIX (here below MATRIX) is an EU-co-funded project within the framework of the One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP). It aims to advance the implementation of One Health (OH) surveillance in European countries, by identifying and extending existing cross-sectorial programmes including animal health (AH), public health (PH) and food safety (FS). Currently, nineteen partners from twelve European countries constitute the MATRIX Consortium².

During the reporting period of this document – month-37 (M37) to M48 – the major achievements of the project included:

- Finalizing a review of commonalities and differences of various surveillance frameworks in AH, PH, and FS and identifying recommendations to adapt existing frameworks into a common sectorial framework for AH, PH and FS
- Mapping surveillance chains for the MATRIX hazard tracks (HT) i.e. *Listeria*, *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, and emerging threats including Hepatitis E
- Reviewing available evidence about output based surveillance within the AH, PH and FS sectors and completing internal inventories of relevant surveillance methodologies among MATRIX partners
- Finalizing a report on the necessary criteria to evaluate OH capacities and capabilities for integrated surveillance and developing a benchmarking tool to characterise, monitor and evaluate OH capacities and capabilities (EU-EpiCap tool)
- Initiating the design of a roadmap for integrated OH surveillance (OHS); adapting and extending the *OHS Codex: The Knowledge integration platform* to the MATRIX objectives and scope; continuing training and dissemination activities
- Initiating the design of user-driven dashboards for collaboration and decision making in OH surveillance
- Continuing to ensure that MATRIX work encompasses relevant pathogens by pairing the activities of Work Packages with that of HTs

In 2021, MATRIX demonstrated an excellent response to the negative impact that the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic had on the project as originally planned. The MATRIX Consortium revised the original Work Plan according to a 6-month extension, as per instructions received by the OHEJP Coordination Team.

² MATRIX i) reviews available national and multi-national One Health Surveillance (OHS) frameworks, linking across animal health, human health and food safety sectors; ii) spreads cross-sectorial best-practices for data collection and analysis, and dissemination of surveillance results; iii) develops guidelines for the design, implementation and evaluation of official controls within the food sector using output-based standards; iv) develops a benchmarking tool for characterizing, monitoring and evaluating OHS capacities and capabilities (EUEpiCap); v) designs a roadmap for the development and implementation of national OHS, considering differences across countries; iv) creates dashboards of OHS inputs and outputs with a focus on possible pitfalls and biases in multi-sectorial data analysis. Finally, MATRIX encompasses four hazard-specific tracks that cross all activities: *Campylobacter*, *Salmonella*, *Listeria* and emerging threats (including antimicrobial resistance).

With the 6-month extension MATRIX can now i) properly benefit from the results produced by other EJP projects, which were also extended; ii) expand the synergies and links among the different WPs and sectors, which is at the core of the project's aim, and therefore achieve the project's objectives under the best possible conditions.

In January 2021, the National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark (12-DTU Food) left the MATRIX Consortium. Despite the scientific loss related to the specific DTU Food expertise in FS, the Consortium managed to take over the related activities. This was the second withdrawal of a partner institute from MATRIX since the project started.

On the other hand, a new partner, the Finnish Food Authority, Ruokavirasto (45-RUOKA), joined the OHEJP and specifically the MATRIX project Consortium in June 2021.

In 2021, MATRIX activities caught up with the project's initial plans and, given the continuous availability of the expected resources including the 6-month extension, the project's objectives can be achieved.

7.2. Work carried out in the JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

7.2.1. WP1: Existing frameworks and OH capacity

JIP05-WP1-T1: Generate an inventory of existing frameworks for surveillance of inter-sectorial hazards, by sector (AH, PH, and FS)

The task does not span the reporting period of this document. The task is completed. However, during the whole time of MATRIX, the inventory will be updated to capture new surveillance systems. The related deliverable D-WP1.1 Report on the commonalities and differences of the different operational frameworks in Animal Health (AH), Public Health (PH), and Food Safety (FS) was submitted as per deadline in M36 (https://zenodo.org/record/5062548#.Yff9k_uZOUk). The report was updated in Year 4 (June 2021) with new available evidence from MATRIX partner institutes, and was then made public via the Zenodo platform.

JIP-MATRIX-WP1-T2 Generate suggestions for adaptation of existing frameworks into a common sectorial framework (AH, PH, FS) which can support surveillance of inter-sectorial hazards (OHS)

This task is ongoing. The objective of this task is to provide recommendations in the form of a guideline to adapt existing sectorial frameworks into one common system for AH, PH and FS. The task focusses exclusively on data mechanics, by which we mean the flow of data from collection through to database storage, then analysis and finally interpretation. Data from WP1-T1 and two further activities within this task (i.e. literature review and quantitative interviews) will inform the guideline development. As part of the literature review task we have systematically searched the available scientific and grey literature for articles relating to OH and surveillance (more details on search terms can be provided). Papers (n=1590) were then screened by a pre-defined and prescriptive process to identify suitable candidates for data extraction. Data pertinent to the guidelines are now being extracted from the selected literature. For each selected paper, if a clear OH surveillance system is identifiable, details of a contact are collected in anticipation of inclusion in the interview task described next. We will deepen our understanding of factors that support successful implementation of OH surveillance systems from

existing frameworks, by conducting qualitative interviews with representatives of existing or previously existing systems. The interview guide has been drafted and is in the process of finalisation following work-package member and outside project expert consultation. The interviews are scheduled to begin March 2022.

In addition, MATRIX partner institutes are sharing information on existing OH surveillance systems, with a focus on relevant hazards (*Listeria*, *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, emerging threats, including antimicrobial resistance), and the mechanics of data flow. This work is conducted in close collaboration with WP5 (literature review), WP4 (interviews), WP2 (guidelines). Altogether, the activities and tasks described above will inform the content of deliverable *D-WP1.2 Description of a common framework for OH surveillance*. The deliverable was originally expected by M48. Following the 6-month extension of the project, the new deadline in the Annual Work Plan (AWP) Year 5 is M54.

JIP-MATRIX-WP1-T3 Evaluation of the sectorial frameworks, for specific inter-sectorial hazards – M49-60

The task does not span the reporting period of this document.

7.2.2. WP2: Best-practices and multi-sectorial collaboration

JIP5-WP2-T1: Mapping of the surveillance chain across all sectors for each hazard-track

The task originally did not span the reporting period of this document. The mapping started in Year 3 (2020) and continued in Year 4 (2021), since additional countries have been involved at a later stage. Per each HT, including Hepatitis E (chosen as the emerging pathogen of interest), a specific food chain was selected to explore in detail the different realities. Twelve online questionnaires were implemented based on the “farm to fork” approach for the three sectors AH, PH and FS, and each hazard-food chain combination. Surveillance activities in place were investigated in at least two countries for each combination. *Salmonella* was investigated in humans and pork meat; *Listeria* in humans and dairy products; *Campylobacter* in humans and poultry meat; Hepatitis E in humans and wild boar meat. Answers were categorized in order to be graphically displayed i.e. events, actors, data, metadata, event producing data, identified data sources, and sharing potential. Categorized answers represent the starting point for the identification of cross-sectorial linkages across surveillance chains. At the moment, the following countries have been investigated: i) *Salmonella* in humans and pork meat, in France, Spain, Germany, Norway and the United Kingdom; ii) *Listeria* in humans and dairy products, in Norway and Italy; iii) *Campylobacter* in humans and poultry meat, in France, Norway and Germany; iv) Hepatitis E in humans and wild boar meat, in Portugal, The Netherlands, Italy and Norway. Results from this task are regularly presented in the Consortium and WP specific meetings, and shared to contribute to the work of WP1, WP3 and WP4.

JIP5-WP2-T2: Identify cross-sectorial surveillance chain linkages, particularly, which outputs should be shared and how they should be shared for OH orientated decision making

The task was completed in December 2021 (M48). Building on the work done and the information collected about maps of integrated hazard-food surveillance chains in MATRIX WP2-T1 during Year 3 (2020), this task identifies cross-sectorial linkages for integrated OH surveillance systems. A workshop

was conducted among MATRIX partners to explore the dynamics of information sharing among sectors. The workshop explored the following hazards and countries: i) *Salmonella* in Germany and France; ii) *Listeria* in Norway and the Netherlands; iii) *Campylobacter* in Sweden and Denmark; iv) Hepatitis E in Italy; v) *Sars-CoV-2* in the United Kingdom. An outcome to highlight was that information was mainly shared during outbreaks in all participating countries, and that information including datasets are not publicly available resources in some countries. The results of the workshop also inform the purposes of WP2-T3, WP5-T1 and WP5-T2. The deliverable *D-WP2.1 Mapping of the surveillance chain for all hazard tracks, and cross-sectorial linkages* was originally expected in M36 and it was then postponed to M42 during Year 3 (2020). In May 2021, MATRIX requested to postpone it by 6 months to December 2021 (M48), which was granted. The deliverable was finalized as per deadline in M48 and it was reviewed by the project Consortium during M49 before being submitted to Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/record/5970164#.YgDXZZaZOUm>).

JIP5-Task: WP2-T3: Propose best-practice guidelines and effective strategies for data collection, analysis, and dissemination aimed at multi-sectorial OH collaboration, for each specific hazard-track

The task is ongoing. This task develops best-practices for multi-sectorial collaboration and puts OH surveillance into practice, also addressing the limitations related to data sharing, data analysis, interpretation and dissemination of outputs. The work in this task is hazard specific i.e. *Listeria*, *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* and Hepatitis E. Case studies are being developed based on the findings of WP2-T1, WP2-T2 and the related hazard-country combinations. The deliverable *D-WP2.2 Suggested best-practices for multi-sectorial collaboration in order to achieve OHS, hazard-specific (hazard tracks)* was originally expected in M48. Following the 6-month extension of the project, the new deadline in the AWP Year 5 is M54.

JIP-MATRIX-WP2-T4 Identify commonalities across the tracks, to propose a common OHS framework when applicable – M46-60

This task initiated at the end of 2021 and the related operational meetings are currently being organized. *D-WP2.3 Common framework of OHS* was originally expected in M54. Following the 6-month extension of the project, the new deadline in the AWP Year 5 is M58.

7.2.3. WP3: Output-based surveillance evaluation

JIP5-WP3-T1: Inventory of previous work and current practice

The task does not span the reporting period of this document. However, WP3 has been heavily impacted by the turnover of key personnel during 2020, including the WP leader. Therefore, activities related to this task continued being implemented during the reporting period of this document. No deliverable is attached to this task. A review of evidence (both peer-reviewed and grey literature) about output-based surveillance within the three sectors AH, PH and FS is now informing the work of other tasks in the WP.

JIP5-WP3-T2: Identification of operational partners and stakeholders

The task is ongoing. The originally planned stakeholder mapping exercise was delayed due to the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic and Avian Influenza, as this WP is primarily implemented by partners working in the AH sector. However, this task spans the entire duration of MATRIX and the delay should not affect its outcome. This task uses input from the RISKSUR project (about risk-based surveillance systems) and from the SIGMA project (about stakeholder mapping). The WP aims to set up specific case studies about *Salmonella* in pigs (AH, PH and FS) and *Echinococcus M.* (AH – domestic and wildlife, PH) but these have not initiated, yet. No deliverable is attached to this task.

JIP-MATRIX-WP3-T3 Selection of appropriate output-based surveillance systems – M37-54

The task is ongoing. Participating partners have identified appropriate output-based methodologies according to the specific objective of the surveillance system they have selected i.e. Salmonella in layer flocks (21-APHA), Salmonella in pigs (41-SVA), Salmonella Dublin in cattle (University of Copenhagen), SARS-CoV-2 in companion animals (31-WBVR) and Echinococcus M. in red fox and stray dog populations (34-PIWET). Deliverable D-WP3.1 Report on the output-based surveillance system selection methodology for each country and as many of the approaches as possible was originally expected in M48. Following the 6-month extension of the project, the new deadline in the AWP Year 5 is M54.

JIP-MATRIX-WP3-T4 Development of evaluation strategies for surveillance systems based on output-based metrics – M40-60

The task is ongoing. This task initiates amidst the reporting period of this document and is in consequence affected by the aforementioned delays. This task is looking at strategies to evaluate the effectiveness of surveillance systems within the three sectors: AH, PH and FS. Participating partners are reviewing the appropriate output metrics that are to be used to develop a country-specific standard for evaluation. Deliverable D-WP3.2 Combined report for all subtasks within the development of output-based metrics was originally expected in M54. Following the 6-month extension of the project, the new deadline in the AWP Year 5 is M58.

7.2.4. WP4: Benchmarking tool for characterising, monitoring and evaluating OH capacities and capabilities (EUEpiCap)

JIP5-WP4-T1: Review of existing methods for surveillance systems evaluation

The task is completed. This task was delayed during Year 3 (2020) and eventually produced the expected deliverable as per plans in M39: D-WP4.1 Report on the selected set of criteria for evaluation of epidemiological capacities for One Health surveillance (<https://zenodo.org/record/4750976#.Yff-ufuZOUk>). The task reviewed existing OH evaluation tools, identifying indicators that are common across the different tools. Inspired by the EU-LabCap approach, the EU-EpiCap tool is structured with three dimensions and four targets per dimension (Figure 1).

Figure1 – OHEJP MATRIX EU-EpiCap tool dimensions and targets (updated from deliverable D-WP4.1)

JIP-MATRIX-WP4-T2 Development of the surveillance capacity benchmarking tool – M37-54

The task is ongoing. Building on WP4-T1, this task works to define a scoring system. An R Shiny-based interface is being developed to record data for each indicator included in the assessment. The interface will automatically generate synthetic country profile reports to facilitate the dissemination of results. The interface allows the exploration of the outcomes of the assessment(s) by way of multiple interactive visualization options. A tutorial is being created to explain how to use the tool. A questionnaire to evaluate the tool has been designed. The questionnaire is reviewed by the MATRIX consortium and experts in OH and multi-sectoral surveillance. The EU-EpiCap tool and the questionnaire are going to be piloted with AMR in Portugal, *Salmonella* and/or AMR in France, *Campylobacter* in Denmark and Hepatitis E in boar meat in Italy. Deliverable D-WP4.2 EU-EpiCap tool and tutorial was originally expected in M48. Following the 6-month extension of the project, the new deadline in the AWP Year 5 is M54.

JIP-MATRIX-WP4-T3 Application and evaluation of the tool – M49-60

The task does not span the reporting period of this document.

7.2.5. WP5 Outreach and roadmap

JIP5-WP5-T1: Perform a requirement analysis for national OH surveillance roadmaps M25-51

The task is ongoing. Due to the mutual benefits for both parties and high-level synergies between the two tasks, Statens Serum Institut (13-SSI) and the National Veterinary Institute (41-SVA) agreed to form a unique collaboration of shared leadership for WP5-T1 and WP5-T2, inviting all partners from both tasks to contribute. An initial workshop was conducted in April of 2021, which included WP1, WP2, and WP4 leaders, HT leaders, and an EFSA representative to discuss various inputs and ideas for the requirement analysis and the roadmap. The requirement analysis aims to investigate barriers and facilitators to OHS implementation at the national level and will aid in the development of a national

OHS roadmap. The requirement analysis includes: i) a review of OHEJP deliverables and outputs including JIP COHESIVE, JIP ORION, JRP NOVA, JRP ListAdapt, JRP ToxDetect and other MATRIX WPs; ii) a focused systematic literature review following the PRISMA reporting methodology; iii) an analysis of user stories collected from the participants in the WP2.2 Workshop that took place in October 2021. Deliverable D-WP5.1 Report on requirement analysis for “OHS roadmap template” was originally expected in M45. In May 2021, MATRIX requested to postpone it by 3 months to December 2021 (M48), which was granted. Then, in October 2021, MATRIX requested to postpone it by 3 additional months to March 2022 (M51), which was granted.

JIP5-WP5-T2: Develop a national OH surveillance roadmap template M37-60

The task is ongoing. Due to the mutual benefits for both parties and high-level synergies between the two tasks, Statens Serum Institut (13-SSI) and the National Veterinary Institute (41-SVA) agreed to form a unique collaboration of shared leadership for MATRIX WP5-T1 and MATRIX WP5-2, inviting all partners from both tasks to contribute. In the continuous process of scanning of new methods and outputs from other OHEJP projects, in late 2021, MATRIX identified additional synergies with the JIP COHESIVE on the topic of One Health Surveillance (OHS) roadmaps and the two projects strengthened their collaboration and exchanges. Accordingly, the activities of the MATRIX WP5-T2 were adapted. This is in line with the “OHEJP Integrative Strategy Matrix”, in which MATRIX and JIP COHESIVE are placed at each end of the strategy. By building upon the JIP COHESIVE roadmap, MATRIX will be able to come to a full circle and strengthen the continuity of the “OHEJP Integrative Strategy Matrix”. The updated AWP Year 5 describes the details of this adaptation. Therefore, this task has now put the basis for: i) evaluating and further developing the roadmap that was built within the JIP COHESIVE project; ii) organizing national systems thinking workshops (with focus on one or more MATRIX HTs per country), involving stakeholders and non-partners of MATRIX from OHEJP and beyond; iii) capitalizing the results of the requirement analysis and the work of MATRIX HTs; iv) integrating MATRIX and JIP COHESIVE work on the topic of OHS roadmaps.

Deliverable *D-WP5.2 OHS roadmap template document* was originally expected in M54. Following the 6-month extension of the project, the new deadline in the AWP Year 5 is M58.

JIP5-WP5-T3: Knowledge-Integration Platform M25-60

The task is ongoing. The development of the Knowledge-Integration Platform (KIP) is progressing in frequent task-specific meetings. In the past, it was decided to extend the OHS Codex that was developed in the JIP ORION project (<https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>). Consequently, the KIP is available as the same readthedocs-web page. To reflect the extension of the OHS Codex through the MATRIX project, we decided to rename the webpage to “OHS Codex: The Knowledge integration platform”; in the following we will refer to the KIP as OHS Codex. In general, it is planned to add relevant tools, sections, and, if needed, extend the OHS Codex framework to extend the OHS Codex. The following extensions/changes were agreed and are being implemented: (1) extend the scope and purpose, (2) add a description of the MATRIX project in the introduction of the OHS Codex, (3) update the existing principles, (4) create new sections for training materials and examples for OHS reports, (5) add MATRIX as funding, (6) add a new principle that focuses on surveillance planning and management. Changes 1 to 6 are already in the draft mode that is evaluated and added by the OHS Codex team (see for the draft mode https://docs.google.com/document/d/1W69Lcc0-5fudoex7-Gjl_BxTpQyVjxHojkUmELu1-8o/edit) and have been published in the public readthedocs

version. The collection of suggestions for resources that might be interesting to add to the OHS Codex and information (e.g. whether these suggestions were approved by the MATRIX team) are listed in a living document (<https://seafiler.bfr.berlin/f/0ad237213cb844588190/>, password: MATRIXKIP); currently, it contains 36 entries (effective 8th December 2021). This collection of resources is reviewed and new suggestions are discussed during the OHS Codex monthly meetings. This way the OHS Codex can be continuously extended and enriched.

In the past, it was decided that the OHS Codex should support the aspect of exchanging of mathematical models from different OH sectors. To accomplish that, it will be necessary that the dedicated OHS Codex section supports harmonized information exchange formats e.g. the Food Safety Knowledge Exchange (FSKX) Format (former FSK-ML, see <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/fsk-ml-food-safety-knowledge-markup-language/>). FSKX format is the basis for various tools that support in re-using and exchanging of knowledge. A dose-response model of *Campylobacter jejuni* and a source attribution model for salmonellosis were implemented and published in FSKX format. Both models are available in the Food modelling journal where they can be executed online (<https://fmj.pensoft.net/article/63309/>; <https://fmj.pensoft.net/article/70008/>) and can be made available in model repositories as well. The work on re-implementing a QMRA model of *Trichinella* in FSKX format has started. The extension of the FSKX format towards PH/OH has started. Re-implementation of existing OH models as FSKX compliant files has started with the purpose of validating the proposed PH/OH FSKX extension where the new Partner 45-RUOKA will be involved. The collection of potential use cases of the FSKX-format within MATRIX has started. Partner 33-NVI will explore the option to apply the FSKX format to annotate/share IRIDIA sequencing pipelines. Two dedicated **workshops** were organized in October 2021 to introduce the tools that support the use of the FSKX format: the RAKIP Model Repository and the FSK-Lab KNIME Extension. New training materials (videos, manuals and tutorials) were created and made available under the eLearning platform <https://bfr-elearning.de/> (Username: fsk-workshop21 Password: Matrix.2110). The *Milestone M-WP5.1 "Knowledge-platform operational"* was successfully accomplished in M42. All MATRIX partner and WPs have a key opportunity and responsibility in supporting the advancement of the OHS Codex/KIP.

JIP5-WP5-T4: Training and dissemination M25-60

The task is ongoing. MATRIX partners are contributing to enrich the opportunities for training and dissemination, which are planned in frequent task-specific meetings. No deliverable is attached to this task.

MATRIX-internal resources: video to inform the MATRIX community on demand about the FSKX format through the 9-BfR eLearning platform.

7.2.6. WP6: Decision and collaboration dashboards

JIP05-WP6-T1: Country-based Identification of existing cross-sectional OH's activities M25-36

This task does not span the reporting period of this document. However, this WP has been heavily impacted by the pandemic in Year 3 (2020), and its activities fully took off in Year 4 (2021). This task gathers information from the first round of EJP projects i.e. the lessons learned in JIP ORION regarding

multi-agency collaboration and data interoperability in OH; the documentation from JIP COHESIVE on dissemination of surveillance results; and the achievements of JRP NOVA recommending novel methods for analysis of surveillance data. The WP is also organizing monthly meetings with project partners to foster the achievement of Task 1, 2 and 3 objectives via exchanging knowledge and first-hand experiences of dashboard development and use at country level. A live document titled Decision and Collaboration Dashboards: an Inventory (<https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/>) collects the ongoing developments of the entire WP and a list of the planned, ongoing or finished dashboard projects of participating partners. An expert list of people knowledgeable in OH surveillance and in the development of dashboards is also maintained. No deliverable is attached to this task.

JIP05-WP6-T2: Defining the content needs for cross-sectoral decision and collaboration dashboards M34-60

M34-60 – The task is ongoing. Following the work in MATRIX WP6-T1, and considering the hazards of relevance to MATRIX, this task invites partners to have inter-agency discussions on the possibilities and problems that can be addressed with joint analyses and/or visualization of data. The design of cross-sectorial decision and collaboration dashboards is driven from the end user perspective, including information gaps and methodological limitations, technical and legal barriers associated with data sharing. Deliverable *D-WP6.1 User manual for construction and implementation of OH dashboards using open source tools (source codes)* was originally expected in M54. Following the 6-month extension of the project, the new deadline in the AWP Year 5 is M58.

JIP-MATRIX-WP6-T3 Technical implementation and testing of dashboards – M37-60

The task is ongoing. This task implements country-specific, cross-sectorial decision and collaboration dashboards. The deliverable of this task will be a dashboard inventory, to be used within MATRIX and hopefully beyond. A specific focus is on the sustainability of information (data usefulness and relevance) and the technical sustainability of dashboards (the used platforms). *D-WP6.2 A practical manual to the use of dashboards in OHS practice, including recommendations for sustainability* was originally expected in M54. Following the 6-month extension of the project, the new deadline in the AWP Year 5 is M58.

MATRIX Hazard Tracks

The HTs, which are a signature feature of MATRIX, ensure that the work in MATRIX is directly relevant to specific pathogens/hazards. MATRIX is actually a frame of WPs and HTs. The HTs were chosen based on the operational priorities of MATRIX partner institutes and their OH relevance. They are *Listeria*, *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* and emerging threats, including antimicrobial resistance. During the 2020 kick-off meeting, it was remarked that not all WPs specifically work on these hazards.

Hazard Track – Listeria – The HT contributed to i) the development of a questionnaire about sampling and analytical methods and capacities of *Listeria monocytogenes* in the animal, food and human sectors and collection of responses from three countries; ii) based on operational observations about OHS during Year 3 (2020), the development of checklists for best practices e.g. in outbreak management and active surveillance (MATRIX WP2); iii) a review of output based surveillance across various sectors (MATRIX WP3); iv) a review of barriers and facilitators to integrated OH systems & planning the inclusion of two new pillars to the OHS Codex/KIP i.e. sampling and management pillars

(MATRIX WP5); v) planning a *Listeria* pilot as a part of “Sykdomspulsen” in Norway, focusing on official surveillance data and selected metadata, for food and human illness cases; this activity further builds on the JRP ListAdapt protocols and experience from JIP ORION (MATRIX WP6). The HT is also following the work of MATRIX WP1 and MATRIX WP4 but no relevant activity was identified yet. The HT is also in the process of collecting and capitalizing a list of lessons learnt about the opportunities and challenges to develop OH surveillance systems that are relevant for *Listeria*.

Hazard Track – Emerging threats (including antimicrobial resistance) – The HT contributed to i) integrating AMR in the work of MATRIX WP4; AMR is described as a relevant topic also from the perspective of other hazards; MATRIX WP3, MATRIX WP5 and MATRIX WP6 offer opportunity for collaboration, too; ii) integrating Hepatitis E in the work of MATRIX WP2 and MATRIX WP4; iii) integrating SARS-CoV-2 in the work of MATRIX WP2 and MATRIX WP4, and potentially of MATRIX WP1, MATRIX WP3 and MATRIX WP5; also this work is advancing in close collaboration with the JIP COVRIN; iv) integrating *Echinococcus M.* in the work of MATRIX WP3 and potentially MATRIX WP4.

Norovirus is no longer identified as a hazard of interest to MATRIX.

Hazard Track – Salmonella – The HT continued the work initiated in collaboration with MATRIX WP2 about mapping surveillance chains for *Salmonella* in the United Kingdom.

Hazard Track – Campylobacter – The HT identified opportunities in collaborating with i) MATRIX WP1, where the surveillance of *Campylobacter* spp. is included in the package’s inventories; ii) MATRIX WP2, where a questionnaire *Campylobacter* spp. (*jejuni* and *coli*) surveillance chains was developed for the PH, AH and FS sectors and responses were collected and analysed for three countries (Task 1); the HT is also represented in WP2-T2; iii) MATRIX WP4, where the EU-EpiCap tool will be also piloted with surveillance systems about *Campylobacter* spp.; iv) MATRIX WP5, where barriers and facilitators in the cross-sectoral surveillance of *Campylobacter* spp. are considered in Task 1; v) MATRIX WP6, where the integration of *Campylobacter* spp. in the Norwegian “Sykdomspulsen” dashboard is in progress.

Figure 2 here below is a brief overview of the current links between WPs and HTs in MATRIX. Currently, not all HTs have already expressed their full potential to enrich the solutions developed by the WPs. This is an aspect of primary relevance to be addressed in the coming months to ensure a balanced representation of all HTs into WPs.

HTs and WPO initiated an exchange about the possibility to summarise the lessons learnt during the work of specific HTs into one or more webinars and/or peer-reviewed publications in view of the end of the project.

Figure 2 – MATRIX of actual (blue) and planned (orange) links between WPs, HTs and countries of coverage (as relevant) as per December 2021.

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6
Listeria		Human / Food / Animal Sector Norway, Italy, Netherlands				Norway
Salmonella		Human / Food / Animal Sector France, Spain, Germany, Norway, UK	Human / Food / Animal Sector	France		
Campylobacter		Human / Food / Animal Sector France, Germany, Norway, Denmark, Sweden		Denmark		
Emerging threat: Hepatitis E		Human / Food / Animal Sector Portugal, Netherlands, Italy, Norway		Italy		
Emerging threat: SARS-CoV-2		Animal Sector UK	Human / Animal Sector	Denmark		
Emerging threat: Echinococcus M.			Human / Animal Sector			
Emerging threat: AMR				Animal Sector France - Portugal		

Actual contribution
Follow-up/Planned

7.2.7. WP0: Coordination

JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T1 Internal coordination – M25-60

Activities included: i) managing the handover of the MATRIX leadership and vice-leadership; ii) managing the withdrawal of the partner 12-DTU Food from the MATRIX Consortium (starting on January 1st, 2021), including the redistribution of the partner activities and budget; iii) welcoming and orientating new colleagues in the Consortium e.g. after handover at partner institute level; iv) managing routine meetings with the MATRIX Consortium and the WP/HT leaders; v) supporting the routine management of WPs; vi) defining a Consortium internal procedure for the validation of the project deliverables; vii) continuous documentation/reporting of the project progresses; writing the 9-month and 12-month reports for Year 4 (2021) and revising the Year 5 (2022) Work Plan in collaboration with WP and HT leaders; viii) routine and extraordinary budgetary management; ix) ongoing housekeeping of the project webpage.

About the redistribution of the 12-DTU Food activities, this included: i) expanding the evaluation of the EU-Epi-Cap tool by 1-ANSES, 23-UoS and 13-SSI; ii) strengthening the involvement of 33-NVI in WP2-T3, WP5-T1 and WP 6; iii) expanding the work of WP3 including output-based surveillance of Echinococcus M. by 34-PIWET; iv) including a concept called "Forum for preparedness epidemiology" in the work of WP5 by 41-SVA; v) extending the work at 13-SSI in WP5-T2. The remaining budget was temporarily placed to 13-SSI for later allocation to the project consortium e.g. to support more participants to the final project meeting.

In autumn 2021, the original project proposal was reviewed and compared to the AWP Year 3, Year 4 and Year 5. Discrepancies were found among the different documents. Particularly, discrepancies were found about the Work Plan as described at pages 11-14 of the original project proposal document.

Considering this, it is important to highlight that the only documents guiding the activities of the different MATRIX WPs are the AWP Year 3, Year 4 and Year 5, in line with the related yearly budgets.

Additionally, it is worth mentioning:

The original project proposal (page 21) describes integrative missions around the MATRIX HTs but these are not mentioned in the AWPs Year 3, Year 4 and Year 5 and their related budgets. However, in consideration of the impact that HTs can have beyond the project, HTs and WPO initiated an exchange about the possibility to summarise the lessons learnt during the work of specific HTs into one or more webinars and/or peer-reviewed publications in view of the end of the project (see also here below at JIP-MATRIX-WPO-T4 Sustainability)

The original project proposal (page 21) states: “The bi-annual project meetings will have a dedicated session for participation of external stakeholders. Representatives from other projects, EFSA and ECDC will be welcomed via teleconference or physical attendance (at their own cost)”. However, MATRIX has already resources dedicated in the Year 5 (2022) budget for this, after the reallocation of DTU-Food activities. In 2022, MATRIX will consider inviting representatives from OHEJP projects (that have already ended) and/or stakeholders to the project’s Consortium meetings in Year 5 (2022) and covering for the related travel/accommodation expenses.

The original project proposal describes the project’s outputs several times using different words i.e. under “objectives description” at page 7, “primary impacts” at page 9, “progresses beyond state-of-the-art” at page 10, “project aims” at page 10, “objectives” under Annex 7 of the original project proposal at page 24.

The original project proposal often confuses with each other the concept of the European Union’s member states and the countries represented by the project’s partners.

JIP-MATRIX-WPO-T2 External coordination and communication – M25-60

Activities included: i) routine communication with OHEJP WP4 and OHEJP Coordination Team; ii) inclusion of new partners i.e. Ruokavirasto (Finland) expressed their interest to participate in MATRIX; therefore, an activity plan and an estimated budget were drafted and submitted for approval ; Ruokavirasto (45-RUOKA) is now a partner of the MATRIX Consortium; iii) communicating with other OHEJP projects (from the first and second call), and with external relevant projects and stakeholders (see below JIP-MATRIX-WPO-T4 Sustainability); iv) applying for the extension of project tasks and related deliverables (see section 3 of this report); v) applying for a 6-month extension of the project (agreed at Consortium level).

JIP-MATRIX-WPO-T3 Data management – M25-60

Within the MATRIX Consortium, the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (9-BfR) has the responsibility of the MATRIX Data Management Plan since spring 2021. Partner 9-BfR is sending quarterly reminders for updates. A continuous update of the data management plan in the CDP-tool is ongoing.

JIP-MATRIX-WPO-T4 Sustainability – M25-60

In autumn 2021, the MATRIX Consortium worked and agreed on a project’s sustainability strategy in 2022 and beyond.

MATRIX is designed in a way that most of its impact (the project’s outputs and their use) is expected after the project ends. Therefore, the impact of MATRIX is closely connected and dependent on the project’s sustainability. MATRIX develops and proposes tailored solutions for European countries that

want to advance the implementation of OHS. The project's sustainability strategy is built around these solutions (outputs) and includes 5 action points:

To support MATRIX partners in making use of MATRIX outputs. This point focuses on the MATRIX Consortium.

To pilot/disseminate MATRIX outputs among non-partners. This point focuses on subjects that are external to the MATRIX Consortium.

To produce and support the production of original peer-reviewed publications.

To continue training / dissemination activities to partners and non-partners.

To continue the advancement and use of the OHS Codex: The Knowledge Integration Platform.

Points 1-to-3 of the strategy started in autumn 2021. About Point 1, we developed a self-assessment tool for MATRIX partners to support them in the use of the project's outputs. About Point 2, we agreed on a communication strategy, in collaboration with the OHEJP Communication Team. Point 2 of the sustainability strategy addresses the original intent to reach out to so-called "non-partners" (pages 10, 17 and 18 of the original project proposal). Despite not being described in the AWP's Year 3, Year 4 and Year 5, reaching out to non-partners remains a relevant opportunity to ensure the project sustainability. It is worth highlighting that some MATRIX WPs already reached out to non-partners for the specific objectives of their work. This process can now fully progress in Year 5 (2022), when most of the project's outputs will be eventually available for piloting/dissemination.

About Point 3, together with JIPs CARE and OH-HARMONY-CAP we prepared a thematic call for original publications, whether research, perspectives, or policy, in the domain of integrated OHS. This call is launched in the Journal Frontiers in Public Health. We hope that this call might collect some of the intermediate achievements of the JIPs OH-HARMONY-CAP, CARE and MATRIX with a special focus on the integrative aspects of the projects' methods and strategies. The call is available at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/research-topics/28964/one-health-surveillance-in-practice-experiences-of-integration-among-human-health-animal-health-envi#overview>

Points 4 and 5 are rooted in the original project plan and continued throughout 2021 (see above JIP-MATRIX-WP5-T3 and JIP-MATRIX-WP5-T4). Capitalizing the lessons learnt during the work of specific HTs into one or more webinars and/or peer-reviewed publications will be part of point 4 of the strategy.

JIPs collaboration

Considering the proximity of the 3 Integrative Projects CARE (12-DTU Food, Denmark), OH-HARMONY-CAP (13-SSI, Denmark) and MATRIX (13-SSI, Denmark), a strong collaboration has been built with the management teams of JIPs CARE and OH-HARMONY-CAP to ensure a joint sustainability strategy.

The three projects are participating in annual/interim meeting sharing knowledge and progress on the projects. The three projects will also hold a joint final meeting in week 38, 2022 at 13-SSI. Representatives from the leading partners of the 3 projects also successfully applied to organise the third OHEJP Continuing Professional Development module in 2022 with a theme on "Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests". Also, point 3 of the MATRIX sustainability strategy (see above) describes another initiative among the 3 projects i.e. a thematic call for original publications in the Journal Frontiers in Public Health.

Other activities related to sustainability

The inventory created during OHEJP JIP ORION project and being updated in MATRIX WP1, has been made available as a shiny-app on the 10-FLI-website; this will be available even after the conclusion of the MATRIX project.

Continuous identification and documentation of sustainability challenges and opportunities to address them.

7.3. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

7.3.1. Deliverables

JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP1.2	Description of a common framework for OH surveillance	Originally M48; postponed to M54 (see comments)		M54	The delivery date was originally in M48. Following the request of the OHEJP Coordination Team to revise the Year 5 (2022) Work Plan according to the 6-month extension, the delivery date is now in M54	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP2.1	Mapping of the surveillance chain for all hazard tracks, and cross-sectorial linkages	Originally M36; then M42; postponed to M48 (see comments)	M48		<p>The deliverable was originally expected in M36. It was then postponed to M42. In May 2021, a request was made for its postponement until M48.</p> <p>Zenodo link: https://zenodo.org/record/5970164#.YgDXZZaZOUm</p> <p>MATRIX staff from the SVA, leader of WP2-T2 that includes this deliverable, have experienced a full turnover in the early months of 2021. This has required an adjustment of the workflow and the creation of new working methods. This happened in the general SARS-CoV-2 pandemic scenario, which is still impacting routine operations. The extension was accepted by OHEJP WP4 and it allowed for the completion of this deliverable under better conditions to ensure its quality.</p>	1, 6

JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
						By the end of M48 the deliverable was finalized and uploaded to the MATRIX webpage (project group). As per the MATRIX Consortium internal review process, the deliverable was reviewed by designated project's members in M49 before being uploaded to Zenodo. The deliverable is public.	
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP2.2	Suggested best-practices for multi-sectorial collaboration in order to achieve OHS, hazard-specific (hazard tracks)	Originally M48; postponed to M54 (see comments)		M54	The delivery date was originally in M48. Following the request of the OHEJP Coordination Team to revise the Year 5 (2022) Work Plan according to the 6-month extension, the delivery date is now in M54	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP3.1	Report on the output-based surveillance system selection methodology for each country and as many of the approaches as possible	Originally M48; postponed to M54 (see comments)		M54	The delivery date was originally in M48. Following the request of the OHEJP Coordination Team to revise the Year 5 (2022) Work Plan according to the 6-month extension, the delivery date is now in M54	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP4.1	Report on the selected set of criteria for evaluation of	M39	M39	-	Public. Zenodo link: https://zenodo.org/record/4750976#.YJuOxrVKguU	1, 6

JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
		epidemiological capacities.					
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP5.1	Report on requirement analysis for "OHS roadmap template"	Originally M45; then M48; postponed to M51 (see comments)		M51	The deliverable was expected in M45. A request was made in May 2021 for its postponement until M48, and then in October 2021 for its postponement until M51. MATRIX staff from SSI, leaders of WP5-T1, which includes this deliverable, have experienced a full turnover in the early months of 2021. This has required an adjustment of the workflow and the creation of new working methods. This happened in the general SARS-CoV-2 pandemic scenario, which is still impacting routine operations. The second request for postponement was made in order to adequately include some JIP COHESIVE input into the Task and its Deliverable. The extensions was accepted by OHEJP WP4 and it will allow for the completion of this deliverable under better conditions to ensure its quality. The deliverable will be public.	1, 6

* Categories of Integrative activities: 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities ; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

7.3.2. Milestones

JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
MATRIX	M-WP3.1	End of the first round of OHEJP projects: this will coincide with the end of the inventory and requirement analysis phase in most WPs	48	Yes		The end of the first round of OHEJP projects was extended due to the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. Therefore, MATRIX inventories and requirement analysis obtained the relevant resources directly from the projects instead of relying on the publicly available expected outcomes. A full achievement of this milestone was obtained during 2021. The milestone was achieved in December 2021. Zenodo link: https://zenodo.org/record/5992510#.YgDYGJaZOUl
MATRIX	M-WP5.1	Knowledge-platform operational	42	Yes	-	The milestone was achieved on time. The platform is operational at: https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html Zenodo link: https://zenodo.org/record/5175982#.YgDYR5aZOUk

7.4. Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Sundermann EM, Nauta M, Swart A (2021). A ready-to-use dose-response model of <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> implemented in the FSKX-standard. Food Modelling Journal 2: e63309. Doi reference: https://doi.org/10.3897/fmj.2.63309 Zenodo link: https://zenodo.org/record/4923018	Yes		Yes, 0 Euro
Sundermann EM, Correia Carreira G, Käsbohrer A (2021). A FSKX compliant source attribution model for salmonellosis and a look at its major hidden pitfalls. Food Modelling Journal 2: e70008. Doi reference: https://doi.org/10.3897/fmj.2.70008 Zenodo link: https://zenodo.org/record/5674165#.YZ5rANDMJPY	Yes		Yes, 0 Euro

Additional output

See above the list of activities covered by the JIP-MATRIX-WP5-T4 Training and dissemination.

Relevant outputs from MATRIX WP2 will be included in the Ph.D. project of an expert from 28-IZSAM, member of the MATRIX Consortium and specifically working on WP2, as a case study on the application of the OH Approach. The project focuses on case studies about the application of OH in different contexts i.e. vector-borne, food-borne and emerging diseases. The project belongs to the Ph.D. course in “Infectious Diseases, Microbiology and Public Health” at the Sapienza University of Rome (Italy).

The infrastructure for the BIOPIGEE Glossary was developed within MATRIX to support the JRP BIOPIGEE project with a website where users can filter, search and read terms and definitions created within BIOPIGEE (<https://bit.ly/3oQwbom>). See section 5 of this report for more details.

Outcomes

All the training and dissemination activities aforementioned in JIP-MATRIX-WP5-T4 Training and dissemination are relevant achievements with an impact.

All the initiatives listed in the project sustainability strategy (JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T4 Sustainability) are developed around the project’s outputs to maximise their impact. These are:

- EU-EpiCap Tool (WP4) – This is an interactive tool to evaluate the capacities and capabilities of a country for OH Surveillance. The tool will be deployed by packaging it as a downloadable application to sidestep issues with database management, GDPR, etc.
- Roadmap to develop national OHS (WP5) – This is a template that a country can use to develop OHS according to its needs and resources. The roadmap expands the work initiated in the OHEJP COHESIVE project.
- Manual to OHS dashboards (WP6) – This is a manual to support the design and implementation of OHS dashboards using open source tools.
- Guidelines for adapting existing AH, PH and FS surveillance frameworks into sectorial systems (WP1).
- Flowcharts of cross-sectorial best-practices for data collection, analysis, and dissemination of surveillance results (WP2).
- Guidelines to design, implement, and evaluate official controls within the food sector using output-based standards (WP3).

Also, under WP5, MATRIX promotes and expands:

- *Codex: The Knowledge Integration Platform* – this is a platform to establish a high-level framework to support mutual understanding and information exchange between OHS sectors.

- Food Safety Knowledge Exchange (FSKX) Format – this is a format that supports the OH community to share and re-use mathematical models as well as data analysis procedures.

7.5. On-going and planned collaborations with national or European projects or networks

Several MATRIX members were also members of the JIP ORION project, and thus they were able to transfer results and add value to them within MATRIX. MATRIX WP1 leaders were also leaders of the work package on epidemiological knowledge sharing in OH in JIP ORION. Leaders of MATRIX WP5 and MATRIX WP6 were part of an initiative in JIP ORION – called “supra-national One-health pilot” that was working closely with EFSA and ECDC to determine how the OH tools developed in JIP ORION can be applied at the European Union level. We expect this work to directly benefit the roadmap and outreach work that is being developed in MATRIX WP5.

MATRIX WP1 has been working closely together with WP2 of JIP ORION, where 10-FLI was actively involved. MATRIX WP1 is further building on JIP ORION’s OH surveillance inventories. Also, the experience of JRP NOVA is considered within MATRIX WP1-T2 through ongoing interviews. The final guidelines delivered by the WP will also be developed in collaboration with JIP COVRIN. In Germany, collaborations were continued between the MATRIX WP1 leaders (10-FLI) and OHEJP partners at 9-BfR. Furthermore, 10-FLI is engaged in different working groups and projects with EFSA, working on surveillance and different animal diseases, and EFSA, regarding their terminology and inventory variables.

MATRIX WP2 leaders have also been leaders of the JIP COHESIVE WP4 regarding a data platform to facilitate risk-analysis and outbreak control as well as deputy leaders of the JRP NOVA WP2-T1 about the availability of food purchase data and barriers. MATRIX WP2 is also collaborating with the JRP BeONE in the evaluation and implementation of national level data sharing as lead and deputy lead on several tasks. In addition, national-level collaborations were developed in France with surveillance actors: French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety, national reference laboratories on *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*; and Santé Publique France, the National Public Health Agency. These experiences contribute to work e.g. WP2-T3 lessons learnt from JRP NOVA.

In addition, the MATRIX WP2 leader is the coordinator of the SIGMA Consortium, a project funded by EFSA, which aims at finding solutions for facilitating the exchange of data between Member States and EFSA. Although the SIGMA project is limited to AH issues, the data mapping solutions and the tools under development in this project are of interest for MATRIX, as possible approaches applicable also in FS. IZSAM is also the coordinator of the EFSA Tender on OH Zoonoses. The tender aims to provide support to EFSA and ECDC in the production of the EU OH Zoonoses yearly report, in the related zoonoses online interactive data visualisation dashboards and story maps.

MATRIX WP3 connected with and received support from EFSA, which provided information on current output based surveillance within the EU and links to the EFSA catalogue browser. Additionally, WP3 have been in contact with members of the JIP COHESIVE to assess the potential of using Mendelow’s matrix for Task 2 – identification of operational partners and stakeholders.

In the framework of the MATRIX WP4, national-level collaborations were developed in France with the Food chain surveillance platform (website, in French: <https://www.plateforme-sca.fr/> - description of platform objectives and organisation), especially the research group on Salmonella surveillance. International collaborations were identified with ECDC regarding the EU-LabCap tool by JIP OH-HARMONY-CAP and with the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) regarding the SISOT (Surveillance and Information Sharing Operational Toolkit) tool. Members of MATRIX WP4 also lead activities in JIP COVRIN WP3, with significant benefits to extending MATRIX surveillance work in the area of the hazard SARS-CoV-2.

MATRIX WP5 is collaborating extensively with other projects. MATRIX WP5 member participated in the first JRP DiSCoVer Stakeholder Web-meeting and got the chance to determine potential synergies and collaboration. The extension of the FSKX format planned in WP5 is also relevant for the EJP RADAR project. In the RADAR project, a model repository was developed, which is already based on the FSKX format and we are in close communication with the responsible partners. In MATRIX WP5-T3, models compliant to the FSKX format are being implemented. Mathematical models and their exchange are relevant in multiple other EJP projects e.g. JRP DiSCoVer. The development of the FSKX format and the including metadata schema to annotate knowledge started within the research project “Risk Assessment Modelling and Knowledge Integration Platforms (RAKIP)” (<https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/rakip-web-portal/>). The RAKIP community, with partners from 1-ANSES, 12-DTU Food, and 9-BfR, continues the collaboration to improve and extend the community-driven metadata schema. The work done in MATRIX WP5 shows high potential for synergies with the work of the WHO/OIE/FAO SISOT-team (Surveillance and Information Sharing Operational Toolkit). We are in contact with the team to align the work and potentially identify reciprocally beneficial tasks. Based on the presentation held at the Cogwheel workshop in November 2020, the SafeConsume community is interested in supporting the OHS Codex and will be invited to joining upcoming meetings. The close collaboration between MATRIX and JIP ORION was continued i.e. members of MATRIX participated regularly in relevant JIP ORION calls. As the JIP ORION project finished, some JIP ORION OHS Codex team members joined the MATRIX OHS Codex/KIP steering board, which meets monthly to ensure the update and maintenance of the OHS Codex/KIP.

MATRIX WP5-T2 has established a strong collaboration with JIP COHESIVE and will continue to build upon its work on systems thinking. This task will utilize and benefit greatly from the experience and expertise of both the JIP COHESIVE project leader (30-RIVM) and the Epidemiology Department at the University of Zurich in planning and conducting several Systems Thinking workshops. These workshops will be hosted by MATRIX in various partner countries to introduce the systems thinking methodology and create an interactive platform for the mapping of the current surveillance system of a hazard of relevance in each country. WP5-T2 will also build upon the roadmap developed in JIP COHESIVE using knowledge gathered in the WP5-T1 Requirement Analysis and the various Systems Thinking workshops held.

A collaboration with the JRP BIOPIGEE was initiated. Several terms related to biosecurity measures in primary pig production were defined within the JRP BIOPIGEE project. Within MATRIX we supported the project with an infrastructure that was developed in the former JIP ORION project for the OHEJP Glossary (<https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/ohejp-glossary/>), and adapted the infrastructure to the needs of the JRP BIOPIGEE consortium. The result is an online solution to host, search, filter and access the terms and definitions defined by the BIOPIGEE consortium (<https://bit.ly/3oQwbom>).

Furthermore, it was agreed between MATRIX and JRP BIOPIGEE to place the link on the OHEJP BIOPIGEE website (<https://onehealthejp.eu/jrp-biopigee/>). MATRIX supports the JRP BIOPIGEE project to disseminate the project Glossary and to make the definitions used in JRP BIOPIGEE findable, accessible, and reusable.

WP6 deals with the creation of “data for decision dashboards”. The WP is collaborating with a similar WP in the OHEJP project JRP BeONE. The JIP ORION project has identified data sources that are already public or shared across sectors. The JRP NOVA project has built automated routines for data analyses and visualisation when trend monitoring is possible. The MATRIX project builds on these results and the experience gained through the dashboard development work to create an information centre, which will serve as a best-practice guide for OHS dashboards

7.6. Data Management Plan

1. *Have you uploaded a first version of the project’s DMP to the DMP group on the OHEJP website?*

The Data Management Plan leader attended the DMP training in September 2020 and obtained initial information of data from the WP leaders in October 2020. A draft was uploaded this data list to the DMP portal by October 31st, 2020. The DMP portal will be updated continuously throughout the Project at the minimal interval of every three months.

The deliverable D-W0.1 aim was to write an initial draft report of the DMP. It was completed and uploaded to the OHEJP-MATRIX webpage and Zenodo with minor delay in M37. It can be found here: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471349>

2. *Have you encountered any problems or difficulties when setting up and updating the DMP? If yes, please specify.*

There are some initial questions regarding the where and how our data should be listed. Integrative projects appear to have a more unusual set of data compared to Joint Research Projects. The DMP leader did receive feedback on the initial data entries at the end of December and was reviewing, editing and responding by January 2021.

7.7. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	Yes
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	Yes
Lack of commitment of partners	Yes
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor intra-project relationship	Yes
Potential entry/exit of partners	Not a risk/Yes
Other risks (please describe)	Yes

All above-mentioned are risks possible to be encountered in MATRIX.

Additional information

MATRIX has already experienced the loss of key-persons (staff and leaders), delays in the execution of the Work Plan, duties, tasks and reporting and the sudden exit of partners. These primarily happened due to the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic and surely affected the possibility for the project to express its full potential. Every time, the project showed an adequate response and resilience.

In January 2021, the National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark (12-DTU Food) left the MATRIX Consortium. Despite the scientific loss related to the specific DTU Food expertise in FS, the Consortium managed to take over the related activities. The remaining MATRIX partners efficiently redistributed the related activities and resources accordingly (see at section 2 of this report under JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T1).

Before that, partner VISAVET-University Complutense, Madrid (17-UCM) already left the project Consortium. Additionally, the originally intended collaboration with the Ross University School of Veterinary Medicine on the Caribbean island of St. Kitts never started due to the loss of key personnel. The original project members of several partners were replaced by new colleagues. This not only affected the operational aspects of the project but also the overall sense of ownership of the project. The newly developed project sustainability strategy (see at section 2 of this report under JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T4), especially with its point 1, also aims to reinforce the sense of ownership among the project's partners.

The SARS-CoV-2 pandemic reshuffled the operational relationship among WPs, and among MATRIX and other projects. The Pert chard described in the original project proposal (page 11) is today partially relevant. The pandemic also affected the way of working, making the use of digital resources widespread, while many of the originally intended physical meeting did and will not happen.

It is difficult to imagine if and when similar negative events might be faced again. In case, the Consortium has already experience to manage them.

In 2021, the OHEJP Coordination Team gave MATRIX the valuable opportunity to apply for a 6-month extension and to update the AWP Year 5 and budget accounting for that. As per February 2022, the eligibility of extra costs (i.e. costs that are additional to the original budget) after June 2022 is still uncertain.

The MATRIX Consortium works in a spirit of collaboration and openness. No conflict, lack of commitment, poor relationships or other negative experience has been reported. Maintaining the closest possible working proximity among the Consortium partners is a paramount aspect of our collaboration.

It is worth remarking here that not all HTs have already expressed their full potential to enrich the solutions developed by the WPs. This is an aspect of primary importance to be addressed in the coming months.

The entry of new partners cannot be regarded as a risk, rather it is an opportunity. A new partner, the Finnish Food Authority, Ruokavirasto (45-RUOKA), joined the OHEJP and specifically the MATRIX project Consortium in June 2021 and effectively integrated in the work of JIP-MATRIX-WP5 and JIP-MATRIX-WP6.

8. JIP6 - COVRIN

8.1. Summary of the work carried out

In Year 4 of the EJP One health and the first year of the COVRIN project a start has been made with the research work on the two main overall operational objectives: A) to identify drivers for the emergence and spread of SARS-CoV-2. B) to generate data and build models for risk assessment of SARS-CoV-2. In the management work package a sharepoint was created, a kick off meeting was held and a scoping exercise was executed to avoid overlaps with other coronavirus projects.

In the research area 1 of detection of SARS-CoV-2 in animal reservoirs and hosts, and the environment, data of SARS-CoV2 genome testing were shared and immunoassays methodologies were shared and harmonised. Approaches in the tasks on assessment of bioavailability were agreed and further developed. In work package 2 on SARS-CoV-2 characterization, genome analyses and next generation sequencing of detected isolates and metagenomic sequencing of different samples were taken forward. At least two surveys were executed to make a summary description of protocols and to make an overview of the key steps of the bioinformatics analyses. A bioinformatics ring trial was prepared to harmonise bioinformatics pipelines. Regarding in vitro and ex vivo biological characterization of circulating SARS-CoV-2 strains, cell line models have been collated and shared between partners. Animal model protocols have also been categorized and shared between partners. This will allow better analyses of virus traits related to zoonotic and/or reverse zoonotic transmission. In work package 3 on SARS-CoV-2 risk assessment and surveillance, formats/procedures for sampling and surveillance in wildlife, livestock and pets and the environment were evaluated and reported. Several workshops were organised to involve partners in the surveillance data collection. A review of surveillance activities in the different countries was produced. Risk factors for virus transmission in wildlife reservoirs, food producing animals and the environment are being studied and analyses of transmissions in pets were produced. An overview of models and parameters to assess transmission in animals was reported, all from a One health perspective. In work package 4 of COVRIN on coronavirus preparedness, isolations of virus from different wildlife species were initiated. As a start on the evaluations of the impacts on ecological factors and interventions, a report on relevant sample types and hot spots for coronavirus sampling was put together. In the coming year more work will be done on the study of virus – host interactions and on the identification of drivers of virus emergence through evaluation of phylodynamics and cross-species interactions with focus on zoonotic and reverse zoonotic aspects and adaptations. Generated data and research outcomes will be used to develop control strategies, intervention strategies and prevention.

8.2. Work carried out in the JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

8.2.1. WP0 – Coordination

JIP06-WP0-T0.1 - Internal project organisation (M40 – M63)

ST0.1.1 – Development of sharepoint for data exchange (M40 – M42)

A share-point for data exchange of the different work packages has been constructed. This sharepoint is included in the COVRIN website; a COVRIN group sharepoint that can be accessed by all researchers within the COVRIN network. Formats and procedures are discussed.

ST0.1.2 – Management reporting year 1 (M40 – M51)

Management reports drafted are uploaded on the sharepoint.

JIP06-WP0-T0.2 - Communication and reporting (M40 – M63)

ST0.2.1 – Communications reporting year 1 (M40 – M51)

The COVRIN project page and group have been set up on the OH EJP website. A comprehensive list of contact details for each work package, task and subtask has been compiled and uploaded to the secure area of the OHEJP website and is in use for organising meetings and compiling reports. Input to the twelve month report was collated from work package coordinators, and a draft version of the report was submitted to OHEJP WP4 on time. The report will be uploaded onto the sharepoint.

JIP06-WP0-T0.3 - Meetings and stakeholder connections (M40 – M66)

ST0.3.1 – Scoping exercise on related projects (M40 – M45)

The scoping exercise to avoid overlaps with other EU funded projects on Covid-19 has been completed. Deliverable D0.3.1 “Scoping review of European Union-supported COVID-19 research activities” (<https://zenodo.org/record/5537781>), and the associated database of identified COVID-19 research activities (<https://zenodo.org/record/5533808>), have been uploaded onto Zenodo.

ST0.3.2 – Organisation and evaluation of the kick-off meeting (M40 – M48)

A very successful kick-off meeting was held in March 2021. A meeting report and work package presentations have been made available to COVRIN participants through the sharepoint, and have been uploaded to Zenodo as Deliverable D0.3.2 “Report on the COVRIN kick-off meeting, 31st March 2021” (<https://zenodo.org/record/6010878>).

ST0.3.3 – Reporting mid-term (M40 – M57)

A series of regular work package meetings was started by June 2021 and all work packages have had update meetings. Several presentations of the COVRIN project were held for stakeholders, REA, SSB and PMT. A mid-term meeting, and work towards the related Deliverable D0.3.3 “Report on the mid-term meeting”, will take place in the coming year (Y5).

8.2.2. WP1 - Detection of SARS-CoV-2 in animal reservoirs and hosts, and the environment

JIP06-WP1-T1.1 - SARS-CoV2 genome detection in livestock, wildlife, pets and environmental samples (M40 – M63)

A record of available specimens from domestic and wildlife animals was initiated which revealed that there were initially low numbers of samples available to the participating labs, and these included domestic animals from households with COVID-19 diagnosed owners. However, surveys/projects are underway now in the participating COVRIN laboratories to get a better overview on the frequencies of such infections.

Activities included initiating compilation and upload of available methods and materials to the COVRIN site, for sharing among partners and contribution to deliverables:

ST1.2.1 – Evaluation of virus antigen detection in clinical samples from animals (M40 – M63)

A collection of established diagnostic protocols was set up which covered antigen detection (Rapid antigen tests (FLI, PIWET, APHA); RT-qPCR (FLI, APHA); A draft proposal for a harmonized protocol for rapid antigen test establishment and comparison was distributed for contributing partners to input and edit. The protocol database and finalised comparison will contribute to Deliverable 1.2.1 “Report on methods for virus antigen detection in clinical samples from animals”, due M63.

ST1.2.2 – Evaluation of antibody testing in livestock, companion animals and wildlife (M40 – M63)

A parallel database of established protocols for antibody detection was set up (Double antigen ELISA (IZSLER), VNT (APHA, IZSLER), Pseudotype Virus Neutralization test (APHA), INGEZIM COVID 19 S VET – INGENAZA (PIWET)). Moreover, mono- and polyclonal antibodies for use in serological assays and antigen detection tests (anti-S, anti-N; FLI, IZSLER) were generated.

As next step, an interlaboratory testing of specific samples with specified antigen detection assays is planned, to include established and novel antigen detection tests developed during the project. Results will contribute to Deliverable 1.2.2 “Report on available data from antibody testing in livestock, companion animals and wildlife”, due M63.

JIP06-WP1-T1.3 - Definition of bioavailability of virus in fomites, water and in the environment (M40 – M60)

The contributors to this important task assessing the bioavailability of the virus in various matrices have met and agreed an approach. A report outline is written and shared for feedback within the subtask group. A literature search was set up including a data charting form to collect infectivity data from other sources than available from partner institutes. Data input from research activities of partner institutes will be collected via an inventory sheet.

ST1.3.1 - Discuss the relevance of detecting SARS-CoV-2 in fomites and the environment (M40 – M60)

The relevance of detecting SARS-CoV-2 will be part of the report. Detection data can provide insight whether and to which extent different environmental routes may play a role in the human-animal transmission of SARS-CoV-2. A graphical scheme was drafted to provide an overview of various potential environmental routes that may play a role in human-animal transmission of SARS-CoV-2.

Next to the relevance of detecting SARS-CoV-2 in the environment, challenges faced by environmental sampling of live SARS-CoV-2 has been discussed during project meetings, but it needs further elaboration. The definition of bio-availability has been commented to be a term that is not (commonly) used within the field of virology. The terms infectivity or viability were suggested as better alternatives.

ST1.3.2 - Assess infectivity of the virus over time, and at different temperatures (M40 – M60)

Infectivity data of live SARS-CoV-2 from environmental sampling (field studies) is limitedly available among partner institutes. Activities of partner institutes include for example sewage water surveillance (humans), experimental SARS-CoV-2 studies on survival/decay in environmental matrices, SARS-CoV-2 transmission in animal models, environmental sampling at (mink)farms. To obtain information on infectivity of SARS-CoV-2 in environmental sources of both field and experimental studies, a literature search will be conducted. A search strategy and a data charting form have been completed. The next step is to collocate information from the literature search on detection and persistence/survival of live SARS-CoV-2, structured by environmental sample type (e.g. water, air) with information on sample location (e.g. farm, domestic pets) and/or environmental conditions (e.g. temperature, humidity). Moreover, since there is variety in detection (collection) and analytical methods that can impact the outcomes, a description of the methods will be included. An inventory sheet has been created to share with partner institutes in which they can list outcomes from their own studies.

ST1.3.3 - Comparison with RNA quantification (PCR versus live virus) to inform risk assessments (M40 – M60)

Work on this task is still to be started. A discussion on the difference in outcome of RNA and live virus detection will be part of the report outline. Detection data of live SARS-CoV-2 studies will be compared to detection data from PCR studies (obtained in T1.1).

8.2.3. WP2 – SARS-CoV-2 characterization

JIP06-WP2-T2.1 – Genome analyses (M40 – M54)

Task 2.1 is focused on the analyses of whole genome sequences of SARS-CoV-2 strains circulating in humans and animals. This involves the exchange of methodologies among partners (sub-tasks 2.1.1 and 2.1.2), as well as phylogenetic analysis and investigation of potential virulence traits (sub-task 2.1.3). In parallel, this task also aims to support the selection of strains from other work packages that may be used for downstream biological characterization in vivo and in vitro.

ST2.1.1 – Protocol repository (M40 – M45)

Within Sub-task (ST) 2.1.1 (Protocol repository), two surveys were circulated among COVRIN partners to collect the following information. 1) A summary description of the methodologies used by each partner for preparation of samples for Next-generation sequencing (NGS) and subsequent data analysis. 2) An overview of the key steps of the bioinformatics pipeline(s) used for the analysis of SARS-CoV-2 NGS data. A 'live' version of these repositories is available within the COVRIN group on the OHEJP website, being accessible for continuous consultation and update by all COVRIN participants as the project progresses. These repositories allow partners to carry out methodology comparison/harmonization and to enhance/compare their capacity to generate, analyse and interpret viral genomic data. These activities were reported under the JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN-D.2.1.1

deliverable “Report on the established website protocol repository” available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5342577>. A final and more comprehensive version of the protocol repository will be publicly released at the end of the project.

ST2.1.2 – Harmonisation of sampling and methods for NGS (M40 – M50, extended from M48)

Within ST2.1.2, a bioinformatics ring trial is being prepared to assess the reproducibility of the bioinformatics pipelines (i.e., from raw reads to consensus sequences/list of mutations) currently being applied for routine genome analyses of SARS-CoV-2 (and other coronaviruses) within the partner institutes. Ten partners confirmed their availability to participate in this exercise, which will involve the analysis of a batch of: i) 27 SARS-CoV-2 NGS fastq files obtained from distinct sample sources, using different wet-lab protocols and/or sequencing technologies; ii) five NGS fastq files obtained from other coronaviruses (optional). To accommodate constraints faced during the preparation of the ring trial and to give partners sufficient time to analyse the test dataset (this is especially important due to the current increase global workload associated with genomic surveillance of the emergent Omicron variant), the deliverable D2.1.2 “Report on the comparisons of variants and reference sample exchange” has been postponed until month 50.

ST2.1.3 – Development of an algorithm for novel virus assessment (M40 – M54)

The main activities within ST2.1.3 are planned to occur during the beginning of next year.

JIP06-WP2-T2.2 - In vitro and ex vivo biological characterization of SARS-CoV-2 (M40 – M57)

Task 2.2 is focused on the assessment of in vitro systems for characterization of SARS-CoV-2 strains. Ex vivo explants and air-liquid interphase cultures of several animal species will be infected with SARS-CoV-2. Viruses replicating in those systems will be characterized with respect to genome analysis, viral growth and host responses.

ST2.2.1 – Cell culturing (M40 – M48)

ST2.2.1 sought to investigate SARS-CoV-2 infectivity and growth in various in vitro animal cell models. To this end the availability of different in vitro animal cell models, along with the, experience and knowledge about cell line models from the different WP2 participants has been collated and shared under the JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN-D.2.2.1 deliverable “Report on cell line sensitivities – species and virus growth characteristics” available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5761026>. This deliverable consists of a database of cell models from diverse relevant species, including continuous cell lines and/or primary cell models from humans, primates, livestock species, companion animals, rodents and some bat species. Knowledge of virus host cell receptors such as ACE2 and TMPRSS2 expression in such cell lines has also been included. This deliverable will enable further development and investigations regarding the use of in vitro cell models for SARS-CoV-2 throughout the life of the COVRIN project. As with D2.1.1, a ‘live’ version of the database (living document) will be made available to the COVRIN group on the OHEJP website, being accessible for continuous consultation, updates and editing by all COVRIN participants. A final and more comprehensive version of the protocol repository will be publicly released at the end of the project.

JIP06-WP2-T2.3 – Development and optimization of animal models (M43 – M60)

Task 2.3 focuses on the development of animal models of SARS-CoV-2 infection and biomarkers analysis.

ST2.3.1 – Animal model protocols (M43 – M45)

ST2.3.1 sought to collate and share protocols, experimental designs and other methodological factors regarding the in vivo animal models in use amongst COVRIN participants for the study of SARS-CoV-2. Since the optimisation of such models is a very specialised activity this sub-task is crucial in sharing the knowledge and expertise already gained by COVRIN participants to prevent duplication and allow further improvements to meet future research questions. As such a database collating aspects such as: experimental species utilised; infection route and dose; clinical, virological and serological readouts; was created and a report describing the catalogue is shared under the JIP06-WP2-D2.3.1 deliverable “Catalogue of Animal Models” available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6011492>. It was found that whilst hamsters, ferrets and mice can be utilised for therapeutic or vaccine studies, pathogenesis studies use hamsters or ferrets given the similarity in disease profile to human SARS-CoV-2 infection.

ST2.3.2 – Pathology toolbox (M43 – M51)

Within ST2.3.2 work has been ongoing to develop, optimise and share reagents and methodologies for pathological analyses amongst the COVRIN participants. These activities have not been solely focussed on viral detection, but also in understanding the localisation of the SARS-CoV-2 receptors within host tissues of different animal species. This work was published here: <https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14232>, but is currently being expanded to assess different host receptors in a wider range of species that will be made available under JIP06-WP2-D2.3.2 “Report on pathology per species and investigative toolboxes” in early 2022. This work will further increase our understanding of SARS-CoV-2 pathogenesis in animal species, as well as enable better evaluation of the potential host range of SARS-CoV-2 in wildlife species.

JIP06-WP2-T2.4 - Analyses of virus traits related to zoonotic transmission (M49 – M63)

Task 2.4 will seek to use the outcomes of studies conducted under the first three tasks in WP2, as well as those in other work packages to analyse virus traits focussing on the potential for zoonotic and/or reverse zoonotic transmission, NGS results from virus isolates acquired from animals (i.e. livestock; pets, wildlife or zoo animals), experimental challenge studies and from already documented zoonotic and reverse zoonotic events (e.g. mink-human-mink, others) will be used to identify and map regions of interest in the virus genome responsible for these transmission events. Frequent or reoccurring mutations will be analysed in silico and experimentally regarding their ability to change virus traits (i.e., replicon system to assess viral RdRp activity, overall virion stability in different environmental conditions or fusion activity).

The majority of work that will be completed under Task 2.4 will begin in Month 50-51 and is dependent on experiments on virus traits related to zoonotic transmission are dependent on T2.2 and 2.3 that are currently being planned/conducted.

ST2.4.2 – Identification of antigenic site modifications (M49 – M57)

Work on ST2.4.2, relating to antigenic cartography of SARS-CoV-2 variants, has been able to progress utilising materials and data that were already available. Antigenic cartography is a series of techniques for quantifying and visualising antigenic relationships between antigens, based on serological titer data. In the influenza field, it is used to explore the patterns of antigenic evolution, and to help select vaccine strains each year; additionally, antigenic distances between virus variants can be compared with genetic distances, to study the molecular basis of antigenic evolution. Initial antigenic maps of SARS-CoV-2 variants, based on published serological data, have been produced for internal review. Discussions are ongoing with regards to the application of antigenic cartography to data generated by COVRIN partners. Additionally, in an informal meeting between University of Surrey (UoS) and APHA, it was proposed to compare antigenic maps for SARS-CoV-2 variants using sera from across different animal models (ferret, hamster and rabbit), as well as human sera where available, in collaboration with the Statens Serum Institute (SSI; a partner of UoS in JRP TELE-Vir). In a separate collaboration, antigenic cartographic analysis of SARS-CoV-2 variants was performed for data derived from elderly human vaccinees ([preprint available](#)).

8.2.4. WP3 – SARS-CoV-2 risk assessment and surveillance

JIP06-WP3-T3.1 - Integration of surveillance activities (M40 – M63)

ST3.1.1 – Design format and procedure for surveillance data (M40 – M45)

The format/procedure for sampling/surveillance data on wildlife, food producing animals, pets, and the environment, from partner institutes, suitable to inform risk assessment, was evaluated, see deliverable D3.1.1 “Report on the format and procedure for integration of SARS-CoV-2 surveillance data” (<https://zenodo.org/record/5541121>). Surveillance data for SARS-CoV-2 are mostly collected in a non-harmonized way between countries, and between different species and environment sites. We identified four topics to investigate: i) data requirements for the modelling in Task 3.4, ii) description of the current surveillance systems, i.e. the processes that generate surveillance data, iii) data available from EFSA (and ECDC), and at what level of aggregation and detail they are available, and iv) how to integrate different data sources.

ST3.1.2 – Collection of surveillance data (M40 – M54)

Drawing from experiences in other OHEJP projects, we decided to arrange a number of workshops, inviting collaborators across COVRIN from the partner institutes to explain the protocol, so that they can lead the surveillance data collection (Subtask 3.1.2) in their respective countries. This will ensure local expertise, to maximize data availability that can be shared, as well as internal knowledge of any approvals needed to be able to share data with the COVRIN project. Two training workshops were carried out (with the same content) in early November 2021, in collaboration with Task 3.2. Before the workshops, we distributed the protocol, in the form of deliverable D3.1.1 “Report on the format and procedure for integration of SARS-CoV-2 surveillance data” (available in [zenodo](#)), with instructions by email, to the respective country representatives. We then conducted two additional Q&A sessions over the end of November and beginning of December 2021.

ST3.1.3 – Identification of additional sources of surveillance data (M40 – M57)

For data sources identified in Subtask 3.1.3, any data that can be accessed or retrieved will be added to and integrated in the database using the same protocol from D3.1.1.

JIP06-WP3-T3.2 - Mapping of surveillance data (M40 – M63)

ST3.2.1 – Evaluation of current surveillance activities (M40 – M48)

Current surveillance activities being carried out in partner institutes are being evaluated. To collect this information, engagement with all partners was needed. Therefore, to better frame the questions and requests to the consortium, preliminary work was initiated with a focus on surveillance activities in one country, the UK. This was chosen because the Animal Plant Health Agency (APHA) in the UK is a strong and active partner in COVRIN. Outcomes from the scoping of surveillance activities in the UK is summarized in deliverable D3.2.1 “Review of surveillance activities carried out by member countries” (available in [zenodo](#)).

As mentioned above in ST3.1.2, workshops were organized to communicate the information request to partners in early November 2021, with Q&A follow-up later in the year. In particular, to help align our search, and ensure that we were capturing information of interest, we used a list of parameters which was integrated with the data request from Task 3.1, that sought to answer which institutes are: 1) in charge of surveillance steering; 2) involved in the design of surveillance protocol; 3) involved in data collection; 4) involved in laboratory analyses; 5) involved in data management and data analysis; 6) involved in result dissemination.

At the time of writing this report, a detailed list of institute involvement across the chain of surveillance activities was reported for Spain, Poland, Latvia, Sweden, Belgium, Germany and Norway; this has been included in deliverable D3.2.1 “Review of surveillance activities carried out by member countries” (available in [zenodo](#)).

JIP06-WP3-T3.3 - Risk factors for virus transmission (M40 – M63)

This task, risk factors for virus transmission, has been initiated through meetings of task leader and contributors and will be dependent on the outcomes from T3.1, 3.2 and Work package 1.

ST3.3.1 – Analyses of transmission in pets (M40 – M54)

The first point in this task has been completed; the online epidemiological survey has been designed and it is now available at: <https://forms.gle/JXwjxX1x5ULmshpmu9>. Additionally, the sampling protocol was designed. Both documents were shared with the task 3.1. The conceptual assessment of the epidemiological survey was carried out in a region of Spain with a high prevalence of SARS-Cov2 infection. In order to collect epidemiological and clinical data on family groups affected by the disease and their pets, a network of veterinary clinics has been created to provide sampling points for the pets. In order to evaluate heavily and normally exposed pets, the SARS-Cov2 affected family groups include both hospital health workers and not health workers pet owners (informed through the vet clinic network). The next WP3 meeting in Q1 of 2022 will mark the beginning of the process of disseminating the online survey and the sampling protocol to other partner groups and countries. The preliminary

findings were presented at the biannual International Meeting on Emerging Diseases and Surveillance (IMED) 2021 meeting under the title "SARS-CoV-2 in pets of infected family groups in a severely affected region of Spain", and the abstract has been selected for publication in the next International Journal of Infectious Diseases (IJID) online supplement.

JIP06-WP3-T3.4 - Models for transmission routes and risk assessment in a One Health perspective (M40 – M63)

ST3.4.1 – Listing of existing models (M40 – M45)

An overview is made of the different dynamics models and required parameters to test hypotheses regarding the role of animals as potential reservoir hosts and parameters needs. A biological information matrix was developed as standard tool to collect information for the identification and assessment of susceptible risk species. A list of existing models and required parameters that need quantification was done for deliverable D3.4.1 "Overview of models and parameters to assess transmission in animals" (<https://zenodo.org/record/5541335>). A code library is being developed and will be made available with later deliverables, once finalised. It is currently being used and shared internally with collaborators within the COVRIN project to apply for the analysis of transmission from experiments done within COVRIN or data collected from the systematic reviews.

ST3.4.2 – Reviewing transmission parameters (M40 – M54)

As part of Deliverable D3.4.2 "Systematic review report and quantification of transmission parameters for different animal species", systematic reviews (SR) were carried out to collect data and generate summaries for this biological information matrix. Three SR reviews on this topic have been finished: assessing persistence in pets (Decaro *et al.* 2021a); human-to-dog transmission (Decaro *et al.* 2021b); and assessing the risk of cat-to-cat transmission of SARS-CoV-2 (Gonzales *et al.* 2021). SR are still ongoing to assess the infection and transmission dynamics of hamsters and ferrets.

Decaro, N., Grassi, A., Lorusso, E., Patterson, E. I., Lorusso, A., Desario, C., Anderson, E. R., Vasinioti, V., Wastika, C. E., Hughes, G. L., Valleriani, F., Colitti, B., Ricci, D., Buonavoglia, D., Rosati, S., Cavaliere, N., Paltrinieri, S., Lauzi, S., Elia, G., & Buonavoglia, C. (2021). Long-term persistence of neutralizing SARS-CoV-2 antibodies in pets. *Transboundary and emerging diseases*, 10.1111/tbed.14308. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14308>

Gonzales, J.L.; De Jong, M.C.M.; Gerhards, N.M.; Van der Poel, W.H.M.(2021) The SARS-CoV-2 reproduction number R0 in cats. *Viruses* 2021, 13(12), 2480; <https://doi.org/10.3390/v13122480>.

ST3.4.4 – Reviewing of challenge experiments (M40 – M63)

As part of Deliverable D3.4.4 "Report on systematic review of challenge experiments using different host species", a SR was carried out on challenge experiments in non-human primates (Counotte *et al.* in press).

ST3.4.5 – Description of transmission characteristics in mink (M40 – M63)

Work on the analysis of the spatio-temporal transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in minks (between farm transmission) has been performed and a manuscript is being written.

8.2.5. WP4 - Coronavirus preparedness

JIP06-WP4-T4.1 - Virus-host interactions (M40 – M63)

ST4.1.1 – In vivo and in vitro studies of animal coronaviruses (M40 – M57)

Plans are underway for this task: In a number of partner institutes animal coronaviruses are being passaged in vitro and in vivo and ex-vivo in their homologous host or in alternate animal hosts, cells or tissues.

ST4.1.2 – In vitro and ex vivo studies of experimental co-infections (M40 – M63)

Plans are underway for this task: Experimental co-infections will be performed in vitro or ex-vivo and the genetic make-up of viral progeny will be investigated by deep sequencing.

ST4.1.3 – Virus isolation from wildlife (hedgehogs) (M40 – M63)

Work on the isolation of hedgehog coronavirus has been initiated. In case coronaviruses will be successfully isolated from hedgehogs, the zoonotic potential of such isolates will be assessed experimentally using models of Covid19.

JIP06-WP4-T4.2 - Drivers of virus emergence (M40 – M63)

ST4.2.1 – Analyse coronavirus phylodynamics at global time and geographical scales (M40 – M49, extended from M42)

To improve the understanding of factors affecting coronavirus genetic diversity and evolution in domestic animals and wildlife, Global time and geographical phylodynamics of animal coronaviruses are being studied. Phylogenetic relationships between coronaviruses are analyzed between animal species, and within one coronavirus species in different breeding facilities or operations.

An evaluation of potential sample types and hot spots for SARS-CoV-2 infections has been made, and a report about this has been written: Deliverable D4.2.1 “Relevant sample types and hot spots for coronavirus sampling” (<https://zenodo.org/record/5848638>). This deliverable was delayed due to a delayed start of the project and staffing issues due to COVID-19.

ST4.2.2 – Trace relevant virus mutations and recombinations (M40 – M51)

We aim to detect relevant mutations and recombination events in coronavirus isolates to gain insights into genetic variation under “natural” conditions (as compared with ST4.1.1 and ST4.1.2). Virus sequencing protocols are being evaluated and discussed.

ST4.2.3 – Evaluate the impact of ecological factors and interventions (M40 – M63)

Of the observed genetic changes we will investigate how they correlate with ecological factors (species interactions, habitat etc) and human interventions (vaccination, trading of animals), and how such factors may impact coronavirus evolution (evolution rates, composition of recombinants, possible contribution of vaccine viruses). The aim is to gain more insight into the role of ecological factors and human interventions.

JIP06-WP4-T4.3 - Virus emergence risk modelling (M40 – M63)

This task is underway following successful task leader meetings: Specific animal communities will be followed over a predefined period of time (RT-PCR, NGS) to monitor intra-community CoV genetic variation. Data from other WPs and other WP4 tasks will be used to assess the potential of CoV genetic variation on future emergences (for animal species and humans). Samplings have been started as part of a longitudinal study of genetic variation under ‘natural’ conditions (to be compared with T4.1 and T4.2).

ST4.3.1 – Follow coronavirus contaminations in bats (M40 – M60)

Samplings have been started of bat colonies in natural areas.

ST4.3.2 – Follow coronavirus contaminations in cats (M40 – M63)

Samplings have been started of cats in domestic environments. A monthly fecal sampling of cats and kittens under breeding farm conditions is performed to assess the impact of human interventions (link with ST4.2.3). Fecal samples are seldomly tested SARS-CoV-2 positive. Also in cats, the virus seems to be mainly transmitted through the respiratory tract.

ST4.3.3 – Follow coronavirus contaminations in wildlife (M40 – M63)

A frequent sampling of animals hosted for prolonged periods in wildlife shelters (incl. hedgehogs) is performed to assess the impact of modified interactions on the evolution of wildlife coronaviruses (link with ST4.2.3)

ST4.3.4 – Risk assessment and modelling of animal coronavirus evolution (M40 – M63)

Data from WPs 1, 2, 3 and WP4 tasks will be integrated to model which animal species / conditions offer the highest potential for future emergencies.

8.3. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

8.3.1 Deliverables

	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
COVRIN	D0.1.1	Share-point for data exchange of the different work packages	42	42		Data currently being exchanged via closed COVRIN members group on OHEJP website	3
COVRIN	D0.3.1	Report scoping exercise	45	45	-	Public The deliverable has been uploaded onto Zenodo at https://zenodo.org/record/5537781#.YVSqyprMK70 The associated dataset has been uploaded at https://zenodo.org/record/5533808#.YVSq0JrMK70	2,5
COVRIN	D0.3.2	Report Kick-off meeting (presentations)	48	49		Public https://zenodo.org/record/6010878	

	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
COVRIN	D2.1.1	Report on the established website protocol repository.	45	45	-	Public D-COVRIN.2.1.1 Report on the established website protocol repository Zenodo	2
COVRIN	D2.1.2	Report on the comparisons of variants and reference sample exchange	48		50	Delivery date changed to accommodate some constraints faced during the preparation of a bioinformatics ring trial and to give partners more time to run the test dataset.	
COVRIN	D2.2.1	Report on cell line sensitivities – species and virus growth characteristics.	48	48		Confidential due to unpublished data Deliverable D-COVRIN.2.2.1 Report on cell line sensitivities – species and virus growth characteristics. Zenodo	2,3
COVRIN	D2.3.1	Catalogue of animal models in use, pros and cons, and designed protocol sharing and harmonisation.	45	45	-	Public https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6011492 .	2
COVRIN	D3.1.1	Report on the format and procedure for data integration.	45	45	-	Public D3.1.1: Report on the format and procedure for integration of SARS-CoV-2 surveillance data Zenodo	4

	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
COVRIN	D3.2.1	Review of surveillance activities carried out by member countries	48	48	-	Public https://zenodo.org/record/5803075#.YcWYimjPOuU	4,5
COVRIN	D3.4.1	List of existing models and required parameters that need quantification	45	45	-	Public OHEJP COVRIN D3.4.1: Overview of models and parameters to assess transmission in animals Zenodo	3,4,5
COVRIN	D3.4.2	Systematic review (SR) report and quantification of transmission parameters for different animal species.	54	54		Public Gonzales et al. (2021) Two other reviews ongoing	
COVRIN	D3.4.4	Report on SR of challenge experiments using different host species	63	54		Public Counotte et al. (2021)	
COVRIN	D4.2.1	Report on relevant sample types and hot spots for Coronavirus sampling.	42	48		Deliverable delayed due to delayed start to the project and staffing issues due to COVID-19 Public OHEJP COVRIN D4.2.1: Relevant sample types and hot spots for Coronavirus sampling Zenodo	2

8.3.2 Milestones

JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
COVRIN	JIP06-WP4-M4.1	In vitro and in vivo experiments performed	54			On target
COVRIN	JIP06-WP4-M4.2	Samples collected under farming and natural conditions	57			On target
COVRIN	JIP06-WP4-M4.3	Coronavirus evolution under experimental and natural conditions analyzed	63			On target
COVRIN	JIP06-WP4-M4.4	impact on the capacity to cross the species barrier evaluated and risk modelized	63			On target

8.4. Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Impact of animal saliva on the performance of rapid antigen tests for detection of SARS-CoV-2 (wildtype and variants B.1.1.7 and B.1.351) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetmic.2021.109243	Yes		2822
Differential susceptibility of SARS-CoV-2 in animals: Evidence of ACE2 host receptor distribution in companion animals, livestock and wildlife by immunohistochemical characterization DOI: https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14232 Zenodo Reference: https://zenodo.org/record/5795457#.YcG5QGjP3IU	Yes	No	4100
Newman, J., Thakur, N., Peacock, T.P., Bialy, D., Elreafey, A.M., Bogaardt, C., Horton, D.L., Ho, S., Kankeyan, T., Carr, C., Hoschler, K., Barclay, W.S., Amirthalingam, G., Brown, K., Charleston, B., Bailey, D., 2021. Neutralising antibody activity against SARS-CoV-2 variants, including Omicron, in an elderly cohort vaccinated with BNT162b2. medRxiv. https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.12.23.21268293	Yes	Yes, in pre-print	
Gonzales JL, de Jong MCM, Gerhards NM, Van der Poel WHM. The SARS-CoV-2 Reproduction Number R0 in Cats. Viruses. 2021; 13(12):2480. https://doi.org/10.3390/v13122480	Yes		1578
Decaro, N., Grassi, A., Lorusso, E., Patterson, E. I., Lorusso, A., Desario, C., Anderson, E. R., Vasinioti, V., Wastika, C. E., Hughes, G. L., Valleriani, F., Colitti, B., Ricci, D., Buonavoglia, D., Rosati, S., Cavaliere, N., Paltrinieri, S., Lauzi, S., Elia, G., & Buonavoglia, C. (2021). Long-term persistence of neutralizing SARS-CoV-2 antibodies in pets. Transboundary and emerging diseases, 10.1111/tbed.14308. Advance online publication. https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14308	Yes		

Additional output

Med-Vet-Net Association Workshop **Wednesday 1st of September: online workshop on SARS-Cov-2 at the Human-Animal Interface**– SARS-CoV-2 at the Animal-Human Interface COVRIN presentations:

- Wim van der Poel (WBVR) – ‘Study of SARS-CoV-2 in mink, a One Health approach’
- Gabriele Vaccari (ISS) – ‘Circulation of Coronaviruses in wild animals in Northern Italy’
- Sophie Lepoder (ANSES) – ‘Epidemiological role of domestic animals in SARS-CoV-2 transmission: where are we?’
- Richard Delahay (APHA) – ‘Assessing the risks of SARS-CoV-2 in wildlife’
- Joe James (APHA) – ‘Tools to study SARS-CoV-2: Virology, Serology and Animal Models’
- Elodie Monchatre-Leroy (ANSES) – ‘Intranasal type I interferon treatment in the SARS-CoV-2 hamster model’
- Fabian Lean (APHA) – ‘The pathology of SARS-CoV-2 and tools to study host range’
- Rachel Taylor (APHA) – ‘A Global world: assessing the risk of human travel to the spread of SARS-CoV-2 and preparing for the next Disease X’
- Daniel Horton (UoS) – ‘Quantifying antigenic variation between SARS-CoV-2 variants’
- Paul Brown (ANSES) – ‘Genome evolution of the coronavirus IBV depending on immune status: considerations for SARS-CoV-2 vaccination’

UK-International Coronavirus Network Launch Event COVRIN presentations:

- Wim van der Poel (WBVR) – One Health and Zoonoses
- Sharon Brookes (APHA) – Surveillance, Detection and Characterisation
- Martin Groschup (FLI) – Surveillance, Detection and Characterisation

Recording of the event is available here: <https://www.liverpool.ac.uk/health-and-life-sciences/research/uk-international-coronavirus-network/launch-meeting/>

8.5. On-going and planned collaborations with national or European projects or networks

COVRIN cooperates with a lot of nationally funded projects in partner countries, and also with international organizations like WHO, FAO, ECDC and EFSA. Links have been established with international research networks and projects like the UK Coronavirus network, the PREZODE network and the ERRAZE project. COVRIN research outputs are reported nationally and internationally. All significant results have been reported to national Ministries and also to ECDC and EFSA as appropriate. Preliminary findings have been presented at meetings and conferences on emerging diseases (i.e. IMED 2021) The aim is to make all COVRIN results available for the entire scientific community, primarily through peer reviewed publications, and also to the general public.

8.6. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

Project number	Project name	Requirements Ethical Reviewers, August 2021	Comments Project Leaders, Sep 2021	Recommendations Ethics Advisors, January 2022	Comments Project Leaders, 2022	Recommendations Ethics Advisors, 2022
JIP06	COVRIN	Human Sample: In case Human samples will be manipulated, their source must be revealed and the relevant authorisations to obtain them must be presented;	Importance of this cannot be understated and is acknowledged. All partners handling human samples have the necessary national authority and licenses in place. Sources of samples and relevant approval will be included in the deliverable reports			

Project number	Project name	Requirements Ethical Reviewers, August 2021	Comments Project Leaders, Sep 2021	Recommendations Ethics Advisors, January 2022	Comments Project Leaders, 2022	Recommendations Ethics Advisors, 2022
JIP06	COVRIN	Animal: in Tasks 2.3 animal models of SARS-CoV-2 infection will be developed, the beneficiaries must demonstrate the implementation of the 3Rs and must present the ethical authorization to conduct the experiments in these animals;	Experiments involving animals will only be undertaken following independent ethical review and under relevant national licences. These will be explicitly stated in the relevant deliverable reports.			

Project number	Project name	Requirements Ethical Reviewers, August 2021	Comments Project Leaders, Sep 2021	Recommendations Ethics Advisors, January 2022	Comments Project Leaders, 2022	Recommendations Ethics Advisors, 2022
JIP06	COVRIN	<p>Safety: the beneficiaries must demonstrate that appropriate safety procedures have been put in place to protect the staff involved in the inoculation studies using different coronaviruses. Also, in case of the manipulation of contaminated Human samples, appropriate safety procedures must be established.</p>	<p>Work on Sars-CoV-2 requires very specialist containment facilities and partners contributing to tasks involving virus propagation and culture are only those with facilities and procedures that meeting or exceed relevant national and international standards.</p>			

8.7. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	Yes
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes- see below
Poor intra-project relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe)	No

Additional information

Due to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic as well as other factors, there have been losses of some key staff that are involved in this project across participants. Whilst all participant institutes aim to minimise the effects of these losses through within-institute redundancy and other mitigation strategies, in the event that there is a requirement to recruit new staff, the recruitments and training process can be lengthy and can lead to delays in planned work. The COVID-19 pandemic, as well as other factors (including the ongoing European epizootic of high pathogenicity avian influenza) may also result in a delay to the execution of planned work as staff may be re-prioritised within institutes. Access to laboratories/sampling sites may also be limited due to implementation of local/national COVID-19 restrictions which also may delay planned work.